

Case Study Report:

Austrian Science Fund (FWF) –
“Early-Stage Program:
Research – Innovation –
Training”

OVERVIEW FWF CASE STUDY REPORT

This case study consists of three parts that have been produced independently. They are merged into this case study report and aim to provide comprehensive insights into activities of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF).

- Part A: Practices in FWF Board meetings (p.2-46)
- Part B: Results and Learnings from the FWF Applicant Survey (p.47-194)
- Part C: Analysis of FWF funding data (p.195-234)

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PART A: PRACTICES IN FWF BOARD MEETINGS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the H2020 project GRANteD we have investigated whether and how gender bias might occur in panel meetings. For this purpose, we conducted five case studies, with the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) being one of the five research funding organisations (RFOs) we analysed in detail.

In the policy analysis, a low risk for gender bias was identified for FWF on the level of formal gender equality (GE) policies in place (Husu/Peterson 2022). We were interested in how formal GE policies were *implemented in practice* and which risks for gender bias could be identified.

To get an insight into that we observed three FWF board meetings negotiating applications in the funding scheme ESPRIT – two virtual and one in person. ESPRIT was of specific interest as it was a newly implemented early career postdoc programme with a specific focus: In the case of equal qualifications and equal quality of projects, applications by female applicants were given priority and gender balanced funding outcomes (quota) were to be achieved.

Various practices of how to meet the quota were identified and the quota was met successfully: In each of the three observed Board meetings, the number of female and male grantees was equal. However, we found that the focus on the representation of women grantees could have limited Board members' gender awareness to numbers and less focus was put on other aspects of the assessment process, e.g. when introducing applicants by personal information (name and gender of applicant, home and host institution), which might activate (gender) stereotypes.

While analysing practices in FWF Boards, we also identified various aspects of how the FWF might contribute to further changing the rules of the game, such as strengthening reviewers' capacities to apply innovative formal policies in practice or raising awareness regarding gender and other minority groups in science, and the role RFOs can play in universities and other research performing organisations, e.g. when asking for a detailed mentoring plan for the applicant.

Based on these suggestions, various tailored recommendations were developed, which can be seen as ideal, evidence-based suggestions that need to be checked for usability in practice.

Overall, the FWF case study illustrates the challenges to get from advanced formal GE policies to advanced GE *practices*. New policies are not picked up immediately as putting formal policies into practice takes time and requires awareness and capacities.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CoI	Conflict of Interest
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
EC	European Commission
ERC	European Research Council
FFP	Frontiers for the Future Programme
FWF	Austrian Science Fund
GC	General Call
GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GiRI	Gender in Research and Innovation
IC	Informed Consent
IPD	International postdoc grant
MDPI	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NCN	Narodowe Centrum Nauki (National Science Centre Poland)
PI	Principal investigator
RFO	Research funding organisation
SFI	Science Foundation Ireland
SRC	Swedish Research Council
SRDA	Slovak Research and Development Agency

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STEM

Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

WP

Work package

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

This report was developed within the H2020 project GRANteD (Grant Allocation Disparities from a gender perspective), aiming to identify (potential) sources for gender¹ bias when allocating research grants. In WP6 of the GRANteD project, the work of decision-making bodies (panels, boards, councils) in research funding organisations (RFOs) in practice was studied in depth, based on five case studies.

One of these five RFOs is the Austrian Science Fund (Wissenschaftsfonds; Fonds zur Förderung der wissenschaftlichen Forschung, FWF). FWF was selected as a case study due to its character as an RFO with advanced formal gender equality policies in place (Husu/Peterson 2022). Broad insights were expected into the strengths, weaknesses and chances of GE policies in place for overall policy learnings and for identifying potential gender bias. Further, at the time of negotiating a collaboration with GRANteD, it was decided that FWF will give up women-only funding programmes and will instead implement a new programme for all genders, guaranteeing to allocate 50 % of all grants to female researchers ('quota'), in order to make sure that female researchers still have the same access to the science system. This was an interesting development for our analysis as well.

1.2 GRANteD case studies

In GRANteD, a case study approach was selected to be able to learn specifically from each case. Cases provide broad data which enable us to better understand social processes, practices and meanings during the assessment process. For this purpose, the focus was put on what is specific to this RFO and to the one funding instrument selected to be analysed in depth.

Case studies allow for a detailed examination of each case, while their scope is also limited (cf. Yin 2013). Instead of aiming for a comprehensive analysis, a GRANteD case study rather concerns the review processes, focusing on one specific funding instrument at a specific point in time. For FWF, the funding instrument ESPRIT² was selected for the analysis. While some parts of the analysis are only specific to ESPRIT, other parts are of general significance as they analyse general assessment practices and thus enable us to better understand the research assessment process in general. The findings describe and explore various elements and practices in the assessment process.

A qualitative research approach was applied to study the work of peer review panels. In our case studies, we addressed three overall research questions:

¹ We use 'gender' for any biological and social identities.

² For this funding instrument, FWF also provided quantitative data along the funding process, which are analysed in GRANteD WP4 and WP9 (a few of these findings can be found in the Annex of this report).

- (i) What is discussed in panels/boards, including assessment criteria?
- (ii) How are formal gender equality policies implemented in practice?
- (iii) How is decision making organised and in which way does gender become relevant in this context?

As five case studies were conducted, we had the opportunity to collect data on similar processes and to identify overall risks and challenges, but it also enabled us to compare the cases with each other (see D6.1 of the GRANteD project). While all five GRANteD case studies aim to answer similar research questions (see 2.1), each case study also aims to highlight approaches that are specifically relevant for this respective RFO.

1.3 FWF case study on practices

The FWF case study on panel practices follows the overall design of the GRANteD case studies. However, it puts a specific focus on the implementation of a quota for balanced funding outcomes as this is considered as an innovative instrument for gender equality.

The FWF case study started with a policy analysis to better understand the policy context relevant for FWF work (see GRANteD deliverable 5.1 and 5.2).

For studying practices in Board meetings, one funding programme was examined in more detail, namely the ESPRIT programme (see 3.1.1). Findings are based on observations of FWF Board meetings and interviews with Board members. Additionally, qualitative interviews with FWF staff and management were conducted to deepen the understanding from these observations.

The main aim of this specific case study is to report on key themes regarding the grant allocation process in FWF. The analysis particularly focuses on the assessment process, on the way in which excellence was discussed, on the decision-making process and on the quota at the end of the funding process. The analysis investigates these aspects from a gendered perspective, focusing on whether/when/in which way there is a risk of (gender) bias and whether/when/in which way gender equality is considered during the process.

It needs to be mentioned, however, that this case study is not an evaluation of the ESPRIT programme.

Another purpose is to use the findings for developing tailored recommendations for FWF regarding how the grant allocation process could be improved in respect to gender fairness. Some of these evidence-based recommendations address the ESPRIT programme, while others are of a more general nature.

A first target group for this case study report are FWF representatives interested in optimising this funding scheme as well as representatives from other RFOs aiming to learn from the FWF experiences. A second target group might be scholars and practitioners working on gender equality and inclusion in research funding or people involved in other initiatives to reform the research assessment process. For them, some context knowledge is included (on FWF processes, criteria; see chapter 4), in order for them to be able to put the findings on practices in context.

Chapter 2 of the report presents the broad gender equality policy context in which FWF Boards are active (2.1) and describes the funding programme ESPRIT (2.2), while chapter 3 focuses on the methodology (research background, research approach, data collection and analysis). In chapter 4, the relevant formal bodies and the formal FWF assessment are presented to provide the background for studying practices in FWF Board meetings. These assessment practices are discussed in chapter 5, which represents the core of the empirical analysis. Aggregated findings are highlighted in chapter 6, while in chapter 7, evidence-based, tailored recommendations are derived. In the Annex (chapter 9), more detailed information on data can be found.

2 CONTEXT OF THE FWF CASE STUDY ON PRACTICES

2.1 Gender equality policies in place

2.1.1 Formal GE policies

FWF has a long tradition of comprehensive gender equality policies. Accordingly, the overall risk for gender bias in FWF funding was found to be relatively low in the policy analysis (see GRANteD deliverables D5.1 and D5.2).

An FWF management representative also highlighted the decisive role of RFOs for more gender equality in science, arguing that “one of the key roles of funding organisations is to create a culture in the whole science landscape where diversity and gender equality are taken for granted” (SM-3). Further, it was stressed that FWF needs to interact with other stakeholders, arguing that “gender equality can be solved solely in the interaction between funding organisation, research institutions and policies (...). Funding organisations can set standards, this is one of their key roles” (SM-3).

The FWF gives a clear formal statement that supports gender equality: “The review of an application must not put researchers at a disadvantage for non-research-related reasons such as age, gender etc.”. To realise this function, FWF has various gender equality policies in place to build capacities internally and externally.

It was argued that for scientists who start working in FWF Boards, bias awareness trainings are available, also including gender awareness. In addition, FWF staff (heads of departments, scientific project officers, and administrative project officers) are offered general gender trainings. In case of specific needs, also individual capacity-building activities are available. For remote reviewers – who are selected individually for each proposal and each year – no gender awareness-raising activities or trainings for assessing the gender dimension in research (GiR) are offered.

Further gender policies in place are addressing applicants: In the CV, career breaks should be taken into account, also the academic (not biological) age should be reported to balance differences in career tracks by gender. Resulting differences in scientific outcomes are addressed by limiting the number of publications which can be reported in the CV to ten. In this respect it is relevant that FWF signed the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), aiming to change the research culture and forms of assessing scientific merits. A core GE policy is childcare allowance, which is available for female project leaders.

Women are encouraged to work full-time, while a lump sum is added to their salary as financial support for care costs for children aged 1 to 3. Finally, to attract more female applicants in general, special information workshops for women are organised, successful women are presented as role models and a yearly networking workshop enables women to share experiences with other women at the same career stage.

2.1.2 Mainstreaming gender – implementing a quota for gender-balanced funding outcomes

As already stated, when introducing ESPRIT, FWF pursued the goal to simplify and homogenise its funding portfolio (Schmidt et.al 2020, p. 3). Further, FWF aimed to go beyond funding programmes for women only and to introduce a new funding scheme for all genders. Prior to this decision, a data analysis on FWF grant allocation processes had shown that no overall gender bias existed (Mutz/Daniel 2022).

When the FWF launched the ESPRIT programme, an explicit target was to ensure that a sufficient number of female researchers would be granted (after giving up a women-only programme for early career researchers and mainstreaming the gender approach). For this purpose, the following gender target was set: “The FWF plans to award at least half of all ESPRIT projects to female principal investigators: In the case of equal qualifications and equal quality of projects, applications by female principal investigators will be given priority, especially in disciplines in which women are underrepresented at the FWF as principal investigators. In general, the approval rate for projects by female principal investigators must not be less than that for projects by male principal investigators” (FWF 2022, p. 17).

FWF members argued in interviews that a (binding) quota is required to achieve an impact; experiences in other funding programmes had shown that only imposing recommendations was not effective: “Recommendations are always nice, but they do not work (...) In the application of [another funding scheme] we recommend the consortium has to be a third women, but at the end it is a Consortium of men and I think there we have to implement rules and not recommendations” (SM-2).

Applying the so-called ‘gender quota’ in the ESPRIT programme was described in the respective policy document: “In order to implement the allocation of at least half of the funds per Board meeting for projects submitted by women, the following procedure is provided: (...) All A and A- cases will be approved. In order to achieve an equal distribution of the funds to be allocated, preference will then be given to women in B-cases, if necessary, especially in research areas where they are underrepresented. Is an equal distribution across the B-cases not possible, there is a determination of quotas for both sexes, women must not fall below the quota of men” (Schmidt et al. 2020, p. 7, own translation).

Further, a mandatory mentoring plan is required as part of the grant application for all applicants (all genders). Following a suggestion from GRANteD in an ex-ante policy assessment prior to the launch of ESPRIT, the mentor’s experiences and competences on equal opportunities need to be included in the mentor’s CV.

Finally, when the ESPRIT programme was launched, workshops for female researchers only were organised to attract female applicants.

2.1.3 Before implementing a quota

For this approach, multiple resistances from parts of the scientific community were articulated. As a consequence, a consultation process was set up with different stakeholder groups, explaining the arguments for introducing ESPRIT and reflecting on the preliminary design of the funding programme. One concern was that when women are compared to men, their different styles of presenting research or their CVs could lead to a biased assessment. Another concern was that if not enough women would apply this would mean for later that not enough women would be trained to become professors (SM-2). In this respect, the quota of 50 % grants being decided to be allocated to women should be a signal to female researchers to apply. Finally, an argument was raised concerning universities: It was argued that with women-only programmes, female researchers could be sure that some funding budget within the research unit can only be brought in by them, which provides a specific position in the unit.

Other concerns were raised in the stakeholder interviews that referred to the broader societal context: Giving up women-only programmes was even more challenging as a conservative government was in power which would not foster equality and inclusions. A final argument was that changes are even more demanding when people (applicants, reviewers, staff members) are not able to meet in person as it was the case in the initial phase of the ESPRIT programme due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

2.2 ESPRIT programme

The FWF funding programme ESPRIT (<https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/fwf-programmes/esprit-programme>) was first implemented in 2021. ESPRIT (Early-Stage-Programme: Research–Innovation–Training) was created to specifically target early career postdocs by merging two previous programmes – Lise Meitner and the women-only programme Hertha Firnberg – in order to have one programme for this specific target group. The aim was the following: “Through ESPRIT the Austrian Science Fund FWF offers postdocs a higher funding amount, greater flexibility in the use of funds and the opportunity to submit applications on a year-round basis”. In ESPRIT, proposals are handed in on a rolling basis and discussed in the next of the five board meetings per year.

The ESPRIT programme includes some measures to foster equality and inclusion, such as asking reviewers to take into account “breaks or delays in applicants’ research careers that have led to publication gaps, unorthodox career paths or limited international research experience” (FWF 2022, p. 24). Further, the number of publications which can be assessed is limited to ten. Finally, as FWF has signed DORA and CoARA, reviewers are asked not to use journal-based metrics, such as journal impact factors or the h-index.

From a gender perspective, the focus was put on gender-balanced funding outcomes (see more in 5.7) and mentoring for each applicants.

In November 2021, when the first ESPRIT grants were allocated, the GRANteD research team was able to observe this first online Board meeting as well as the second in March 2021 and the third in May 2021 (the latter was organised on-site)

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research background

Our approach builds on various research that has identified the main factors for bias in the context of assessing and allocating research grants (see more in Schiffbänker et.al 2023a).

The gendered composition of panels/boards is one crucial factor, reflected in EC policies aiming to achieve a 40 % quota of the underrepresented sex in decision-making bodies. While some studies confirmed that female applicants benefit from the presence of female reviewers (Van den Brink et al. 2006), others found that more female reviewers did not notably favour female candidates (Bagues et al. 2017). For FWF, Mutz et al. (2015) found evidence for a lower approval rate in case female reviewers make up 50 % or more of the reviewers.

Other bias factors refer to the assessment process and to assessment criteria: Gender scholars have highlighted various suboptimal aspects of discussing and assessing excellence in review panels (Rees 2011), referring to the way in which excellence is defined, but also to how excellence criteria are applied in panels. Heilman (2001) showed that the more ambiguous assessment criteria are, the more they open up room for individual interpretations and stereotypes, e.g. a vague definition of independence showed some gendered effects and challenges (Schiffbänker et al. 2022b). That excellence is discussed as a neutral concept, while being rather vague, can serve as 'rationalising myth' that gives way to gender-biased practices (O'Connor et al. 2020).

A different layer to gender and excellence was added when the EC and increasingly other RFOs started asking applicants to take gender into account in the design of research projects and in the analysis and interpretation of data (Fritch et al 2022), which brings about new challenges for the assessment of excellence (Schiffbänker 2023). Further research focuses on the general peer review process, its limitations (Langfeldt 2022) and potential factors for bias (Söderqvist et al. 2019). Kahneman et.al (2021) have contributed new insights in the various limitations of human decision making.

By addressing these and further bias factors, RFOs have proven already to be important drivers for improving the fairness of the assessment process and for changing the research culture (Curry et.al 2020).

3.2 Research approach

To study the work of Boards, we refer to the concept of 'practices' as "activities which are situated, corporeal, and shaped by habitus without reflection" (Poggio 2006). To better understand what is going on in FWF Boards, social practices were studied by participant observations of three Board meetings. This allowed us to investigate how panel and board members interact, negotiate and discuss "in real time and space" (Martin 2006, 258), e.g. when Board members were negotiating the applicants' scientific excellence. We want to understand in which form practices emerge and how they change (Gherardi 2012). A second source for identifying practices in Board meetings was by interviewing Board members after the meetings.

We worked with two forms of practices: general practices and practices that distinguish between female and male applicants (= gendered practices).

Against this background, the following research questions for studying practices of FWF Boards when assessing ESPRIT applications were identified:

- (1) What is discussed in FWF Board meetings? How is gender addressed in FWF Board meetings?
- (2) Which assessment criteria are applied to assess excellence and how are they applied? How is the Gender in Research dimension implemented?
- (3) How is decision making organised in practice (what is contributed by which actors), what is the role of the chair in this process?
- (4) How are formal gender equality policies implemented in practice?
- (5) How does the 'ESPRIT quota' support the inclusion of women researchers? What can we learn from ESPRIT for giving up women-only programmes for a better inclusion of female researchers?

3.3 Data collection and analysis

The used data were collected in the context of the FWF funding programme ESPRIT (see 2.2).

In a first step, exploratory semi-structured interviews were conducted with FWF staff and management representatives to get a detailed picture about procedures and policy aims and about the ESPRIT programme in more detail. To gain insight into the restructuring of the policy portfolio, also external stakeholders were interviewed (see Table 1 below).

The main data were derived from observing the FWF Board meetings in November 2021 as well as in March and May 2022, when the ESPRIT applications were assessed for the first few times. Due to the COVID-19 lockdown regulations, only the last FWF meeting could be held on-site, while two were observed online, which is why mainly remote participatory observation was used.

Observations enable a different kind of data, generated in real time (as observational data is not impaired by the awareness and experiences of the interviewed Board members, i.e. first-hand experiences can be collected). Therefore, observations provided complementary information and data on practices in Board meetings. Observation as a method for collecting data was already agreed on in the MoU that was signed in the initial phase of the GRANteD project.

All Board members had given their Informed Consent (IC) to be observed for research purposes. However, a few applicants did not provide IC, so when those proposals were discussed, the GRANteD researchers were sent to breakout rooms or had to leave the room physically. Each Board meeting was observed by two GRANteD researchers from the Joanneum Research team. For collecting data in the three Board meetings, an observation scheme was developed, based on previous research experiences.

After the three observations, Board members were interviewed to clarify open questions and follow up on unclear aspects.

The general interview guidelines used for all five GRANteD case studies, including several different descriptive and evaluative research questions, were adopted for FWF to best reflect FWF standards and procedures. Interviews were conducted between fall 2020 and April 2022 by researchers from Joanneum Research, a few also by the Örebro University GRANteD team. Candidates were contacted directly by email to request an interview; all interviewees signed a consent form. The interviews lasted between 20 and 80 minutes, were conducted in English using GoToMeeting or in person, and were fully transcribed. The following table provides an overview of all interviews.

Table 1 Overview FWF interviews

	All	Females	Males
Staff, management	5	3	2
Stakeholders	2	2	-
Board members	4	2	2
All	11	7	4

The data analysis was based on two pillars: In a first step, it referred directly to the GRANteD Conceptual Framework (GRANteD Deliverable D2.1) and the relevant analytical categories developed therein. More broadly, an inductive analysis was conducted, allowing the data to guide the analysis in order to identify emerging themes and concepts to develop new insights. As we *observed* Board meetings in their daily practice, the data rather reflect what emerged and became obvious in observations, compared to interviews when the data are collected along an interview guideline. We used thematic coding (Fereday/Muir-Cochrane 2006, Braun 2006) to develop themes and MaxQDA analysis software for general content analysis (Silverman 2006).

Quotes from interviews are used to illustrate findings; to guarantee anonymity of all data providers, these were edited: Informants are referred to with a code, for example (BM-1) stands for Board member 1, quotes from FWF staff and management members are cited with SM-1, stakeholders with SH-1. We do not present findings separately for each of the three Board meetings as all three observed meetings were composed in the same way (despite alternates replacing reporters); in addition, all were chaired by the same person.

Joanneum Research was responsible for the collection and analysis of FWF data. Preliminary findings of the practices analysis were presented to FWF representatives in early 2023, and some clarifications were added to the draft case study.

After all five case studies were finalised, the FWF draft report was sent to FWF for feedback. From FWF, comprehensive feedback was provided and integrated into this report. The authors want to thank the FWF representatives for their time and support.

When information was added that is not based on interviews or observations, but on the written feedback, this is marked in the text.

In addition to the qualitative data presented here, FWF provided quantitative data along the funding process, which were analysed in GRANteD WP4; findings are also reported in part C of this case study report.

4 (FORMAL) CONTEXT OF FWF BOARD MEETINGS

To be able to discuss practices in FWF Board meetings, information is needed about the formal policies in place. Therefore, we first introduce the main bodies relevant for the assessment process (4.1) before the formal assessment process is described in more detail (4.2). To draw this picture, we build on relevant FWF documents and interviews with FWF staff and management.

4.1 Relevant bodies

4.1.1 FWF Board (Executive Board and reporters)

The FWF Board³ consists of two parts: the Executive Board and the reporters. The latter – according to Austrian law – represent various Austrian research organisations and hold this position for three years. Each reporter has an alternate who replaces the reporter in case of non-availability. The Board is composed of representatives from all disciplines, as FWF Boards cover all scientific fields (OECD 2007)⁴. In the FWF Board meetings, the reporters present the assessment of the remote reviewers, but are not supposed to assess the applications themselves. The second part of the FWF Board is the Executive Board⁵, which is composed of the FWF president, one executive vice-president and three vice-presidents.

The FWF Board meets five times per year (*Kuratoriumssitzungen*), members are the same each time, only in case a reporter is not available s/he is replaced by the alternate. In the feedback to this report, the FWF members concluded in this matter: “All the Board members are aware of the principles to which the FWF is committed. (...) This applies to the mission and objectives of the FWF as well as the procedures, including of course e.g. gender and DORA policies” (FWF feedback).

Each Board meeting lasts for two to three days and decides on several funding programmes, ESPRIT being one of them.

4.1.2 Remote reviewers („Gutachter*innen“)

Remote reviewers are leading international experts in their field and should not have been located in Austria for the last five years. They should reflect diversity in respect to gender, age and geographic origin (FWF 2023 b). In the first step of the assessment, remote reviewers provide a written statement, in which they are supposed to address specific questions and an overall formal assessment for various questions

3 <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-the-fwf/organisation/board>

4 OECD Fields of science and technology: 1) Natural Sciences; 2) Engineering and Technology; 3) Medical and Health Sciences; 4) Agricultural Sciences; 5) Social Sciences; 6) Humanities.

5 <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/about-the-fwf/organisation/executive-board>

using a five-point scale (from “excellent = funding is highly recommended” to “poor = rejection is recommended”) (FWF 2023b).

4.1.3 FWF Office („Büro“)

Each incoming application is allocated to a FWF administrative and a scientific officer who check the formal aspects of the application. The administrative officer is approaching the remote reviewers after they have been nominated (=suggested) by the Board member in charge of the respective application. The scientific officer is involved in preparing the suggested funding category that is presented to the Board by highlighting the strengths and weaknesses according to the remote reviewers’ written reviews.

4.2 The FWF formal assessment process

How is the ESPRIT assessment process organised at FWF? In the following, this formal process is described in detail – based on analysing FWF documents, interviews with FWF staff and some feedback provided by FWF on a former version of this report – before we discuss in Chapter 5 how the assessment process was done in practice. The ESPRIT assessment process is a two-step approach: First, applications are sent to remote reviewers, and then, in a second step based on these remote reviews, the FWF Board decides which applications are funded.

4.2.1 Prior to Board meetings

When ESPRIT applications are submitted, they are assigned to a scientific and an administrative project officer at the FWF Office. They first formally check if the application is complete and meets all formal requirements, then they assign the application to a particular reporter and alternate of the FWF Board who are experts in the field of the application. The reporters also check the formal correctness of the application (FWF 2023b).

For each application which meets the formal requirements, the reporter and the alternate recommend two remote reviewers. When these scientists accept the invitation, the application together with the evaluation sheet, information about the FWF’s commitment for equal opportunities and equal treatment as well as a link to specific information on unconscious bias in the decision-making processes on the FWF site are sent to the remote reviewers, as remarked by the FWF in its feedback to this case study. Now each remote reviewer provides a written assessment statement and a numeric assessment along a five-point scale along the following topics: innovation/novelty; quality of the proposed research; approach and feasibility; principal investigator’s qualifications; ethics, sex and gender aspects; career development/suitability of mentor; suitability of the research institute. In addition to these aspects, an overall evaluation needs to be provided.

After the remote reviews are sent back to FWF, the FWF Office (the scientific project officer) and both reporters check the quality of the reviews and ask whether further information is needed. In case that both reporters and the scientific project officer decide that the quality of a review is not sufficient, it is rejected and another review needs to be collected.

In a next step, the reporters and scientific project officer summarise the written remote reviews and group the applications into three categories: category A means clear case for 'Approval', category B means that 'Further discussion is needed if the application is fundable' and category C means 'Rejection', while additional numbers specify the reason for the rejection (C1 to C5). If the scientific project officer, the reporter and the alternate have the same assessment on the rejection reason (e.g. C4), a proposal does not need to be further discussed in the Board.

4.2.2 Board meetings

The FWF Board negotiations are held in German, sometimes quotes from remote reviews are pointed out which are in English, and some Board members also bring in their contributions in English.

In the Board meetings, applications are introduced to the FWF Board based on a list with the application ID numbers. An FWF representative (the same for all applications) first states the project number, the name of the applicant and name of the reporter in charge. In case the FWF Board and staff members have a conflict of interest, their names are stated and they must leave the room (physically or sent to breakout rooms).

Following this, the reporter in charge presents the application and the assessment of the remote reviews (see 5.1.1) that was prepared together with the alternate and the scientific officer. The most relevant strengths and weaknesses according to the remote reviews are highlighted here. After the assigned reporter presented the proposal, s/he makes reference to the remote reviews, to the written and the numeric assessment. Also, the preliminary suggested funding category (A, B or C) is introduced, which reflects the assessment of the scientific officer, the reporter and the alternate. In the next step, the Board basically negotiates whether this suggestion should be confirmed or revised. This negotiation usually takes a few minutes and is supposed to follow the General Principles of the FWF Decision-Making Procedure (FWF 2023b), after which the chair closes the discussion by announcing the final decision (see 5.5.3 and 5.6).

5 EVALUATION IN PRACTICE IN FWF BOARD MEETINGS

In this chapter we analyse practices in FWF Board meetings, starting with how reference was made to the applicant (see 5.1), how excellence is discussed in Boards (see 5.2) and which role remote reviewers play in this context (see 5.3). In a next step, we have a closer look at the way gender is addressed in Board meetings (see 5.4) and at various dynamics within Boards (see 5.5), illustrating how negotiations are practiced and chaired, taking into account that two Board meetings were held online and one was on-site. Finally, we illustrate how decision making is practiced (see 5.6) and, in particular, how the ESPRIT ‘quota’ for gender-balanced funding outcomes worked (see 5.7).

5.1 Boards addressing applicants

We were interested in the way the Board talks about applicants, i.e. how applicants are introduced at the beginning and addressed during Board negotiations.

5.1.1 Introducing applicants

When reporters introduced applicants, this often happened in quite a personal manner, explicitly mentioning the applicant’s name and gender, using phrases like “[Mrs Huber] works on [topic of application] and would like to move to [city] and collaborate with Prof [name of professor] from [name of department or university].” When personal pronouns [HE would like...] or the male/female German form [DER Antragsteller möchte...] were mentioned, they identified the applicant’s gender⁶. Beyond an applicant’s personal information, also information on the name of the supervisor, the name and institution of the mentor or the institution of the PhD was shared with the Board members. For how this might contribute to gender bias, see 5.3.2.

Not all eligible applications were discussed in the Board meetings: When the respective reporter, the alternate and the scientific project officer all three agreed on rejecting an application and on the reason for this rejection⁷ prior to the Board meeting, an application was not discussed, but only read out.

5.1.2 Flagging female applicants?

When discussing all applications in the first round, Board members sometimes claimed to know the applicant’s gender, stating that “it seems to be a woman...”, turning to other Board members for confirmation. In another case, when the Board discussed the preliminary suggested funding category (in German called “Bürovorschlag”), a Board member asked if upgrading makes sense at all in case the applicant is not a woman. Upgrading here seemed to be linked to achieve the quota of 50 % female grantees at the end of each Board meeting. Board members seemed to have this quota in mind already when they negotiated the applicant’s scores provided by the remote reviewers.

⁶ We use ‘gender’ when we refer to the biological sex and to different gender identities.

⁷ Reasons to reject a proposal see FWF 2022c, p. 7

This was stressed by another Board member who demanded that the applicant's gender should be noted in the IT system and visible along all steps of the assessment process, as this would make it easier to achieve the intended quota. This means that already during the negotiation phase in round 1, some panel members focussed or tried to focus on the applicant's gender, probably to have enough women funded to achieve the quota.

This practice implies that knowing an applicant's gender could impact the assessment as early as in round 1, when deciding which application is approved immediately (category A) and which one has the potential for funding and should be re-discussed (category B). Flagging female applicants' applications and making explicit that these are female applicants would mean to support treating them differently.

This could invite Board members to promote them in order to meet the quota, which would in turn violate the rule to apply the same standards for each applicant.

As described in chapter 5.6, the gender of applicants should only play a role in the second round of discussion proposals. Thus, it would be important to make sure that gender is of no concern in the discussions of round 1.

5.2 Boards discussing excellence

In Board negotiations, a lot of time was spent to discuss various elements of excellence. When FWF Board members needed to agree on the final grade and overcome diverging positions, reference was made to various elements of excellence, often relevant to gender bias.

5.2.1 Publications

Publications were (still) the core element of negotiating excellence in Board meetings. This was not expressed explicitly, but became apparent when Board members developed their image of the 'ideal grantee'.

Nevertheless, it could be observed that a top publication record was no precondition for being granted within this early career grant (eligibility: up to five years after PhD). Applicants discussed as *"not having such a strong track record looking at the number of publications and citations"* (Board member, observation) were funded. Another publications record was assessed as *"not very much outstanding"* (Board member, observation) – this application was also funded. In other cases, Board members referred to the applicant's potential, arguing that the listed number of publications *".. is promising"*. (Board member, observation), reflecting the junior position of most applicants. These assessment practices were expected as the ESPRIT programme addresses early career researchers.

In respect to gender, some reference was made to maternity leave as a reason for fewer publications. In one case, reference was made to the COVID-19 pandemic when a Board member pointed out that a female applicant was not able to move to a new host institution as planned before and thus was not able to produce more publications. Further, publications and scientific outcomes were discussed from a gender perspective

"As we are supposed to fund enough women, the applicant's gender should be easily visible in the digital assessment infrastructure."
Board member

when discussing gender balance and scientific excellence: *“If you look at gender balance, what happens? Women are brought in. They are then younger and scientifically weaker. This is, of course, a downward spiral. Then you have exactly the situation that it looks as if the women were picked out”* (B-2-PM3). Here, gender and age are discussed as intersecting variables for different excellence standards.

5.2.2 Alternative excellence standards

FWF as a signatory of DORA – and also CoARA – has formally limited the number of scientific publications/outcomes that applicants can report to the ten most relevant (see 3.1). An adapted CV template – from 2018 onwards – allows applicants to report merits and research outcomes on a broader basis. Reviewers were instructed to *“refrain from using journal-based metrics such as the Journal Impact Factor (SM-4)”*.

It was, however, remarkable that DORA standards were never addressed in any of the three observed Board meetings. One explanation for this silence could be – as brought up by an FWF member after the feedback loop workshop – that DORA standards were relevant in all funding programmes and thus well-known and not mentioned specifically in (the briefing of) the ESPRIT session. Another argument might be that these standards are not yet actively practiced and that more accountability is needed to implement them in FWF Board meetings.

5.2.3 Language use: Hyperbole

When Board members discussed excellence, they sometimes pointed to remote reviewers’ use of language in their written assessment. When presenting an application as excellent they stated *“I like that there [in the remote reviews] are words like ... ‘high’ or ‘superb’”* (BM-1). And when remote reviewers did *not* include such superlative wording, it was missed, e.g. *“no enthusiastic feedback”*; while in another negotiation it was argued that *“the superlatives we want to hear are not in it, but there is no criticism either”* (Board member, observation). On one occasion, it was even demanded that due to this lack of enthusiasm, a proposal should not be funded – this argument was rejected by the chair.

This reflects the Board members’ expectation that remote reviewers use a specific, overstating language to highlight the excellence of applications, implying that applications are more excellent when remote reviewers use more superlatives or hyperbolics.

5.2.4 Ambivalent standards

Another language issue with potential for (gender) bias is unsystematic language use. Although we did not systematically analyse the use of language, one notion was striking – ‘overambitious’ was discussed quite ambivalently: It was used as an argument to reject a proposal as its implementation was perceived as not realistic; in another case, the Board argued that overambition is not a problem due to very positive remote reviews. Of course, the reviewers’ assessment based on the proposals is relevant here, e.g. how much support is provided for implementing an ‘overambitious’ project. However, this could also be seen as an indication that standards for dealing with overambitious projects differ among Board members.

Another unsystematic approach became visible when Board members discussed the length of the A-subgrade: On the one hand, it was argued that applicant X received very little criticism from the reviewers, so a “very small minus” should be allocated. On the other hand, it was argued that a review was not of good quality as it was too short and included little criticism. This means that receiving few critical comments was interpreted as good quality in some cases, while in others, it was seen as low quality of the remote review.

5.2.5 Broader excellence: interdisciplinarity, societal impact

Sometimes, Board members addressed elements of excellence that point to a broader understanding of excellence, like the innovativeness of research methods and research approaches or the interdisciplinarity of a research project. This was also discussed in respect to gender differences.

“We often have women making science and research creating new ideas and they open disciplines and they are working very interdisciplinary.”
SM-2

It was argued that female applicants would benefit from an interdisciplinary approach, describing them as *“in average younger and so more risk-liking and more interested in interdisciplinary research... but competing with the very traditional science they fall out”* (SM-2). It was stated that the (former) women-only programmes allowed female researchers to go beyond the classical understanding of excellence and explore interdisciplinary approaches. This argument indicates that fostering interdisciplinary research could be an active measure to increase gender balance particularly in male-dominated disciplines. This means that in the assessment process, more focus could be put on interdisciplinarity in assessment guidelines for remote reviewers and Board members.

Societal impact, another criterion relevant when discussing a broader concept of excellence, is not a formal criterion and was not addressed in Board meetings. It was even clearly rejected by an FWF Board member: *“I don’t think that society impact should play a role. That is one of the principles of those RFOs funding basic science”* (B-1-PM2).

When looking at the survey that was sent to FWF applicants, however, clear gender differences can be found as regards the relevance of their research for societal problem solving: This fully applies for 44 % of all female respondents, but only for 19 % of the male respondents (see part B of this case study, Holzinger et al. 2023).

In the ESPRIT programme, a mandatory mentoring plan was implemented for all genders for the first time. When Board members addressed mentoring, they mainly raised the quality of the mentor, highlighting a mentor’s scientific reputation or their position as a very renowned researcher. No reference was made to the support provided for the mentee. Interestingly, the gender of the mentor was never pointed out in the three Board meetings we observed.

5.2.6 Gender in research content (GiR)

As part of the excellence definition, FWF asks applicants and reviewers to take gender into account in the research project (GiR) when developing a research design (research questions, sampling) and when

implementing funded projects (data analysis, data interpretations). FWF is now asking the applicants to elaborate on the gender dimension in their research project based on this formal instruction: *“A separate section must describe what gender-specific and gender-related issues⁸ the planned project may potentially give rise to”* (FWF 2023b).

By integrating a gender perspective in knowledge production, more specific and better scientific outcomes are expected. FWF staff members and external stakeholders supported this approach and argued that RFOs have a responsibility for the knowledge created by their funding and that *“RFOs establish standards for how research needs to be done”* (SM-3).

The formal request to take the gender dimension into account was implemented gradually. FWF members described it as a challenging process to obtain commitment within FWF to start implementing the GiR policy. It took time to prepare and drive the implementation, as this required an understanding of *why* the policy is needed. FWF representatives argued that there was high acceptance of the policy among the research community (applicants and reviewers).

The assessment of GiR in ESPRIT applications was done by remote reviewers who were asked to assess whether gender was addressed adequately by the applicants (yes, no, not applicable). FWF provides the following assessment instruction: *“Applicants are required to address any relevant sex-specific and/or gender-related elements inherent in research questions and/or research design. Please assess whether the treatment of these components is adequate.* (FWF 2023b, p. 24).

Here, the remote reviewers assess the adequacy of addressing GiR only, without involving the research content. In contrast, in the three observed Board meetings, GiR was hardly addressed. This could mean that reviewers have not brought up this topic very often. However, as each application needs to be assessed for GiR, it should have some relevance for the discussion in the Board as well. So far, only in very few negotiations, reference was made to gender in research: For a proposal in the Social Sciences, reviewers pointed out that gender was addressed as a non-binary concept. In the review of another proposal, the composition of a mice sample was highlighted as gender-balanced. The following Board discussion about different behaviours of female and male mice was met with laughter on the part of some Board members, which the chair called a halt to. These examples illustrate that most Board members have limited awareness about gender in research, which might be related to the reviewers’ disciplinary backgrounds, with Social Science representatives being more engaged. However, an FWF staff member argued that GiR is becoming more accepted in general and relevant for approving or rejecting a proposal: *“At the beginning it was a formal thing and now it is a thing that they take into account for the decision”* (SM-2).

⁸ This is specified as follows: *“Positioning and reflecting on the research approaches planned for the project in terms of sex-specific and gender-related issues, for instance: Is the research approach likely to produce sex-specific and gender-related findings? If so, what findings? How and where are these integrated into the research approach?”*

5.3 Boards discussing remote review/er/s

5.3.1 Role of remote reviewers

In the Board negotiations, the quality of the two (sometimes more) remote reviews was discussed. Moreover, remote reviewers as persons were discussed regarding several aspects, but interestingly no reference was made to their gender. The discussions referred to the reputation of reviewers or their home institution, with arguments like *“this reviewer is one of the most cited researchers in the field”*, or mentioning that a reviewer has worked with well-known scientists or laureates. At this point, the chair intervened, reminding Board members that all remote reviewers are equally important as are their reviews.

5.3.2 Quality of remote reviews

The quality of remote reviews and reviewers was an issue discussed lively and ambivalently in the FWF Board meetings. One aspect of evaluating the quality was the length of a review: Sometimes it was argued that a review cannot be taken into account as it was too short and superficial. In others cases, although the review was described as rather short, it was still considered good quality: A Board member argued that a specific proposal *“received far less criticism”* and thus should be funded (Board member). This means, the Board members considered a short review as an indication for either – for good quality due too little/short criticism or for low quality for not discussing the application sufficiently. The length or quantity of a review seemed to be an ambivalent and vague assessment factor.

Similar discussions could be observed about the ‘specificity’ of reviews. Board members had ambivalent perceptions regarding whether a remote review is specific enough in addressing an application or whether it is more a general statement that might be copied and pasted from other applications. To obtain an aligned position in this context, sometimes quite heated discussions among the Executive Board members were necessary.

In some cases, remote reviewers’ scores were brought up and discussed in detail, for instance elaborating on the consistency between the written feedback and the numeric assessment by scores. Overall, it was not clear in the observations how the numeric assessment and the written assessment are weighted against each other. A member of the Executive Board stated that the written assessment comes first and the numeric second. However, usually the main part of the negotiation practice revolved around the funding category proposed by the FWF Office. Based on what was discussed before, this suggestion was either confirmed or revised.

5.3.3 Usability of remote reviews

Discussions about an insufficient quality of a remote review culminated in discussions about the usability of remote reviews. For several applications, it was discussed whether the reviews were of sufficient quality to be used. This decision is in particular relevant as not including one of the two remote reviews could mean that no (positive) funding decision can be made in this Board meeting, as fundable applications need two remote reviews.

While the Board discussed the potential exclusion of external reviews, it also highly valued remote reviews and the expertise of remoter reviewers. In some cases, this expertise was discussed as most relevant for the funding decision. A Board member who had initially expressed some doubts on the remote reviewers' scores finally accepted their assessment, arguing that *"I like to bow to the remote reviewers as experts"* (Board member). Another Board member confirmed *"Right, she [the remote reviewer] is the one who judges the quality"*. In this case, the Board prioritised the remote reviewers' assessment over their personal doubts on the quality of the review.

It was usually the chair who finally decided whether the quality of a review was sufficient and could be used or not, mostly after negotiations and checking back with Executive Board members.

5.4 Gender awareness in Boards

An important aspect when analysing the potential gender bias in the allocation of research grants is how gender is addressed in Board meetings, both explicitly and implicitly.

When discussing ESPRIT applications, the FWF Board rarely addressed gender or the relevance of gender in the assessment process explicitly. In the three observed Board meetings, this happened when the Board referred to GE policies already in place, mentioning maternity, paternity or parental leaves policies as explanation for publication gaps. Further reference was made to the FWF request that applicants have to integrate gender in their research design and research content (see 4.2.6).

The strongest focus was put on gender in respect to the 'gender quota' (see 4.7): Here, gender came in when the funding outcome, i.e. the list of grantees, was checked for gender balance after discussing all applications. As a gender-balanced funding outcome was the formal objective to be met in each Board meeting, gender seemed to be a kind of elephant in the room during the Board discussions. The Board members and the chair (implicitly) might have had an equal number of female and male grantees in mind as early as during the negotiation phase (see chap 4.1.2). While the Board fulfilled the gender-balanced funding outcome quota in all meetings, it was not clear whether the underlying rationale for this GE policy and its aim were clear to all Board members.

FWF members remarked that gender awareness-raising activities were supposed to be limited to online trainings in place, but that it would be important to have specific awareness measures for the concrete setting of the FWF Board, so *"that people also get a feeling for what bias could mean in such a meeting, because when they would realise that, then we would move a big step forward"* (SM-1).

Board members talked about gender awareness as a subtle norm, arguing in interviews that in Board meetings *"you really have to be careful what you say"* (BM-3). They seemed to be afraid of 'incorrect' language use in Board meetings, which can be interpreted as a (rhetorical) awareness to avoid gender biased language. This illustrates potential gender bias, although gender awareness measures and GE policies might have already created an atmosphere that mitigates Board members' gendered language use. It is questionable whether this awareness is sustainable or rather reflects a social desirability and might still negatively impact the assessment behaviour.

Indeed, FWF members reported that it was difficult to increase the awareness for gender and how gender is inscribed in the assessment process. Raising awareness for gender bias of Board members was described as a challenge, as pointed out by an FWF interviewee: *"The most important thing is that people realise that bias is existing, ... they haven't realised that..., you can talk to them like against a wall, there is just no understanding"* (SM-1).

Finally, gender was discussed not only in respect to the assessment process, but also in respect to who is doing the assessment. One further issue was the unequal representation of female and male scientists in different scientific disciplines and its relevance for recruiting female remote reviewers. It was argued that in some fields, finding female reviewers was difficult due to the horizontal segregation in the science system and the different representation of women in different academic fields. FWF strives for a 'field-appropriate representation' of female remote reviewers (see 3.2), and officers reported that they had worked hard to find an appropriate number of female remote reviewers in male-dominated fields: *"We cannot change universities and if there are any kids [female students] in different fields. But we try very hard. Of course, it's sometimes difficult to find female researchers. So, then you must do a second round and a third round to find a female researcher"* (SM-4).

5.5 Dynamics in Boards

In the following section, we analyse *how* the negotiation process in Boards took place and the dynamics behind it.

5.5.1 Negotiation practices

When observing ESPRIT Board meetings, the two different components of the Board became apparent: the reporters (as delegates from Austrian research performing organisations) who presented and discussed the proposal, and the Executive Board (the chair and three vice-chairs, each in charge of one scientific discipline). In most cases, negotiations in Board meetings were conducted between the chair, the reporters (the main reporter, called nominator or the alternate reporter, called commentator) and the Executive Board member responsible for the scientific discipline the application belongs to. Only in a few cases, further Board members engaged in the negotiation process.

After the assigned reporters had presented the proposal and gave their statement, making reference to the remote reviews and/or to the preliminary suggested funding category, the Board negotiated whether the grade suggested should be confirmed or revised. When (some) members disagreed and strived for a revision of the grade, complex negotiations could take place. When the reporter, for instance, argued for C3 and the Executive Board member who is an expert in the field of the application argued for C4, the chair might step in by highlighting the arguments and suggesting the final funding category on which all Board members involved can agree on. In cases with no tendency for change, the negotiation process was rather short.

Some power structures became visible when certain decisions, like to include or to exclude a remote review, had to be made; then, members of the Executive Board took a leading role, while the reporters were less involved in this process.

5.5.2 On-site and online dynamics

Negotiation practices in FWF Boards differed, depending on the different formats of the meetings. While before the COVID-19 pandemic, all Board meetings took place on-site (face to face), they later were shifted to digital (online) meetings to avoid social contacts.

Two of the three Board meetings we observed were held online. In these online meetings, negotiations were quite structured: Typically, after introducing a proposal (see 4.1.1), the chair gave the floor to the commentator who then made a statement. Then, the commentator was usually asked to present his/her view on the proposal. By actively inviting people to speak up, the chair tried to avoid that two people start speaking at the same time. Board members did hardly interrupt or jump into discussions easily to bring in diverging positions. This way, negotiations seemed to be practiced in an efficient way. At the same time, this could mean that when fewer Board members engaged in the negotiations process, also fewer and less diverse perspectives were brought up. This way, the Board as the decision-making body might have had less power to reflect and to challenge the assessment suggested by the FWF Office.

When the FWF Board finally met face to face again in May 2022, a different atmosphere was noticed: The Board members had livelier discussions, more people were chatting at the same time. Sometimes it was quite noisy in the meeting room and for us as observers, understanding the contributions of Board members was not always easy. This finding is in line with a reviewer's comment from a different case study describing the dynamics in face-to-face panel meetings: *"Everyone gets involved, especially in very good proposals. Everyone wants to understand why we like it [the discussed proposal] so much. In virtual environments, it's flatter. The enthusiasm is flatter"* (RFO 5, PM).

However, reestablishing an open face-to-face atmosphere seemed demanding; a FWF Board member compared the dynamics of this first face-to-face discussion to the time before COVID-19: *"We are not yet where we have been before"* (BM-2).

5.5.3 Chair

All ESPRIT Board meetings were chaired by the same person, the FWF president (which is in contrast to most other case studies, where panels are structured by research fields with a chair coming from this field). Accordingly, the chair had a strong position in organising the (dynamics and atmosphere in) Board meetings and in setting up the negotiation practices.

When steering the negotiations, the chair gave the floor to or asked selected Board members for their opinions. He also took responsibility for quality standards, like stopping long negotiations between Board members by arguing that time should be spent equally for each proposal. He asked Board members not to prioritise remote reviewers based on their scientific reputation.

Whereas the chair had a leading role in steering the discussion (see 5.5.3), the Executive Board had a crucial role in reaching a decision. To achieve a common solution, the chair actively addressed reporters and Executive Board members to explain and justify their assessment. Before reaching a final decision, the chair usually checked back with the Executive Board member responsible for this scientific discipline to agree on

the final grade. To come to a final decision in round 1, the chair summarised the pros and cons raised by the Board members. When striving for the final decision to fund or not to fund a proposal, the chair was supported by the members of the Executive Board, who were asked to confirm or to question the final decision suggested by the chair. After balancing all that was discussed before, the chair announced the final grade in round 1. To us observers, it was not always clear on what exactly this final decision was based, as it did not always seem to reflect the prior discussion in the Board, i.e. it seemed that the last step was the chair's decision.

Finally, the chair had a relevant role after all applications were discussed in a first round and a gender-balanced funding quota had to be achieved. He then checked the list of applications to be funded for gender balance and reported the status quo on male and female applicants graded with an 'A' before suggesting how to proceed to fulfil the quota (see more 4.7).

In the Board meetings, also other FWF members were present, staff responsible for statistics and the IT system, the ESPRIT programme manager and members of the gender equality office. These people did not intervene in the negotiation process and only spoke up in case of formal issues.

5.5.4 Conflict of Interest

All Board members worked in Austrian research institutions, so Conflicts of Interests (Col) occurred several times. We observed that during the Board meeting, the FWF representative who introduced the proposal also announced who of the Board members and staff members had to leave the meeting due to a conflict of interest (if applicable). Accordingly, the respective Board member left the room or was sent to a breakout room in virtual meetings. Some Board members reported in informal chats during the time-out that they did not know exactly why they were dismissed, but they never questioned this in the meeting. It also happened that Board members themselves brought up the Col issue and told all participants via the chat: *"I am also biased"* (Board member).

We observed that in online Board meetings, Cols were much easier to handle and less time-consuming, as sending Board members to breakout rooms and back worked quickly. In contrast, sending Board members out of the room and bringing them back took more time and they were sometimes late, when the next proposal was already negotiated.

5.5.5 Time

ESPRIT Board meetings were scheduled for about two hours, with other funding programmes being discussed by the same Board before and after ESPRIT applications. The number of proposals to be decided was around 60 per meeting⁹, so limited time was available for each application.

We did not clock the speaking time of each Board member nor the speaking time for each proposal, but for most negotiations we put down the starting time. From this information, we can see that the time slot for discussing a proposal including the introduction was mostly between four and six minutes. Only a few

⁹ Some were not discussed in the Board meeting as they were already decided to be rejected by the reporters and the FWF scientific officer ('akkordiertes Ergebnis').

discussions took longer than six minutes. In these cases this was due to (male as well as female) Board members who talked longer or repeated their positions various times.

Two further interesting aspects emerged in respect to the use of time and scheduling of Board meetings: In one Board meeting, members started discussing their tiredness as they had been sitting for a long time and the impact this could have on the assessment, arguing they might have been less critical and more often confirmed the preliminary suggested funding category. Another remark was that Board meetings were scheduled until late in the evening, which got in the way of the Board members' private life.

5.6 Decision making and calibrating the final funding category

When observing decision making in panels, we observed that this process consisted of two rounds. In the first round, the remote reviewers' written assessment and some selected aspects of the numerical assessment (issues to be assessed see 4.2.1) were negotiated in order to come to a decision on the funding category (A, B, C).

When negotiating the final funding category, some informal calibration practices were observed. Sub-grades were assigned, e.g. in case of minor doubts an 'A-' was suggested and more detailed sub-categories were introduced, like 'a very short A-' or a 'long A-'. Sometimes comparisons were made, arguing that the A- for application X was shorter than the A- for application Y. The need for more fine-tuning of grades became evident when a Board member supported a fine-tuning assessment practice introduced and applied by one Board member individually: *"One should introduce a decimal scale, as [name of Board member] has already practiced it"* (BM-6). So there seemed to be an individual practice to use a 'decimal scale'¹⁰.

The chair steered the negotiation process and partly checked back with other Executive Board members and/or the reporter (by raising hands, by sending information in the chat) before confirming or rejecting the preliminary suggested funding category. For all applications assessed with an A, the final funding decision was announced by stating that an applicant is approved (*"Huber approved"*). For applicants with an A-, a second negotiation round took place (see 5.7).

5.7 Final decision making – gender-balanced funding outcomes (quota)

As described in chapter 2.2, the FWF Board was expected "to award at least half of the projects in the program to *female principal investigators*" (FWF 2023, P. 4). It was the chair who took on the responsibility to achieve this objective (see 5.5.3). Therefore, after discussing all applications in a first round, all applications scored A and approved for funding were listed. When this number did not meet the number of maximum grantees to be selected, the Board then entered into a second round of discussion to decide which of the remaining applications could be funded. Then, all applications scored A- (and potentially also B) were re-discussed, this time focusing on the applicants' gender. Within this group of equally assessed

¹⁰ In former times FWF used a 100-point-scale (see Much et.al 2015)

applicants, the list of the remaining applications including the gender of the applicant was read out and the lacking number of women was selected for funding so that the quota was met.

The pattern how this objective was achieved, however, differed between the three Board meetings we observed:

- In one Board meeting, twelve applications were graded A and thus approved for funding, five of them from female applicants after discussing all applications in the first round. The budget enabled to fund 16 projects, so four more applications could be selected from the pool of proposals graded with A-. This pool included three applications from female researchers, which were added to the list of approved projects, as the chair argued that this was foreseen by the new quota procedure. After that, one male applicant was selected, coming from a scientific field with fewer grantees so far.
- In another Board meeting, eight women researchers were approved for funding at the end of the first discussion round. As the budget covered 16 proposals in total, this met the quota without any further re-ranking activity. Yet, it was evident that the grantees were highly gender-segregated by scientific domains: All grantees in Humanities and Social Sciences were women and all grantees in Natural Sciences were men, while in Biology and Medical Science, grants were equally distributed between female and male researchers.
- In the last Board meeting, 14 applications were approved with grade A after all proposals were discussed in round 1, six from female applicants. As in total 18 projects could be funded, the chair pointed out that applications from nine women were to be funded to achieve the target. Thus three females out of the A- pool were selected for funding. Unfortunately, the following negotiation process could not be observed by the GRANteD research team, as one of the discussed applicants had not given Informed Consent, so the GRANteD observers were sent to a virtual breakout room during this discussion.

The examples show that in all three meetings, after the first round the number of female grantees was equal or less than half of the number of applications to be funded. This means that no re-scoring or re-ranking had to be practiced in the observed Board meetings. In all three rounds, when the chair checked the gender balance of grantees after this first round of discussing proposals, the full number of applications selected for funding (= graded A) was lower than the full number of all applications that could be funded. In two of the three meetings a few more grants could be allocated, and they were selected in a way that the quota could be properly fulfilled. Here, priority was given to the applications of women with equal quality – in consistence with the formal FWF commitment that *“in the case of equal qualifications and equal quality of projects, applications by female principal investigators will be given priority”* (Schmidt et.al 2020).

In one Board meeting, the quota was met ‘naturally’ – without any additional activities, the same number of female and male applicants were granted.

Interestingly, the 50 % quota for female applicants was never discussed or questioned during the three Board meetings we observed. Board members seemed to be aware that a sufficient number of women needs to be funded to meet this policy aim. It seemed a given policy, supported by the chair who stated clearly that the quota needed to be met and who applied a clear agenda: *“First we look how many women we need, then we check which ‘women are swimming on the top’”*.

Nevertheless, in interviews conducted with FWF Board members after the first three ESPRIT decision rounds, they expressed that they felt “released” (BM-1) that no re-ranking was needed, which would have been stressful: *“No problem – all these problems I expected, when we have to rank down males despite being better and just to fulfil this 50 % rule”* (BM-1). This quote indicates that the ‘quota’ is perceived as a policy target that needs to be achieved and less as a reasonable policy to counteract difficulties and barriers that female researchers are still facing in the research system.

6 DISCUSSION – GENDER RISKS IN PRACTICE

The previous chapters presented findings from observing FWF Board meetings in which applications from the ESPRIT funding programme were assessed. In respect to potential gender bias, we analysed the assessment process and how GE policies (= formal policies implemented to mitigate gender bias) were applied in practice.

Some of the risks are specific to the ESPRIT programme, others are of a more general nature. As the ESPRIT programme is supposed to test some ‘reforming elements’ which later might be implemented in other FWF funding programmes as well, both are discussed here.

From the research perspective of the GRANteD project, it was particularly interesting to analyse the assessment process in practice in the FWF ESPRIT programme as gender balanced funding outcomes were implemented, replacing a women-only funding programme. This way, we could study how this policy adoption impacted the assessment process.

In the following, we discuss the most striking issues by identifying potential risks for gender bias.

6.1 Implementing a gender quota

With the gender quota, FWF has introduced an innovative gender equality policy. Three aspects are of interest: (a) How the quota impacted the ESPRIT assessment process from a gender perspective; (b) How the quota worked overall and in different scientific disciplines; and (c) What can be learnt for designing and implementing gender equality policies.

6.1.1 Risk of reducing gender to numbers

By implementing a quota for female grantees, gender awareness gets reduced to the focus on representation – how many female applicants are scored A, how many A- and thus available to be adjusted to A. So, as risk 1, we define that practicing a quota for gender-balanced funding outcomes can reduce gender to numbers.

It is, however, crucial to go beyond numbers and not limit gender to representation, but rather guarantee gender fairness in the assessment process, e.g. by addressing applicants in a gender-neutral way, by specifying excellence criteria in a gender-neutral manner, etc. A (gender-)fair process should make sure that the best researchers are granted, which is ideally the same number of female and male applicants.

However, a focus on representation can be an important step to raise awareness for gender and to reflect about different probabilities for male and female applicants to be funded and included in the science system. A quota that enables re-scoring or re-ranking might thus be an appropriate policy to raise awareness about disadvantages for women.

While the quota is an instrument for bringing a defined number of women into the science system, the implementation of the quota should be accompanied by explaining why a quota is needed; this way, awareness for more subtle forms of gender bias can be raised.

6.1.2 Risk of horizontal segregation

As further risk we identified that the quota as an instrument to include (more) women can increase the horizontal segregation in science.

As discussed above, a core aim of the FWF when dismissing a women-only programme was to make sure that a sufficient number of female researchers apply, get funded and are thus included in the science system. Following this objective, the quota worked in practice. In each Board meeting we observed, the quota was met and as many female as male researchers were approved for funding.

From a gender perspective, it is crucial to also look at the inclusion of female researchers by scientific disciplines. Looking at approval rates of male and female researchers by scientific discipline, the inclusion worked only partly, as the following table shows:

Table 2 ESPRIT approval rates by gender and scientific discipline

Board meetings 1–3	Applications (number)			Applications (share)		Approved (number)			Approved (share)		Share of female grantees in all ESPRIT grantees	Approval rate		Differenc e (female minus male)
	F	M	all	F	M	F	M	all	F	M		F	M	
Biology and Medicine	35	29	64	55%	45%	11	5	16	69%	31%	19,2	31,4	17,2	+ 14,2
Natural and Technical Sciences	14	56	70	20%	80%	4	18	22	18%	82%	7,7	26,6	32,1	- 5,5
Humanities, Social Sciences	32	22	54	59%	41%	11	3	14	79%	21%	19,2	34,4	13,6	+20,8
All	81	10 7	188			26	26	52	50%	50%		32,1	24,3	+7,8

Source: data provided by FWF, own calculations

When looking at the number and share of female researchers per discipline, we found a majority of female grantees in Biology/Medical Sciences (69 %) and in Humanities and Social Sciences (79 %), while only 18 % of the grantees in Natural and Technical Sciences were women. This distribution of course refers to the share of female applicants by discipline. So when looking at the number of successful female applicants (= approval rate), we learn that female applicants were more successful in disciplines they were over-represented in (Humanities/Social Sciences: 34,4 % vs. 13,6 % males; Biology/Medicine: 31,4 % vs. 17,2 % males). In Natural and Technical Sciences with a low share of female applicants, those who applied were not as successful (26,6 % compared to 32,1 % of male applicants).

This means that in fields with already few women, fewer women are granted and included in the science system. Gender imbalances at applicant level increase on grantee level and thus are increasing the horizontal segregation already existing.

These preliminary GRANteD findings were discussed at the feedback loop workshop with FWF representatives. Following this workshop, the FWF provided data for grantees for all five ESPRIT meetings in 2022, which show that numbers have changed and approval rates have become more balanced (see Annex). These differences were explained by the small size of the sample.

From the perspective of gender fairness, it is crucial that the public funding budget is equally distributed between genders. Following a gender budgeting approach, it can be argued that in each discipline, budgets should be spent in a gender-fair way overall, but also when taking disciplines into account. So in the next future, FWF could work towards a gender quota by scientific discipline, using affirmative action approaches to increase the participation of women in disciplines where they are underrepresented so far. This would require a definite commitment from FWF to the number of funded female grantees in the ESPRIT programme, by discipline and overall.

However, the general ESPRIT funding budget should be taken into account as well, using a gender budgeting approach that keeps track of where the money goes to: Different ways to distribute the budget in a gender-fair manner could be possible, like a distribution of funding according to the proportion of female applicants or of female PhD holders (when 30 % of Physics PhDs are female researchers, then 30 % of the Physics budget should go to female applicants). A more radical approach would be to have three different sub-budgets and 50 % of each budget should be spent on female applicants. This would clearly follow the idea: When you aim to change something (more women in NTS), you need to change something (for further development see Annex, 9.1).

In this respect, it is interesting from a gender perspective to analyse how the preliminary funding category suggested by the FWF officer and reporters assessed applications by female and male researchers (how scores by remote reviewers were transferred into the category suggested to the FWF Board), and in the next step, check to which extent the Board up- or downgraded this suggestion by gender.

This is analysed quantitatively in part C.

6.1.3 Risk of double standards

A third gender risk identified while studying practices when implementing a quota for gender-balanced funding outcomes was that double standards might be applied when assessing female and male applicants in order to achieve this quota.

In section 4.7, it was discussed that in all three Board meetings, the gender balanced-funding quotas were achieved when – after discussing all applications in the Board meeting in a first round – a list of all approved male and female applicants was presented by the chair; who then announced the number of grants that can be allocated in a second discussion round. When selecting those further grantees, the gender balance between female and male grantees was clearly checked. We have discussed that the quota might not only be relevant from the moment on when the list of applicants graded A is presented at the end of the first discussion round, but could have been a guiding idea already during the negotiations in the Board meeting.

Female applicants could already have been “pushed” in the negotiation phase, as Board members had argued that female applicants should be flagged. Knowing which applications are from female researchers to maybe assess those differently would not be a gender-fair practice. Applying standards differently to female applicants in order to avoid re-scoring and re-ranking, without clear guidelines and in an unsystematic manner gives way to further bias. This would mean that the timing for an intervention informally started too early. Anyway, pushing female applicants already in the negotiation phase on an individual and informal basis would decrease transparency and is not supposed to be part of implementing a re-ranking quota at the end of an assessment process.

One final remark concerning the quota: While we argue that re-ranking should only be done at the very end of the assessment process – and not started already during the negotiation process, e.g. by applying double standards – we also claim that a re-ranking policy is not the perfect gender equality policy. The optimal assessment process would be that Board members are aware of and mitigate gendered norms during the negotiation phase, and not that Board members correct and re-rank the list of grantees at the end of the assessment process.

6.1.4 Risk of not addressing underrepresented groups

Currently, awareness for a diverse research workforce beyond gender is less developed in the European context compared to the US. More focus could be put on the inclusion of underrepresented groups, like researchers with different ethnical or social backgrounds. It was shown that early-career researchers of underrepresented minority groups were enabled to successfully apply for NIH funding (Weber-Main et al. 2020) when participating in intensive training throughout the proposal design process.

6.1.5 Learnings from the ESPRIT gender quota for general policy design

The quota – i.e. the policy to have the same number of female and male grantees in the ESPRIT programme – shifted the focus to the number/representation of female grantees. Accordingly, the number of women to be funded was specifically focused on in Board meetings. At the same time, further gendered aspects in the assessment process, like the role of care responsibilities in respect to publications, what is perceived as excellence and how gender was integrated in the content of research proposals (see 5.2.6), received little

attention. More generally, the focus on gender-balanced outcomes of the assessment process limited the focus on the process and its gendered nature. At the end of each Board meeting, gender had to be addressed anyway by checking for 50 % female grantees. To put it more bluntly: When striving to fulfil the quota, any gender-imbalanced distribution of grants is corrected anyway. The formal gender goal is met anyway, irrespectively of the gender sensitivity in the formal assessment process in the Board meeting and in the steps prior to the Board meeting. The argument here is not that Board members ignored gender or any gender policies consciously, it is more that the Board did not reflect on this, there was no awareness about gender as a relevant category in the assessment process beyond the number of female grantees. This way, gender and gender equality policies were reduced to the representation of women grantees. And more generally, this focus on the gender equal approval rate has the potential to narrow down the understanding of gender to the representation of women (grantees).

The empirical findings from implementing a quota in the ESPRIT programme provide food for thought regarding the underlying general ideas of a quota: A quota at the end of the assessment process means that if the funding outcome is gender-imbalanced, the outcome will be corrected by re-scoring and re-ranking, so that a gender-balanced distribution of grants (quota) is achieved. This way a quota indicates that a group is disadvantaged, while another has advantages and that a policy is needed to counteract these imbalances.

6.2 Excellence

Excellence was discussed in the FWF Board meetings when addressing the applicant, the research content and also the remote reviewers. From a gender perspective, a few risks were identified which address gendered norms of the excellence concept.

6.2.1 Risk of biased excellence

Indicators to measure scientific excellence have been widely discussed as a potential factor for gender bias (e.g. Rees 2011), focusing mainly on the number of publications, citations and impact points. When FWF Board members discussed the quality and excellence of ESPRIT applications, this focus was found as well, practicing a 'traditional' concept of excellence (risk 4).

Board members expected that excellent researchers were portrayed as geniuses, looking for the remote reviewers' use of superlatives and exaggerated notions for describing applicants and applications. However, there might be differences between female and male remote reviewers in how they apply such hyperboles and how much they question an applicant's self-presentation that would justify this use of language. Differences in the self-presentation have been discussed as a factor for gender bias (see e.g. Vinkenburg et al. 2021). Making Board members aware of this use of language and making efforts to mitigate it, could decrease this risk for gender bias.

A second layer of this risk is that ongoing discussions about revising the excellence concept would not be fully considered. We have found, however, that Board members argued that proposals without an outstanding, but promising track record are fundable, which fits the early career stage of the ESPRIT applicants. However, it could also be an indication for practicing a 'revised' concept of excellence. The FWF is a signatory of the DORA declaration, an initiative to change the research culture, to foster a broader

concept of excellence and adapt assessment criteria and procedures accordingly (DORA 2014). Some of the DORA standards have been integrated in the formal ESPRIT assessment guideline, like limiting the number of important publications to ten and listing research activities beyond publications, explaining career breaks, and remarking that *“journal-based metrics like the journal impact factor should not be included”*.

However, in Board negotiations, no reference was made to DORA and it was not stated explicitly that metrics should be avoided. This can be explained in two ways: It could indicate that awareness needs to be further developed, but could also mean that it is already incorporated in daily work practices. In this context, it was pointed out by FWF that ESPRIT is only one of more funding programmes discussed in an FWF Board meeting and the Board members are equal over the meetings.

Assessment criteria for Board and Office members need to be clear and clearly communicated, for example by pointing out DORA principles as *“especially for early-stage investigators, (...) the scientific content of a paper is much more important than publication metrics or the identity of the journal in which it was published”* (San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment, DORA). Further, DORA states that a broader set of indicators should be applied, *“such as influence on policy and practice”* (DORA). As the FWF signed the declaration on a strategic level, applying DORA in the assessment practice in this direction by Board members, remote reviewers and Office members could be enhanced. These (DORA) standards – specifically for early-career researchers in ESPRIT – could be formalised to transfer them into practice.

A similar clarification seems relevant for interdisciplinary research, which was argued to have the potential to increase the share of female researchers and to push a more innovative research culture, as already stimulated within women-only funding programmes.

6.2.2 Risk of not understanding the impact of Gender in Research policy

A risk closely related to scientific excellence is that gender (and other social dimensions) is not integrated in the creation of new knowledge. FWF requires applicants to integrate gender in the design and implementation of research projects (GiR), in line with EC standards (EC 2022). Consequently, ESPRIT remote reviewers had to assess how gender was addressed in research projects. In Board meetings, little reference was made to this policy, most Board members did not seem aware of this policy and its objective.

When observing Board negotiations, we identified the risk that the underlying aim, the narrative and the impact of this policy are not clear to all Board members. An understanding of how gender is inscribed in various research topics and how gender aspects contribute to more excellent research seemed lacking.

This is why guidance and clear instructions on how to assess the integration of the sex and gender dimension in research projects should be provided for reviewers (and applicants), and online access to international resources, such as the Gendered Innovations Portal and the GenPORT portal could be offered. Examples of how to apply this policy in various research topics and gender knowledge that better enables reviewers to assess this can stimulate mutual learning. To enhance awareness on this topics, FWF could implement a policy that asks the chair or other FWF members to make sure that GiR is picked up in negotiations systematically.

Nevertheless, we need to be aware that even when ‘revised’ excellence criteria are formalised, they are not necessarily applied in practice in a systematic manner. When new standards are implemented, Board members need to be well-informed. And then it also takes time and practice to become used to their application. The fact that FWF Boards are a permanent group which meets several times a year could be a chance to enhance awareness and build capacities in this respect.

6.3 Gender in Board meetings

6.3.1 Risk of highlighting vs. ignoring gender

In FWF Boards we could identify tension between highlighting the sex/gender of applicants and ignoring sex/gender altogether. The first was primarily fostered by the quota (see above). Gender also came to the fore when sex/gender was made explicit when applicants were introduced to the Board members; thus, the applicants’ gender became a relevant issue in the assessment process.

While the representation of female applicants was an issue, little awareness could be identified in respect to the gendered character of organisational processes and knowledge creation: Gender was rarely discussed in respect to the assessment process and the gendered character of assessment criteria; in particular, awareness and capacity were lacking on how to assess GiR.

6.3.2 Risk of gendered language

When observing panel meetings in other RFOs, we learned that some tried not to mention the gender and names of applicants. Instead, only the proposal ID number was used for introducing applicants (“IDXXX-100 works on...”). RFO representatives immediately intervened in case an applicant’s gender, name or any personal pronoun (“she”) were mentioned.

In contrast, in FWF Board meetings personal information was shared (like the applicant’s name, gender, the potential host institution or the potential collaborators). Using personal pronouns [“HE would like...”] or the German male/female form [“DER Antragsteller möchte...”] makes the applicant’s gender obvious. Bringing in this kind of information might create a ‘personal atmosphere’ and might shift the focus of Board negotiations to the person (and not so much to the research content and research quality). This can give way to the attribution of typical characteristics to female and male applicants and to activating gender stereotypes, which impacts a gender-neutral assessment process negatively. FWF could promote a ‘gender-free’ language and thus foster a more objective atmosphere, which helps to establish a more gender-neutral negotiation practice and to avoid that Board members activate existing gender stereotypes.

6.4 Suboptimal ungendered assessment practices

General suboptimal practices illustrated that FWF Board members had and used space for interpretation and selecting what is discussed when making funding decisions, including the risk that different standards are applied for different applications.

6.4.1 Calibrating funding categories

When observing Board meetings, we learned about an informal calibration practice for selecting grantees. To get granted, applications need to be assessed with an 'A'. All applications with A- are entered into a pool that gets discussed in case that not enough As were allocated at the end of the first discussion round. Sub-grades (A-, B+) were introduced to be able to distinguish and rank the applications in a more detailed manner.

Yet, to be able to do this ranking more specifically, the sub-grades (A-, B-, etc.) were specified by adding fine-tuned descriptions, like 'a very long minus', a 'short minus', etc. This was done informally, without being specified in written documents and without coordinating with other Board members.

6.4.2 Calibrating the formal structure of the FWF assessment process

Beside the Board, it became obvious when studying decision making in FWF Boards, that the FWF Office played a relevant role in the assessment process as well. The FWF scientific officers and reporters (delegates of the main research performing organisations in Austria) constantly collaborate for three years. They select the remote reviewers and transfer the ratings from remote reviewers into funding categories then presented to the Board to be confirmed or rejected.

As the GRANteD research focus was on Boards only, it could not be investigated how this process – to develop the "Bürovorschlag" – was conducted in practice and whether and in which way gender played a role in this context. This needs further investigation, also focussing on the gender awareness and gender competence of Office members (some analysis can be found in the annex).

While the FWF Board consists of national researchers only (due to the legal basis), it can be stated that in other RFOs developments were observed to bring in more international panel or board members, e.g. NCN and SRDA panels. SFI uses only international panel members.

6.5 FWF as a game changer

6.5.1 Applying strong formal gender equality policies in practice

RFOs in general and the FWF in Austria as the main funder for basic research play a crucial role in setting the standards for how to do research by defining the standards for what research is funded. This fact was highlighted in interviews with FWF staff and Board members, pointing out the transformative potential that a funding organisation has when challenging existing structures of the research ecosystem.

Fostering gender equality has been an FWF objective for decades and strong formal gender equality policies have been implemented. In the GRANteD analysis of the formal GE policies in place, "*a relatively low overall risk for gender bias in FWF funding*" was identified (Husu, Peterson 2022, p. 102).

FWF as a key actor for promoting equal chances of female researchers in the Austrian science system had implemented women-only programmes in the past. These were now shifted to a mainstreaming approach, integrating gender elements in all FWF funding programmes (Zimmermann 2023). ESPRIT was seen as pioneer for that approach, offering insights and learnings for other programmes.

Studying how policies are applied in practice in Board meetings provided some generic insights, both general and gender-specific, like a limited gender awareness when applicants were introduced by their personal name and their gender, or when Board members expected that excellence was discussed in hyperboles. GiR was hardly discussed in Boards, although it is specified in the FWF guidelines and should be negotiated in the context of scientific excellence.

These are examples of formal policies in place which were not fully practiced yet and which can be improved. Bringing comprehensive and advanced formal GE policies into practice can be a demanding process that requires awareness, as in some respects, this process demands a change in the reviewers' mindsets (e.g. no metrics, addressing gender in research design and content). The reviewers need (more) gender awareness and a deeper understanding of gendered structures in science.

It also needs to be clear who is accountable for implementing formal GE policies in practice. This could be the chair or observers.

6.5.2 Building capacities for reforming research assessment

When implementing new policies, RFOs transform formal standards for research that is funded, and by this ask applicants and reviewers to apply the standards in practice. This way, RFOs can 'educate' both stakeholder groups, applicants and reviewers. A relevant question is how RFOs make them able to apply these formally defined standards in practice.

Our research shows that applying innovative formal policies in practice – policies to foster gender equality and policies to improve the assessment process – is not an easy task. It is not sufficient to implement a formal policy. Further, providing instructions and guidelines to support the implementation does not guarantee that formal policies are properly applied in practice.

When a new policy assessment criterion or assessment step are implemented, reviewers are expected to adapt their behaviour. We found that this does not work quickly; although when support material like instructions or guidelines are provided, reviewers did not stick to them automatically. Yet, when reviewers are asked to reform or change the mode of assessing grant applications, it helps when they have appropriate capacities, competences and awareness to understand the underlying ideas and objectives of a new policy. To get used to these new standards, reviewers need time and space to practice. Only then, these innovative elements can be assessed or applied properly.

Building these capacities is different for the various actors in the assessment process: Board members can negotiate and calibrate within the Board; they can bring in and exchange their experiences and learn from each other. Board members often are active in various international RFOs and so become used to different policies. Their awareness is inspired by the standards in these RFOs; they might share them with other colleagues. This way internationally active reviewers might enable mutual learning between each other.

Also in FWF Boards, more gender awareness and competence could facilitate the work. In this respect, the challenge to raise awareness for gender bias was pointed out, despite tailored trainings being offered.

When implementing the quota, it was demanding to make clear why a gender-balanced outcome was requested and how this refers to the ESPRIT narrative to mainstream gender.

In contrast, remote reviewers do the assessment on their own/individually. The assessment is facilitated as they remotely enter their scores in a very structured template, but they lack any chance of calibration. As the quality of their scoring is discussed by the FWF Office and the Board, receiving feedback on this from FWF would be a possibility for 'external' calibration and for adjusting the individual assessment in the future.

In our observations and interviews, we learned that reviewers from overseas often have more gender sensitivity and thus potential to make the European reviewers more gender-sensitive. In this respect, one Board member argued that reviewers need some time to develop this gender-sensitiveness, but *"reviewers are scientists and scientists are used to integrate findings in their thinking"* (BM-5). Some interviewees highlighted the need to increase reviewers' gender awareness and argued that in a few years, reviewers should only be selected when they are gender-sensitive. In case reviewers are paid, those without gender-sensitiveness should not get (full) money (SH-1).

For FWF this would mean that, when selecting remote reviewers, reporters need to check their gender-sensitiveness. Further, Board members, who make the final decision, would need to prove their gender competence as well.

6.5.3 Fostering gender knowledge of reviewers

FWF has implemented a Gender in Research (GiR) policy, addressing applicants and reviewers. It asks applicants to take gender into account when designing and implementing their research projects and reviewers to assess the applicants' uptake of this policy. As this new element of excellence needs to be assessed in more and more RFOs, we were interested how this GiR assessment takes place and what can be learned from observing and interviewing FWF decision makers.

As discussed in section 4.2.5, FWF Board members did hardly refer to GiR, which might indicate a lack of awareness for this indicator of excellence. When addressing GiR, we observed that Board members' capacities to understand the objective of this policy differed and some were lacking awareness at all. Board members in the meetings made no reference to any specific GiR awareness measures.

FWF remote reviewers are the ones who assess GiR as an element of excellence; more precisely, remote reviewers assess the adequacy of the applicants' approach. To be able to do this assessment properly, remote reviewers need some gender awareness in general and in their respective research field. As remote reviewers were not interviewed, no empirical evidence is available about how aware and how well-prepared FWF remote reviewers feel. However, we have information from SFI remote reviewers, which shows that this awareness is widely lacking (see Schiffbänker et al. 2023a).

For FWF remote reviewers no trainings are offered, so there is also no training on how to assess GiR. And as remote reviewers have no chance to exchange experiences or best-practice examples in their respective research field, it is difficult for them to build up capacities, also on how to assess GiR. A challenge – that

also emerged in other GRANteD RFO case studies – is thus whether and how remote reviewers can be best informed about this new policy and made accountable for applying it properly. In this respect, FWF staff argued that it is already difficult to recruit remote reviewers, and trainings would require additional time. Further, FWF remote reviewers are selected for each proposal specifically and do not necessarily review a second time.

So, capacity building is more demanding as there is no pool of reviewers. An adequate format for building GiR capacities of remote reviewers seems to be a challenge; having a gender expert in the Board would be an option. Furthermore, monitoring and feedback loops will be needed to check whether the FWF GiR objectives are achieved and what kind of support is needed for the various stakeholders to increase their GiR capacities.

However, this capacity is now required and needs to be assessed in various RFOs. Putting more focus on GiR is in line with other funders, e.g. in the next round of the Excellence Initiative, the German DFG has explicitly called for the inclusion of gender perspectives in research, *"equality, inclusion, diversity will be a relevant decision criterion"* (DFG 2023). FWF, together with other RFOs, could address remote reviewers and provide support for them to develop capacities for being able to assess GiR properly.

6.5.4 Engaging universities

FWF funding goes directly to research performing organisations and this way, universities can be made more accountable for fostering gender equality. Indeed, it was argued by some interviewed stakeholders that when women-only programmes were still in place, universities knew that their female researchers can bring in this earmarked funding. This could then be used to develop the female PIs' careers and to employ further team members.

As this FWF funding line has now been dismissed, universities need to support female researchers' careers more actively and offer various support instruments, beyond the gender targets set up in their Performance Agreements (*Leistungsvereinbarungen*). This might have positive implications on the gender composition of research teams and the position of women.

The ESPRIT programme requires a mandatory mentor and a mentoring work plan as an element of the application. This can be seen as step to strengthen the responsibility of universities for supporting female and male early-career researchers.

6.5.5 Virtual Board meetings

The FWF was the only RFO where we could observe online as well as on-site meetings. While the sample of two online and one on-site meeting is too small to generalise findings, we could explore some characteristic practices in each format. We noticed that overall, virtual decision making is more structured, with less interactions and shorter negotiation phases. In section 4.5.2, we discussed that less interaction might reduce the critical perspective and thus could decrease the quality of the assessment.

Nevertheless, this higher efficiency can be seen as an advantage – in addition to saving Board members' time and reducing travelling and traffic. This way, in particular reviewers with care obligations (mainly

women) might benefit from online Board meetings. Furthermore, online panels/boards are less costly for RFOs and save CO₂, so they are beneficial also from an ecological point of view. This way, online meetings are especially convenient for international panels and Boards. As FWF Boards are composed of researchers working in Austria only, the advantages might be less relevant. Beyond this, FWF Board members are nominated for three years and thus their participation might not depend as much on the meeting format.

7 TAILORED RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the empirical findings, the GRANteD project aims to provide ideas for further improvements of the grant assessment process, both on a general level and from the perspective of gender fairness and inclusion. These evidence-based recommendations can be seen as ideal ideas to mitigate bias, serving as inspirations for FWF to enhance existing policies and deciding on new priorities to make the FWF grant assessment process more (gender-)fair.

Table 3 Overview of risk areas for gender bias

Risk area	Field of action	Recommendations to mitigate risks	Comment
Quota	Definition of quota	1. Making clear which balanced funding outcome is intended: same number of F/M grantees, same success rates or same budget spent for F/M grantees	In the existing documents divergent definitions were found.
	Rationale for quota	2. Increasing support by explaining why quota is relevant (e.g. in ESPRIT briefing session)	Specify when quota becomes relevant in Board process
	Observation period	3. Extending the period to check for the quota to one year (or to two or three years like SRC).	
	Quota in relation to discipline	4. Applying existing ESPRIT policy for women in NTS (affirmative action), defining a quota per scientific discipline (gender budgeting) 5. Analysing where the money goes: which topics, how are female researchers represented there (= gender budgeting)	
	Number of female applicants in NTS	6. Trying to increase number of female researchers in NTS, e.g. by offering specific support in application phase or by providing incentives for universities for female PIs (see SFI) 7. Bringing in international perspectives/standards for how to attract female researchers in NST 8. If female applicants in male-dominated fields are younger: think about regulations to weight younger applicants differently	E.g. SFI: number of male applicants per university is limited, if female applicants apply more applications can be submitted.

Risk area	Field of action	Recommendations to mitigate risks	Comment
	Intersectionality	9. For the future: As the EC is now pushing for more inclusiveness beyond gender, have in mind also other underrepresented groups that might need to be encouraged to apply, e.g. researchers with a migrant background in Social Science /Humanities	
Excellence	DORA Narrative CV	10. Defining accountability for applying DORA principles in practice (Office, Board) 11. Raising awareness by communicating them broadly 12. Providing clear instructions for remote reviewers and Board members for how to assess elements of a more qualitative CV	
	GiR	13. Explaining why GiR is relevant for more scientific excellence 14. Implementing clear guidelines for Board on how to address GiR 15. Providing information/trainings/room for exchanging experiences on GiR assessment for reviewers	Added value: GiR policy can increase gender awareness of remote reviewers and Board members in all disciplines
Assessment practices in Boards	Gender blinding Gendered language	16. Implementing a formal policy (guidelines) for gender-neutral language used in Boards, e.g. ID (no personal information on gender/name/affiliation of applicant and SV) 17. Gender blinding already in FWF Office 18. Making Board members avoid hyperboles	Need to change language might increase general gender awareness
	Gender awareness of reviewers	19. Advancing general gender awareness of reviewers to facilitate applying (advanced) GE policies (GiR, intersectionality)	
	Calibration of sub-grades	20. Specifying calibration process (length of A-) to increase transparency	
	Equal standards	21. Specifying what exactly is discussed in Board meetings (quality of reviews, applications, Board members' assessment) 22. Defining accountability for applying same standards in all applications (chair or FWF/external observers)	
		23. Sharing experiences on innovative elements of the assessment process, e.g. a short reflexion round could be scheduled at the end of the ESPRIT negotiation session	Opportunity to pick up ideas for improvement
	Mentoring	24. Making mentoring a fixed element of discussing excellence of application in Board meetings: to stress responsibility of universities for careers	

Risk area	Field of action	Recommendations to mitigate risks	Comment
Assessment process (formal)	Intersectionality	25. Integrating intersectionality strategically in the assessment process	Taking into account inequality criteria beyond gender: age, ethnic background which might intersect
	FWF Office	26. Work of Office could be checked for potential gender bias	
	Timing of Board meetings	27. Thinking about different time schedule so Board members have evenings available for private duties	

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9 ANNEX

9.1 Further FWF data

Table 4 ESPRIT approval rates by gender and scientific discipline: first three ESPRIT board meetings (one 2021, two 2022)

11/2021-05/2022 three Board meetings observed by GRANteD	Number of Applications			Share of applications		Number of approved applications			Share of approved applications	
	women	men	all	women	men	women	men	all	women	men
Biology and Medicine	35	29	64	55%	45%	11	5	16	69%	31%
Natural and Technical Sciences	14	56	70	20%	80%	4	18	22	18%	82%
Humanities, Social Sciences	32	22	54	59%	41%	11	3	14	79%	21%

Table 5 ESPRIT approval rates by gender and scientific discipline: all 5 ESPRIT board meetings 2022

5 Board meetings 2022 (incl. 2 observed by GRANteD)	Number of Applications			Share of applications		Number of approved applications			Share of approved applications	
	women	men	all	women	men	women	men	all	women	men
Biology and Medicine	53	46	99	54%	46%	18	12	30	60%	40%
Natural and Technical Sciences	23	68	91	25%	75%	9	18	27	33%	67%
Humanities, Social Sciences	41	39	80	51%	49%	12	10	22	55%	45%

Compared to the Board meetings observed by GRANteD, in all Board meetings in 2022 (including two meetings observed by GRANteD) women have a significantly higher approval rate in Natural and Technical Sciences.

PART B: RESULTS AND LEARNINGS FROM THE FWF APPLICANT SURVEY

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarizes the results of the GRANteD applicant survey sent to applicants of the FWF's „ESPRIT Programme“. It looks into gender disparities among applicants in relation to several dimensions of gender inequality in research and academia which were identified in the scientific literature. Furthermore, the analysis also compares successful and unsuccessful applicants which provides insights into potential factors that could be relevant for grant success. The report closes with a discussion of the results.

Keywords: applicant survey, grant success factors, gender bias, pilot

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1 INTRODUCTION

There are ample gender disparities in research as documented in the literature (Sugimoto and Larivière 2023; Kozlowski et al. 2022; Zheng et al. 2022). These disparities are not just a relic of the past but continue to shape the research system in the present and will continue to do so in the future. Gender disparities are both cause and effect of unequal opportunities among different groups and individuals to progress and succeed. The research funding system is built on the ideas of competition and of the selection of the most excellent and brilliant researchers and their research proposals. Research grants are not only necessary to carry out research, to generate data and publish research papers but they have become an indicator for excellence and therefore research funding is “making” research careers. Any inequality or bias in this system, its structures and processes will lead to significant disadvantages and lower chances for successful research careers.

The aim of the GRANteD applicant survey has been to gather information on gender disparities among applicants as well as on main factors that are responsible for a successful grant application. The literature identifies several issues that impede the careers of women in research, apply less often for grants, are less successful and often have a lower academic performance measured by bibliometric indicators (Eloy et al., 2013; Waisbren et al., 2008, Jebesen et al. 2019). In the following paragraphs, we will briefly discuss the main issues that affect academic careers and performance of women in respect to research funding applications.

However, there are certain indicators that possibly have a major role in the career of a scientific researcher. For example, having a helpful supervisor, a strong mentor and supportive colleagues, for instance, can open many doors and opportunities but also helps to understand the requirements for a successful academic career much better. Consequently, early career researchers who have a strong formal or informal support network have better chances to be successful in grant applications and in academic careers. Women researcher compared to their male colleagues experience a lack of supervision, career guidance, support and cooperation in their research environment (Benschop and Brouns 2003; Moss-Racusin et al. 2012; Howe-Walsh and Turnbull 2014). The differential support offered to women and men in research is a result of their lower integration in formal and informal networks (Gupta et al. 2004; Van den Brink and Benschop 2012) as well as of pervasive gender stereotypes and implicit gender bias: women are perceived as less competent and hireable and are offered less support by their superiors (Moss-Racusin et al. 2012). Hill et al. (2010) conclude that women have higher intentions to leave academia due to “dissatisfaction with departmental culture, advancement opportunities, faculty leadership, and research support” (Hill, Corbett, and St Rose 2010, 24).

Another issue that impedes career advancement of women and increases their intention to leave academia and research is that women often do not feel that they fit or belong into their research environment or academia in general and that they do not believe that they have the relevant competencies and skills to succeed (Van Veleen and Derks 2020; Welde and Laursen 2011). Moreover, women tend to assess their own performance less favourably than equally performing male colleagues (Lindeman et al. 2019). Stereotype threats like “the masculine superhero stereotype of the successful academic” (Van Veleen and Derks 2020) and other organisational and cultural barriers affect the feelings of belonging and fitting in of

women in academia but also in other settings (Stewart and Valian 2018; Welde and Laursen 2011). There is evidence that feelings of belonging have a strong influence on academic success and performance (e.g., Glass and Westmont, 2014; Stewart and Valian 2018). Consequently, women with a low sense of belonging may even “self-select” themselves out of grant applications (i.e. they might not even try to submit a proposal) or will not seek support for writing their application (Jebsen et al. 2019). Blake and La Valle showed that women are less likely compared to men to consider themselves as eligible to apply for Wellcome Trust and Research Council grants (Blake and La Valle 2000, 96).

The “the masculine superhero stereotype of the successful academic” (Van Veelen and Derks 2020) also denies that researchers have commitments and responsibilities outside their academic jobs. Although work life/family balance issues in principle concern all researchers at some point in their careers, women are still experiencing higher conflicts between work and especially their care responsibilities as they still shoulder the main burden of care and domestic work (Thun 2019; Sugimoto and Larivière 2023) – nearly in every country. Therefore, careers of women in academia are significantly more likely to be affected by care responsibilities and a lower availability and presence. They are non-linear and interrupted careers and do not correspond with the picture of the ideal academic or ideal professional (Ramos et al. 2015; Herschberg et al. 2018; Lynch et al. 2020). Especially women in their early career stages are heavily affected as family formation collides with the formation of an academic career, establishment of reputation and visibility and high insecurity due to fixed term work contracts (Cardel et al. 2020; Goulden, Mason and Frasch 2011; Ceci and William 2011). Women with care responsibilities and especially mothers of young children switch to part time work, receive a lower pay, remain in more junior positions, leave academia and research or even exit the labour force completely (Cech and Blair-Loy 2019; Lynch et al. 2020). But as Cech and Blair-Loy (2019) point out, this is not only a mothers issue as also fathers are affected by the care-free model and working culture in academia but not to the same extent as women. Male researchers seem to be significantly more often partnered with a stay-at-home spouse who takes over the domestic and care work compared to women (Schiebinger et al. 2008).

Another factor that is mentioned as inhibiting career advancement of women is their stronger involvement in so called academic housework (Jebsen et al. 2019; Hanasono et al. 2019; Heijstra et al. 2017; Heijstra, Steinhorsdóttir and Einarsdóttir 2016; Guarino and Borden 2017). This means that women are using more of their working time for teaching activities, management tasks, administrative work or emotional labor supporting their students and colleagues and consequently have less time available for research work or writing publications and grant applications. This also contributes to leaky pipeline and glass ceiling phenomena (Heijstra, Steinhorsdóttir and Einarsdóttir 2016; Oleschuk 2020) and consequently can also reduce the success chances of women in research funding.

As already discussed above the different barriers women are facing in their careers have an impact on their career progression or as different barriers or experiences of disadvantage are adding up affect women’s decision to leave academia or research at all. How these barriers are affecting the productivity and performance of women compared to men is assessed and discussed by scholars not unanimously. Whereas some research results seem to point to a significant performance gap between male and female researchers (Cole and Zuckerman 1984; Long and Fox 1995; Lutter and Schröder 2020) other, mostly more

recent results are challenging these results (Nielsen 2015; Rørstad and Aksnes 2015; Besselaar and Sandström 2017; Ramos et al. 2015; Xie & Shauman, 2003). As reported by some of these studies research productivity does depend more on the position of the researchers within the research system and as women are positioned differently compared to men in terms of positions and disciplines they might have a lower number of publications or less impactful publications (Nygaard, Aksnes and Piro 2022; Besselaar and Sandström 2017; Rørstad and Aksnes 2015; Xie & Shauman, 2003). Thus, explaining the performance gap between researchers we can ascertain that sex differences are mediated by position and status which are reflecting gender differences in career progression and advancement. Furthermore, Rørstad and Aksnes (2015) report that only a small part of the variance in productivity can be explained by academic position, age or gender. Most of the variance is related to other factors not included into the regression analysis and could be due to care responsibilities, different career support, imposter syndrome and (lack of) integration into the science system. Although, Lutter and Schröder (2020) report for their study of German sociologists that care responsibilities do not affect the productivity gap between men and women. Rather, it seems to depend on the levels of achievements of women predating childbirth as lower performing women experience a stronger motherhood penalty whereas the publication output of highly productive and successful women is not affected by their care responsibilities (Lutter and Schröder 2020). But, Derrick et al. (2021) show that the level of engagement in caregiving is a much stronger predictor of academic productivity than the presence of children in the household: “the more engagement with parenting, the lower the productivity” (Derrick et al. 2021, p.14) Consequently, also men who engage in parental activities are experiencing lower productivity.

More recently, in the wake of the **COVID-19 Pandemic** and the measures introduced to prevent an uncontrolled spread of the disease have amplified existing gender inequalities (Fisher and Ryan 2021) as women are shouldering the main load of additional caregiving due to lock downs of schools, kindergartens and nurseries (Frize et al. 2021). Consequently, the COVID-19 Pandemic has impacted negatively on the available time for research of women researchers and their academic productivity (Minello et al. 2021) which has led to a decline in manuscript submissions by women (Pereira 2021; Cardel et al. 2020; Andersen et al. 2020; King and Frederickson 2021; Kasymova et al. 2021, Krukowski et al. 2021) and possible also to fewer or less successful grant applications of women.

There is also evidence that female and male researchers are interested in and attracted to different research fields and disciplines that is highly visible in the study choices of women and men and their representation in different scientific disciplines (European Commission 2018). However, women seem also to focus their research more on social or societal impact: Gonzales et al. (2015) report that women put more emphasis on social innovations than on technological solutions suggesting different orientations of research objectives of women and men. At the same time, it seems that applicants who more strongly focus their research on societal problem solving are also less successful in research funding and their research careers.

The aim of the GRANteD applicant survey is to answer the following main research question: Are there differences between women and men applicants especially in respect to the factors and dimensions listed

above? And if so, do these differences affect the success chances of female and male applicants? This leads to the following hypotheses that we try to test in the subsequent analysis:

Hypothesis #1: Support from a mentor¹¹ or supervisor is associated with higher chances of grant success. Especially male applicants are more likely to be supported by a mentor or supervisor in their career development compared to female applicants, which will lead to higher chances for male applicants when it comes to grant selection.

Hypothesis #2: Male applicants have a higher sense of belonging and therefore higher chances of success compared to female applicants.

Hypothesis #3: Female applicants are more engaged in care responsibilities for children and the elderly and therefore have a lower research performance and consequently lower chances of success compared to their male colleagues.

Hypothesis #4: Female applicants use less working time for research and publication activities compared to their male colleagues which reduces their success chances.

Hypothesis #5: Female applicants report more often that their academic productivity was delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic compared to their male colleagues. Consequently, women have lower success chances than their male colleagues.

Hypothesis #6: Male applicants exhibit higher research performance scores (measured in successful grant applications) and consequently have higher success chances.

The aim of this report is to summarize the results of the GRANteD applicant survey conducted among applicants of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) “ESPRIT Programme¹²” 2022. The survey was sent out to all (successful and unsuccessful) applicants of this grant who have signed an informed consent sheet during the application process. Its target group are highly qualified post-docs from all scientific disciplines who hold their PhD (or equivalent qualification) for not more than five years at the time of the proposal submission and must demonstrate that they are authors of international scientific publications and that they will be supported by a mentor in their career development during the implementation of the ESPRIT grant. It aims at fostering “*the career development of researchers from all disciplines by carrying out an independent research project as principal investigator.*”¹³ Among the more specific objectives of the ESPRIT programme is the objective of supporting outstanding women researchers. Therefore specific measures to promote gender equality are in place for this call. For instance career breaks due to parental leave, illness or caring responsibilities which might have resulted in lower numbers of publications, limited international experiences or atypical career paths will be treated equally in the peer review process. Furthermore, applications of female applicants will be prioritized if they are assessed as equally qualified and their

¹¹ This hypothesis does not address the mentor for the ESPRIT application but mentoring relationships prior to the ESPRIT application.

¹² Early-Stage-Programme: Research-Innovation-Training

¹³ See <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/fwf-programmes/esprit-programme> (last visited on September 12, 2022).

proposals are of equal quality compared to a male applicant. The aim is that approval rates for projects of male and female applicants are balanced¹⁴.

The FWF operates in a national context that enables and demands research funding as well as research performing organisations to develop and implement ambitious gender equality policies. Austria comprises a well developed framework for promoting gender equality in the whole society as well as in research and innovation. Husu and Peterson (2022) report that gender equality actions have a high legitimization across the FWF and these policies do promote adequate participation of women in research teams as well as the integration of the gender dimension and intersectional approaches into research. The FWF gender equality policy is very comprehensive as it addresses all risk areas with counteracting measures as awareness raising, gender balance in decision making, eligibility rules taking into account family related and other career breaks, gender data collection, gender dimensions in research content and several other measures that support gender equality in their decision making procedures as well as in implementing research grants (Husu and Peterson 2022).

The report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides information on the sample and methodology used and discusses data and representativity issues. Chapter 3 shows the results according to the dimensions of grant success asked in the online-survey. Chapter 4 summarizes the results, draws conclusions on the main hypotheses described above and discusses open questions that may be answered once more data is available also from other countries. Chapter 0 consists of an Appendix, holding additional information on data preparation and analysis as well as additional figures and tables not included in the main text.

¹⁴ See ESPRIT Application Guidelines:

https://www.fwf.ac.at/fileadmin/files/Dokumente/Antragstellung/ESPRIT/esp_application-guidelines.pdf (last visited on September 12, 2022)

2 SAMPLE AND METHODOLOGY

The survey was designed based on results reported in the literature on reasons for differential career advancement and grant success of women and men and related the hypotheses outlined above. To operationalize the different concepts like research performance, belonging, care responsibilities we have tried to build on previous surveys designed by the GRANteD consortium members like the DZHW Scientist Survey¹⁵ or building on other surveys or scales where possible like the AIP Longitudinal Study of Astronomy Graduate Students¹⁶ or the GEAM tool¹⁷. For measuring belongingness, we built on a scale developed by Slaten et al. (2017) and adapted it slightly to our purposes. We have also tried to measure previous/past research performance through survey questions about previous grant application behaviour and especially successful grants and the total amount of funds received through successful applications. Additionally, we have asked applicants whether they have received scientific awards or prizes e.g. best paper awards or prizes for their PhD thesis etc.

Different drafts of the survey were discussed in the GRANteD consortium and also with members of the GRANteD stakeholder committee. The questionnaire was programmed and implemented by JOANNEUM RESEARCH (JR) via SoSci Survey, hosted on a secure server of JR. It was sent out to a sample of colleagues who tested the questionnaire in terms of technical functionality and clarity. Out of 188 applicants to the FWF's "ESPRIT Programme", 156 agreed to be contacted and invited to the GRANteD applicant survey. The survey was carried out via three waves. The first invitation to the online-survey was sent out to the first wave of applicants (59 persons) via E-Mail on December 16th, 2021, followed by three reminders over the course of almost 2 weeks. On March 29th, 2022 the survey was sent out to the second wave of applicants (52 persons), followed again by three reminders. On May 25th, 2022 the survey was sent out to the third and last wave of applicants (45 persons), followed by two reminders. The survey was closed on July 8th, 2022. Within this timeframe of three waves, altogether 103 applicants (55%) responded by completing the online-survey.

As common in many survey data studies, non-response and non-coverage is a common potential problem that has to be taken into account by checking and correcting for it. Particularly, unit non-response may be relevant in this case. In order to examine whether the sample of applicant responses is representative of the population (all applicants), certain characteristics of all applicants, provided by the FWF, got included into the evaluation procedure, while still keeping applicants identity anonymous. The following three graphs compare the sample characteristics to available population characteristics. Those characteristics include the funding decision and the gender.

Figure 1 shows the proportion of successful (approved) and unsuccessful (not approved) applicants in the sample (n=103) compared to the proportion of the population (all applicants, N=188). As can be seen, the distribution of the sample does not fit exactly the distribution of the population. The share of approved

¹⁵ <https://www.wb.dzhw.eu/en/about>

¹⁶ <https://www.aip.org/content/longitudinal-study-astronomy-graduate-students>

¹⁷ <https://geam.act-on-gender.eu/>

applicants is slightly overrepresented and the proportion of not approved applicants is underrepresented. Despite the fact, that the discrepancy is existing, it does not seem to be extremely high. The gender specific discrepancy between the sample and the population can be investigated in the next graph. Figure 2 shows the distribution of applicants in the sample compared to the population by gender and funding decision. Overall, 43% of applicants (N=188) to the „ ESPRIT Programme“, are female. In the population, the female share is smaller than the male share, meaning there are in general less female applicants than there are male applicants. However, the gender distribution of applicants in the sample equals not exactly the distribution of the population. In general, there is a higher share of women in the sample than in the population. Hence, the sample has a slightly higher share of successful female applicants. In Figure 3, the distribution of successful and unsuccessful applicants within each gender can be examined.

Figure 1: Funding decision, sample vs. population

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Figure 2: Funding decision by gender of applicants, sample vs. population

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Figure 3: Gender by funding decision of applicants, sample vs. population

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

In this report, the analysis is based on estimating population descriptive statistics using the collected sample survey data. The focus here lies primarily on differences between approved and not approved applicants, with special considerations of gender. The aim of this work is to identify systematic differences of gender and gender specific factors in the context of grant success. With a number of 103 applicants, the sample is relatively large compared to the population ($n=188$). Therefore, it possesses a fair amount of statistical power. However, as mentioned above a potential bias could be detected by visible investigation. Table 1 shows the contingency table of numbers and the shares of gender and grant decision. Comparing this contingency table to the population pendant (Table 2), it is even clearer that there is a bias stemming from female applicants in the sample. However, the value for each cell in this contingency table inhabits a seemingly small bias. Furthermore, to inspect whether this bias is significant, a Goodness-of-fit-test is performed, to examine whether the distribution of frequencies in the sample is representative of the population distribution. Results imply that the sample distribution fits the population distribution. The exact procedure of these tests is explained in the appendix at section 5.2. The results of the tests indicate that the bias is insignificant and the sample is randomly drawn from the population. Therefore, the sample is assumed to be representative.

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Table 6: Sample differentiated by funding decision and gender, absolute and relative numbers (n=103)

Funding decision	No. of observations			Share		
	Approved	Not approved	Total	Approved	Not approved	Total
Female	20	28	48	19%	27%	46%
Male	15	40	55	15%	39%	54%
Total	35	68	103	34%	66%	100%

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Table 7 : Population differentiated by funding decision and gender, absolute and relative numbers (n=188)

Funding decision	No. of observations			Share		
	Approved	Not approved	Total	Approved	Not approved	Total
Female	28	53	81	15%	28%	43%
Male	28	79	107	15%	42%	57%
Total	56	132	188	30%	70%	100%

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Field and background of applicants

Before going deeper into the survey results, some further background information on the applicants is necessary. In this first chapter, the following questions will be answered:

Which scientific areas do the applicants assign themselves to and are there differences in the success-rate concerning individual areas?

Is applicant success connected in any way, to whether or not one or both parents of the applicants have received a PhD degree or worked as a researcher?

Are there differences when it comes to applicants' nationalities?

Looking at the sample with respect to the scientific area of applicants (see Figure 4) shows that most applicants assign themselves to the field of Natural Sciences (59%). The other fields are nearly equally distributed between the applicants, each around 10% (Health Sciences 9%, Economic & Social Sciences 10%, Arts and Humanities 12% and Applied Sciences 11%). Figure 4 shows that the distribution is similar in the not approved group but the approved group differs in its distribution. Natural Sciences still have the largest amount (66%). However, Health Sciences (3%) are under-represented in the approved group compared to the general distribution just as Economics & Social Sciences (6%) while Arts & Humanities (17%) are slightly over-represented. Therefore, applications from the Natural Sciences and Arts & Humanities seem to have been more successful than applications from other fields. Note that the analysis with respect to the scientific area of applicants is based on their selection in the online-survey and not on data provided by the FWF in order to ensure comparability between the case studies of GRANteD.

The distribution of men and women with respect to the individual fields differs significantly (see Figure 68 in the appendix). The largest number of male applicants assign themselves to Natural Sciences (67%) followed by Applied Sciences (16%), fewer assign themselves to Arts & Humanities (7%), Economics & Social Sciences (4%) and Health Sciences (5%). In comparison, female applicants are a bit more equally distributed among the fields. The biggest amount of female applicants assign themselves to Natural Sciences (50%) too followed by Arts & Humanities (17%) and Economics & Social Sciences (17%). While 13% of the female applicants belong to Health Sciences and just a few assign themselves to Applied Sciences (4%). To conclude, besides Natural Sciences, which is the biggest proportion in both groups, female applicants more likely belong to Arts & Humanities and Economics & Social Sciences and men more likely belong to Applied Sciences.

Figure 5 shows the proportion of approved and not approved women and men by scientific areas. In general, the mostly approved scientific area is Natural Sciences for all successful applicants (66%). Comparing now Figure 68 with the upper (approved) part of Figure 5, the success shares of female and male applicants can be compared while also taking the underlying distribution of females and males within the different scientific areas into account. It can be noticed that the grant success of the applicants reinforces

the gender differences in the scientific fields. Approved female applicants belong to Natural Sciences (55%), Arts & Humanities (30%), Economics & Social Sciences (10%) and Health Sciences (5%). None of them belongs to Applied Sciences. The difference becomes apparent when having a look at the approved male applicants: in the survey sample, 80% of successful male applicants have applied for a grant in the field of Natural Science and 20% in the field of Applied Science. This does not necessarily indicate a gender bias, it can rather be explained by the horizontal segregation of female and male applicants between scientific fields in general. Still it can be noticed that the distribution of scientific fields in the not approved group is similar to the whole group. Therefore, we assume that the chance of being successful seems to be higher for male or female researchers when their scientific field is dominated by their own sex.

Figure 4: Scientific areas among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Figure 5: Scientific areas among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

FWF's "ESPRIT Programme" is limited to post docs with an academic age not older than 5 years. However, child care time is excluded from these 5 years in order to provide equal opportunities for applicants with care responsibilities. Therefore, as Figure 6 shows 96% of applicants have an academic age lower than six years and 4% have their PhD degree for more than 6 years. Therefore, the ESPRIT applicants are a quite homogenous group in respect to academic age which is also reflected in the position of applicants (see Figure 17).

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Figure 6: Academic age of approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Figure 7: Academic age of approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Altogether, 101 (of the 103) survey respondents indicated their nationality and 32 different nationalities have been indicated. Only 17% are Austrian, 11% are German, 8% are Italian and 6% from Iran.

3.2 Work and position

This chapter provides some more background information on the responding applicants. This should serve as context in the following chapters. The main questions in this chapter are:

- Which type of organisation are applicants mainly affiliated with? Do they hold a temporary or permanent contract?
- Are there differences related to applicants' careers, such as positions or work outside of academia?

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- Are there differences with respect to applicants' working conditions, such as team membership or number of working hours?
- How independent were applicants when choosing their research topic for the FWF application?

Among the survey respondents, 72% affiliate with a Higher Education Institution (HEI) at the time of their application (see Figure 8). Another 19% affiliate with a Public Research Organisation (PRO), 5% with other and 5% with no academic or research organisation at the time. All different affiliations are represented in the approved and not approved group. Further, differences between female and male applicants, as can be seen in Figure 9, are insignificant. The share of approved applicants affiliating with HEI is nearly the same between male (64%) and female (65%). The other shares of affiliations in the approved group differ between the genders, although the original distribution is similar, as shown in Figure 71, 20% of the approved female applicants affiliate themselves with PRO and 15% have no affiliation, while 29% of the approved male applicants affiliate themselves with PRO and 7% have other affiliations. To conclude, although most applicants affiliate with HEI, the other affiliations also earn grant success. Especially women who do not have an affiliation at the time of submitting the proposal are comparatively successful which can be interpreted as an indication that the ESPRIT programme enables women to start a career in academia or public research.

Figure 8: Affiliation among approved and not approved applicants (n=102)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 9: Affiliation among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=102)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

On average, 29% of applicants already worked outside of academia since they graduated (see Figure 10). The share is similar for approved and not approved applicants. Considering also the gender of applicants, data shows that 38% of female and 22% of male applicants have worked outside academia (see Figure 72 in the appendix). Considering now the gender distribution between approved applicants (see Figure 11), female applicants who worked outside academia seem to have a higher success rate (50% of the approved female applicants worked outside academia since their graduation) than their male counterparts (just 7% of the male approved applicants worked outside academia since their graduation). The effect from working outside academia between female and male success seems to differ in its direction. From visible investigation, it looks like working experience outside academia have a positive effect on female applicant success while it seems to have a negative effect on male applicant success. But, the results show that the programmes funds women with non-linear research careers and enables them to enter academia or public research. Why this is not the case for men to the same extent would be an interesting topic for further exploration.

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Figure 10: Work outside of academia (after graduation) among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 11: Work outside of academia (after graduation) among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

On average, 87% of total survey applicants were working under fixed-term (temporary) contracts at the time of the application to the FWF (see Figure 12). Another 6% were working under permanent contracts, whereas the remaining 7% indicated to have no working contract at the time of the application. The share of fixed term or temporary contracts is higher for approved applicants (91%) while the share of permanent or open-ended contracts (3%) and no contracts (6%) is slightly smaller. Figure 73 shows that there are no obvious gender differences in this regard. All approved male applicants are working under fix-term contracts, while this is not the case for the female approved applicants (85% fixed-term, 5 % permanent¹⁸ and 10 % no contract), presented in the upper part of Figure 13. The high amount of applicants in a

¹⁸ According to the eligibility criteria for the ESPRIT funding programme, applicants should not have permanent contracts unless the contracts are linked to third-party funding. Considering that survey answers are subjective, the distribution of answers to this questions need to be interpreted with care.

temporary working contract is of course related to the fact, that all participants are in an early career stage where permanent contracts or positions are scarce.

Figure 12: Working contracts of approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 13: Working contracts of approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

All survey respondents who indicated having a fixed-term or permanent contract at the time of their FWF application (n=96) were asked about their contractual and total (including overtime) working hours per week. 11% indicated not having weekly hours defined in their contract. Among the remaining 91 applicants, 69% work full time (i.e. at least 36 hours per week). The remaining 31% work part time (i.e. less than 36 hours per week).

Comparing the distribution of **contractual working hours** between approved and not approved applicants differentiated by gender shows no difference at the median level. The median contractual working hours of approved applicants and not approved female and male applicants is 40 hours per week. However, it can

be seen that the variance of contract working hours is wider spread in the not approved group. Additionally the variance among female applicants in the not approved group spreads even wider.

However, considering the distribution of **total working hours** per week (estimated actual hours including overtime) the median of approved and not approved female and male applicants is 40 hours per week, except in the group of female approved applicants where the median is slightly over 40 hours (see Figure 15). While the variance differs between the approved and not approved group as well as between female and male applicants. First, approved male applicants, except a few outliers, are working at least 40 hours per week, 50% between 40 and 50 hours. Approved female applicants in comparison work not as many hours. Here 25% work between 30 and 40 hours per week, further 25% between 40 and roughly 42 hours per week, 25% between roughly 42 and 48 hours and the residual 25% between 48 and 55 hours. Second, the not approved group works significantly less hours per week than the approved group. Female applicants who were not approved spread the widest. Here 25% work between 5 and 30 hours, 25% between 30 and 40 hours, 25% between 40 and 50 hours and the rest between 50 and 60 hours per week. Their male counterparts work, except some outliers, at least 30 hours, 50% between 30 and 40 hours, 25% between 40 and 50 hours and the residual 25% over 50 hours.

This shows, that successful applicants rather probable work around 40 hours per week, while not approved applicants work much less in the one case or much more in the other case. Additionally female applicants spread wider in their weekly working hours than male applicants. However, a Kruskal Wallis test has shown that neither contractually working hours nor total working hours have a significant influence on the grant success.

Figure 14: Contractually working hours of approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=85)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 15: Total working hours of approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=85)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

As already mentioned above all participants are young post-docs, this becomes obvious when asking them about their working position, presented in Figure 16. Most of them (83%) are holding a postdoc level or equivalent and just a small part (17%) hold another or a higher position. When looking at Figure 17 and Figure 74 in the appendix, it becomes clear that this distribution is similar for both sexes and for approved and not approved applicants. Due to the ESPRIT eligibility criteria¹⁹ the group of applicants is quite

¹⁹ According to the eligibility criteria for the ESPRIT funding programme, applicants should not have senior positions or professorship at the time of the funding application. Considering that survey answers are subjective, the distribution of answers to this questions need to be interpreted with care.

homogenous in terms of their academic position. Therefore, no major differences between women and men applicants as well as between approved and not approved applicants are visible.

Figure 16: Working positions at the time of the application of approved and not approved applicants (n=94)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 17: Working positions at the time of the application of approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=126)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Figure 18 presents the working constellation of the participants between approved and not approved applicants. Generally, most of them (71%) work as part of a research group, 18% work alone, 7% work in ad hoc research teams and 3% are the leader of their own research group. The amount of applicants who work as part of a research group is not only bigger in the approved group (81%) than in the not approved group (67%), but also than in the whole group. That means applicants with this working constellation seem to have higher success chances.

The gender distribution in this regard shows that female applicants tend to work alone (24%) more often in comparison to the male applicants (13%) (see Figure 75 in the appendix) which corresponds with the fact that more female applicants are not affiliated with a research organisation at the time of submitting the application. Additionally, it is interesting that only male applicants are leading their own research group. Considering the gender distribution in the approved group, presented in Figure 19, it can be seen, that

female applicants who work alone also tend to be more successful than male applicants who work alone (13% approved female applicants work alone, while no approved male applicant works alone).

On the one hand, the working constellation as such seems not to have an enormous impact on the grant success. On the other hand, there are remarkable gender differences in the working constellation. The fact that female researchers rather work alone and male researchers more likely lead a research group might reflect existing gender differences in the research system.

Figure 18: Work in research group among approved and not approved applicants (n=94)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 19: Work in research group among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=94)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

All those applicants, who did work as part of a team or group at the time of the FWF application (n=77), have been asked about the group size. This distribution, presented in Figure 20, does not differ very much between the four groups, just small differences in the median level and in the variance are observable. Male applicants who were approved and those who were not do not differ at all in their distribution. A greater difference is visible among female applicants. Approved female applicants have a higher median level and a smaller variance. To sum up, it seems that the group size does not have a direct influence on the grant success.

Figure 20: Research group size among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=104)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

The majority of applicants (81%) was entirely free to choose their own research topic for their FWF application (see Figure 21). More than a half of the applicants (55%) agreed strongly or rather that the research topic was at least related to the research conducted in their PhD thesis. A very small share, but still a few, were influenced by their supervisor or by their superior in the decision for a research topic, fewer from their supervisor (6% rather agreed) and more from their superior (4% strongly agreed and 21% rather agreed). The number of those who were free to choose their research topic is slightly higher in the approved group. Female and male applicants answered this question in a similar way (see Figure 76 in the appendix). However, there are very small differences. Female applicants more often chose a research topic suggested by somebody else.

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Figure 21: Choosing a research topic for the FWF application among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

3.3 Time use and research aims

In this chapter, the focus lies on the more specific activities on which applicants spend their time. This includes research but also review work, supervising students and engaging with society. The main questions in this respect are:

- Are there differences regarding how applicants distribute their time between research work and other work related activities (such as administrative work or teaching)?

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- Are applicants who spend more time on research more successful in their grant application?
- Do applicants differ in relation to their focus of research and outreach activities?

Figure 22 shows how applicants on average distribute their working time across various activities (annual average). Note that in the online-survey, the time spent on the individual areas had to sum up to 100% of applicants' working time. In general, all participants seem to spend their time similarly. This could also be due to all of them being in a similar career state. It shows that all applicants spend the largest part of their time on research. On average, 60% of applicants' time is dedicated to this activity. Approved applicants spend slightly more time on research (63%) than not approved applicants (58%) do. However, these differences are so small and are therefore no indication for an influence of time spend on research on the applicants' success. In comparison, the applicants spend much less time on the other activities, so just a few will be mentioned. On average 9% of the applicants' time is spend on acquisition of third-party funds, 8% on reviews, 7% on supervision of students and doctoral candidates and 7% on teaching and examination obligations.

Considering the time spend on activities sorted by gender, a similar distribution can be observed (see Figure 77 in the appendix). Most of the time has been spent on research, while male applicants (62%) spent slightly more time on it than female applicants (57%) do. However, this difference is not significant. In return, female applicants seem to spend slightly more time on acquisition of third-party funds (11%) than their male counterparts (7%). Due to the homogeneous group the differences in time use are minimal.

Figure 22: Mean time spent on different activities (sum=100%) of approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Furthermore, applicants have been asked which aims they pursue with their research (see Figure 23). All applicants, both approved and not approved, conduct research in order to “move the frontier of our knowledge” (89% say that fully applies, 8% say that partly applies). To “educate the next generation of scientists” is also very important due to nearly all applicants partly or fully agreed (40% say that fully applies, 41% say that partly applies). Other aims, which seem to be reachable for the applicants through research is first to “educate the next generation of highly skilled professionals” (22% say that fully applies, 37% say that partly applies) and secondly to “contribute to societal problem solving” (31% say that fully applies, 26% say

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that partly applies). The other two aims that have been asked are not rated as important. These were firstly to “contribute to economic innovation” and secondly to “support specific social groups/stakeholders”. Overall, there are no certain differences between approved and not approved applicants.

The differences in this regard become bigger when splitting the group in female and male (see Figure 78 in the appendix). Interestingly female applicants found it more important to “contribute to societal problem solving” in research (44% say that fully applies, 29% say that partly applies) than their male counterparts (19% say that fully applies, 23% say that partly applies). Another aim where gender differences become obvious is to “support specific social groups/stakeholders”. Female applicants also rated that higher (21% say that fully applies, 27% say that partly applies) than male applicants did (1% say that fully applies, 10% say that partly applies).

According to these results, the most important research objective has been “to move the frontier of our knowledge”. Interestingly, female applicants share the same objectives as their male colleagues but more often additional emphasis on other objectives like societal problem solving or supporting specific social groups.

Figure 23: Research aims of approved and not approved applicants (n=103), “With my research I am aiming to ...”

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

The online-survey further investigated how often the applicants engage with society in their research, i.e. different actors or entities (see Figure 24). The data shows that the actors with which the applicants most

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often engage are users of their research: Altogether, 65% of applicants say they often or very often engage with them. There is only very little engagement among applicants with the other actors or entities. No differences can be recognised in this regard not only between the approved and not approved group but also not between female and male applicants.

Figure 24: Engagement with society among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Besides focusing on their own various research aims, 95 out of 103 applicants responding to the online-survey have spent at least some of their time in the 12 months prior to their FWF application on writing reviews. In the online-survey, applicants have been asked about the total (estimated) number of reviews written in the following categories:

- Review of journal articles or conference papers
- Written assessment of grant applications
- Participation in evaluation committees
- Participation in recruitment committees
- Evaluation of doctoral theses

To provide an overview, all occurrences were summed up to show the total number of reviews per applicant in the 12 months prior to their FWF application. However, it should be mentioned that by far the most common type of review is that of journal articles or conference papers, with an average of 4,5 reviews per applicant (median at 2 reviews).

Comparing the estimated number of reviews in the last 12 months prior to the application among approved male and female applicants and not approved male and female applicants, minimal differences are recognisable (see Figure 25). On the one hand, male applicants have a similar review behaviour independent of their funding success. On the other hand, female applicants differ in their review behaviour whether they are approved or not approved. Female approved applicants have a higher median level than not approved female applicants. Additionally, the variance of the approved group is also more widespread. Hence, a positive impact of the number of reviews on the grant success can be observed among female applicants, but not among male applicants. Interestingly an additional Kruskal Wallis test has shown that the total number of reviews in the 12 months prior to the FWF application has a significant positive influence on the grant success.

Figure 25: Review work in the last 12 months prior to the FWF application (no. of occasions) among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Altogether, 57 out of 103 applicants (55%) who responded to the online survey indicated that they have supervised master or PhD students in the last five years prior to their FWF application. On average, applicants have supervised four master and one PhD students within that period.

As shown in Figure 26 the number of supervised students in the last five years prior to the FWF application is among all participants very low and around 50% even have no students to supervise. The distribution between approved female and not approved female applicants is quite similar. However, the distribution between approved male and not approved male applicants differs. Not approved male applicants had supervised more students than approved male applicants that can be seen in the wider variance and the higher median level. While supervising students seems not to have a negative impact on the grant success among female applicants, it seems to have a negative impact among male applicants.

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Figure 26: Total number of supervised students (estimate) in the last 5 years prior to the application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

In the online-survey the participants were further asked, whether they experienced delays in their research due to the COVID-19 pandemic (see Figure 27). Overall, 28% of applicants say, they experienced significant and 46% some delays. Unsuccessful applicants reported to had experienced significant delays (37%) much more often than successful applicants (11%) had. Although the amount of applicants who generally experienced delays (significant or some) is similar between the two groups (71% in the approved group, 75% in the not approved group). Therefore, the amount of applicants who were able to conduct their research as planned despite the COVID-19 pandemic is nearly the same between the two groups. As expected the amount of applicants who were able to conduct their research even faster as planned is very small but still most of them are in the approved group.

Comparing female and male applicants (see Figure 80 in the appendix) shows that the experienced delays are quite similar between male and female applicants. Still female applicants (33%) indicated more often to have had significant delays because of the pandemic than male applicants (24%) did.

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Figure 28 shows the gender distribution for successful and unsuccessful applicants separately. In this figure, it becomes clear that delays have a significantly negative impact on the grant success. The gender difference might be because female applicants over all experienced delays more often than male applicants, as had been shown in Figure 80 in the appendix.

To sum up research delays due to the COVID-19 pandemic have a negative influence on the grant success. However, no gender differences in this regard could have been recognised.

46% of unsuccessful female and 30% of unsuccessful male applicants experienced significant delays. This is a higher share than in the overall distribution for female and male applicants, but especially for women. From visible investigation, it can be concluded that female applicants are more strongly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, considering research delays. Whereas approved applicants reported considerable less delays of their research due to COVID-19 which is true for women and men applicants.

Figure 27: Research delays due to COVID-19 among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 28: Research delays due to COVID-19 among female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

3.4 Care responsibilities

Care responsibilities can also take up a lot of time and energy, which is why such responsibilities might have an indirect effect on the success rate of applicants. The main questions in this context are:

- How are care responsibilities distributed between female and male applicants? Are they shared equally or taken on mostly alone?
- Are there differences between applicants when it comes to taking parental leave?
- Are applicants without care responsibilities more likely to succeed?

In order to reflect the higher amount of responsibilities for taking care of younger children, their age limit was set to all those below 16 years. Moreover, care responsibilities for dependant adults have also been

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considered. Figure 29 shows that on average 28% of the applicants have some kind of care responsibilities (consisting of 25% who take care for children under 16 years, 1% who take care of dependant adults and 2% who take care of children and dependant adults). The relatively small share with care responsibilities is again due to the young age of the participants. 71% of all applicants have no care responsibilities at all and this amount stays the same when splitting the group into approved and not approved. Until now, care responsibilities do not seem to influence the grant success.

In the whole sample, male and female applicants are involved in care responsibilities equally (altogether 29% of female and 29% of male applicants), as shown in Figure 81 in the appendix. The same gender distribution can be found in the unsuccessful group, presented in Figure 30. Only, minimal gender differences exist in the successful group. While 30% of approved female applicants have care responsibilities, just 27% of approved male applicants have. Another mentionable point is that all participants who have care responsibilities for dependant adults were rejected.

Among the 27 applicants who take care of children under 16 years, 44% indicate being responsible for one child, 41% take care of two children, 11% of three and 4% (one person) of four children. The average age of children is 3 years. There are no significant differences with respect to the number or age of children between approved and not approved nor female and male applicants.

Figure 29: Care responsibilities of approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 30: Care responsibilities of approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

All applicants, which take care either of children under 16 years, of dependent adults or both were asked, whether they are the main caretaker. Altogether, 79% of applicants say that they share care responsibilities equally with someone else (see Figure 31). Only 14% state that they are the main caretaker and 7% indicated that someone else is the main caretaker. Already when comparing the approved and the not approved group it can be seen, that the amount of main caretakers is higher in the approved group (20%) than in the not approved group (11%) and in the whole sample (14%). Considering the gender distribution here might explain this phenomenon.

Figure 82 in the appendix shows that male applicants are never the main caretakers in this sample but 29% of female applicants with care responsibilities are also the main caretaker. Moreover, just male applicants with care responsibilities are not the main caretaker but rather someone else (13% of male applicants). Regardless the grant success this is a gender bias itself, which cannot be controlled by the policies in the ESPRIT program. In Figure 32 it can be seen how this affects the grant success of male and female applicants. Interestingly the amount of main caretakers under female applicants is higher in the successful group (33%)

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than in the unsuccessful group (25%). Therefore, it can be assumed that care responsibilities or even being the main caretaker does not have a negative impact on the grant success at least for female applicants.

Figure 31: Main caretakers among approved and not approved applicants (n=29)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Figure 32: Main caretakers among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=29)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

In general, care responsibilities tend to have an impact on research work: Overall 65% reported that care responsibilities affect their work to some or even to a large extend (see Figure 33). All approved applicants with care responsibilities indicated that it affects their work at least to a minor extend. This amount is lower in the not approved group whereof 26% even indicated their care responsibilities affected their work not at all. Figure 83 in the appendix shows what has already been described above that care responsibility have a greater impact on the work of female applicants than on the work of male applicants. While 93% of female applicants indicated their work is affected to some or a large extend by care responsibilities, overall 73% of male applicants indicated their work is affected to a minor (33%) to some (13%) or to a large extend (27%) by care responsibilities. A similar trend can be observed in the gender distribution among approved and not approved applicants, presented in Figure 34. Overall, it seems like successful applicants are more often affected by care responsibilities than compared to unsuccessful applicants.

Figure 33: How care affects work among approved and not approved applicants (n=29)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 34: How care affects work among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=29)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Finally, all applicants were asked whether they have ever taken (or are currently taking) any sort of parental leave – independent of the current age of their children. Altogether, 15% of applicants say they have already taken parental leave. There are significant gender differences when it comes to parental leave periods as Figure 85 in the appendix shows. Parental leave periods of women applicants were 12 to 25 months long with one outlier whose parental leave lasted over 50 months. In comparison to that parental leave periods of men applicants were at the maximum 5 months long.

When comparing the approved and the not approved group in this regard (see Figure 84 in the appendix) it cannot be recognised that the parental leave of female applicants harmed their grant success. The median level of the duration of parental leave is even higher in the approved group than in the not approved group and the outlier who took parental leave of over 50 months was approved too.

The impact of the duration of parental leave on the grant success becomes clear when comparing female and male applicants of the approved group with the not approved group, presented in Figure 35. Already

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approved male applicants tend to take shorter parental leave than not approved male applicants but the difference is even clearer when comparing approved and not approved female applicants. Approved female applicants have a lower median level than not approved female applicants and the maximum level of parental leave, except the one outlier, is slightly lower too.

Overall, the duration of parental leave does not necessarily have a negative impact on the grant success. Despite that a broad difference regarding the duration of parental leave exist between male and female applicants. This phenomenon can be explained by traditional gender roles in the Austrian society, as women rather than men take parental leave and if men do, the duration of their leave periods is much shorter than those of women.

Figure 35: Duration of parental leave (in months) among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=15)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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3.5 Support system

One central topic for detecting any sense of bias in grant selection is the amount of support that individual applicants received prior to their application. The support system can be very broad, ranging from colleagues to PhD supervisors or mentors. The main questions in this chapter are therefore:

- Do all applicants receive the same level of support when preparing the grant application?
- Do women and men report that they are supported by their supervisors and mentors to the same degree?
- Does the amount of support received have an impact on applicants' success?

Before taking a closer look at the support received by the applicants when preparing the FWF application, let us consider the general support by applicants' supervisors when it comes to career planning and advancement. In the online-survey, applicants had to rate how helpful they experienced their PhD supervisors in this respect (see Figure 36). Overall, 50% of the applicants considered their supervisor at least rather helpful in career planning and advancement, whereas 12% think their supervisors were hardly helpful and 8% indicated he/she was not helpful at all. The remaining applicants say that they did not seek their supervisor's help (28%) or cannot assess the level of support (2%).

Comparing approved and not approved applicants with respect to this question shows that approved applicants more often consider their supervisors as "very helpful" (26% in comparison to 13% in the not approved group) or "rather helpful" (34% in comparison to 32% in the not approved group). Additionally a bigger proportion (20%) reported that their supervisor was "hardly helpful". The number of respondents who indicated their supervisor was "not helpful at all" is very small in the approved group (3%) but a little bit bigger (10%) in the group of not approved applicants. Interestingly, 34% of the not approved applicants indicated that they did not seek their supervisors support at all – compared to 17% of the approved applicants. This shows that approved applicants got a higher level of support by their supervisors in general while not approved applicants did not receive the same level of support or did not seek it.

Furthermore, we want to know if there are gender differences in the earned support. This can be evaluated with the gender distribution presented in Figure 86 in the appendix. It shows that female applicants received significantly less support than male applicants did. Just 6% of the female applicants assessed the support of their supervisor as "very helpful" in comparison to 27% of the male applicants. The amount of applicants who rated the support of their supervisor as "rather helpful" is similar under male and female applicants. Still the amount who rated their supervisor as "hardly helpful" differs between male (4%) and female applicants (21%). This leads to the assumption that the level of support the applicants receive may not differ between male and female applicants, but the quality of support they receive differs enormously. Another mentionable point is that female applicants (31%) more often than male applicants (25%) not even sought the help from their supervisor.

Considering these gender differences when looking at the grant success (see Figure 37) it becomes clear how this lack of career support disadvantages female applicants. Generally, male and female applicants are more successful the more support they have received. All female applicants who indicated their supervisor as “very helpful” were approved. Furthermore, the amount of female applicants who did not sought help from their supervisor is much bigger in the group who was not approved (43%). For male applicants a similar pattern can be observed but here we also find some applicants who reported a strong support by their supervisors in the group of not approved applicants. although the effect is not as obvious as it is for female applicants. But the Kruskal Wallis test did not report any significant influence of the supervisor support on grant success.

Figure 36: Help from the supervisor in career planning/ advancement among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 37: Help from the supervisor in career planning/ advancement among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Besides the PhD supervisor, a mentor can have great impact on researchers' success: A mentor can open doors to the academic world, he or she can assist in organizing research trips, obtaining funding, publishing research results, building up networks and so on. Hence, it is of great interest for assessing applicant support, whether or not applicants had a mentor other than their PhD supervisor during their early career stages.

In general, most of the applicants had a mentor other than their supervisor (see Figure 38). 23% indicated to had a strong mentor, 45% had a mentor and just 30% had no mentor. Comparing approved and not approved applicants leads to the initial conclusion that the existence of a mentor not necessarily increases the probability to grant success. The amount of applicants who had a strong mentor is smaller in the approved group (14% compared to 28% in the other group) and the amount of applicants who had no mentor is bigger (37% compared to 26% in the other group).

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This trend is also visible in Figure 39 where the two groups with the gender distribution are presented. In this regard are no gender differences observable, neither is in Figure 87 where the overall gender distribution is presented in the appendix. Although male applicants more often had a strong mentor, nothing indicates that this increases the grant success.

Figure 38: Existence of a mentor (other than the supervisor) among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 39: Existence of a mentor (other than the supervisor) among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Next, let us take a closer look at the support received specifically for the 2021 FWF application. Generally, 28% received a lot of support for their application, 54% received some support, 11% at least received very little support and the residual 7% received no support or rejected the answer. Approved applicants tend to have received more support than not approved applicants had (see Figure 40). As Figure 88 in the appendix shows there are almost no gender differences in this regard. This also becomes obvious in Figure 43 where the distribution among approved and not approved female and male applicants is presented.

Generally speaking, the more support applicants received, the higher are their chances to be successful. Female and male applicants indicated that they have received similar levels of support.

Figure 40: Support for the FWF application among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 41: Support for the FWF application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

All applicants who reported at least some level of support (including “only very little”) were further asked, who they were supported by when preparing the 2021 FWF application (see Figure 42). Most of the applicants indicated to have been supported by their mentor (total 82%, approved 82% and not approved 83%) which reflects the requirements of the ESPRIT application guidelines. After that, the next most frequent answer has been “my colleagues” (total 43%, approved 52% and not approved 38%). Moreover, 33% of all applicants indicated to have been supported by the grants office of the host institution (36% of the approved applicants and 32% of the not approved applicants). Further 32% of all applicants indicated to have been supported by their international network (approved 42%, not approved 27%). Further important supporters who have not been mentioned so often are the family (total 22%, approved 24% and not approved 21%) and the PhD supervisor (total 20%, approved 24% and not approved 17%).

There are considerable differences between approved and not approved applicants for some features of support: not approved applicants indicated less often that they have received support from their colleagues, from an international network, from their PhD supervisor, the research team and from the

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grants office of their host or the home institution. This could be an indication that these support features increase the chances of success for applicants.

Now the question if there is a difference in the support system between male and female applicants will be answered (see Figure 92 in the appendix). Female applicants rather take advantage of support through the grants of the host institution, through their international network or their family. While male applicants rather be supported through their mentor, their colleagues, the grants of their home institution or science officers of the research funding agency. Therefore, female and male applicants tend to use different support systems.

Figure 42: Supporters for the FWF application among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Applicants were further asked whether they received specific trainings prior to the application. Overall, 58% of applicants have never received any sort of proposal-writing training neither for this application nor in

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another context, as shown in Figure 43. However, 33% have received a proposal-writing training in another context before, while 9% have received this sort of training specifically for the 2021 FWF application. It is remarkable how this distribution is nearly identical in the approved as well as in the not approved group. Similar is also the gender distribution in this regard (see Figure 93 in the appendix), except female applicants have slightly more often received proposal-writing training, 13% of female applicants for the FWF application and 36% in another context while just 5% of male applicants had this kind of training for the FWF application and 31% in another context. Interestingly Figure 44 shows that approved female applicants received proposal-writing training more often than approved male applicants did.

Figure 43: Proposal-writing training received by approved and not approved applicants (n=102)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 44: Proposal-writing training received by approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=102)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Additionally applicants were asked about their opinion on the career and mentoring plan which needed to be submitted with the ESPRIT application by all applicants and which should support the professional career development of awardees in the course of the project implementation. Applicants do not consider the career and mentoring plan as helpful for the career development of early stage researchers. Most of the applicants do not agree with this statement (84% of all applicants rather or strongly disagree) and there is no significant difference when looking at approved and not approved applicants separately (see Figure 45). There are also no pronounced gender differences in the assessment of the career and mentoring plan as visible in Figure 89 in the appendix.

Figure 45: The career and mentoring plan is helpful for the career development of early state researchers among approved and not approved applicants. (n=102)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

ESPRIT applicants also do not consider the relationship with an official mentor as important for the career development of early stage researchers. As presented in Figure 49 the majority of applicants do not think a relationship with a mentor is important, the answer category “strongly agree” was not even used (6% of all applicants, 3% of not approved applicants and 7% of approved applicants rather agreed with the statement). Comparing female and male applicants irrespective of the grant decision shows that female applicants also disagree more strongly with the statement than male applicants, but the difference is very small though (see Figure 97).

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Figure 46: The relationship with an official mentor is important for the career development of early stage researchers among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

In the third and last question in this section applicants have been asked if they received substantial support by their mentor already during the ESPRIT proposal writing stage. Compared to the other two question, applicants agreed more often with this statement. Overall 22% agreed and 72% disagreed that they received substantial support by their mentor already during proposal writing stage (see Figure 47). Interestingly, not approved applicants (29%) agreed more strongly with it than approved applicants (17%). Looking at the answers of female and male applicants reveals that female applicants (27%) agree stronger with the statement than their male counterparts (16%) (see Figure 91).

Figure 47: I received substantial support by my mentor already during the proposal writing stage among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

3.6 Self-efficacy and belonging

In this chapter, different indicators of self-confidence (or perceived self-efficacy²⁰) and belonging are analysed based on survey data. Whether or not applicants feel that they belong within their research group or how confident they are about their abilities can have great effects on their career choices and success. The main questions in this context are:

- How do applicants differ with respect to their self-confidence? Which factors are related to higher self-confidence-levels and are applicants that are more self-confident more successful?
- How does the sense of belonging in applicants' research group or institute affect other previously discussed indicators, such as the perceived support by their PhD supervisors or the existence of a mentor?

In order to assess the feeling of self-efficacy, applicants were first asked to rate from 1 to 100, how convinced they are of being excellent researchers. As the data shows, applicants are very heterogeneous when it comes to this self-assessment, with answers ranging from 13% to 100% convinced. The mean (73%)

²⁰ Perceived self-efficacy can be defined as "people's beliefs about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performance that exercise influence over events that affect their lives" (Bandura 1994).

and median (81%) levels, however, appear to be rather high. Hence, the majority of applicants tend to be very convinced that they are excellent researchers. In total, 95 applicants provided a self-assessment, the remaining 10 applicants selected “can’t say” or have not answered the question.

Figure 95 in the appendix shows how approved and not approved applicants rate themselves. The two groups assess themselves similar in this regard. The median levels do not differ noticeably only the maximum is higher among the not approved applicants. Comparing female and male applicants shows that male applicants rate themselves higher on the median level (86%) than female applicants (81%; see Figure 96 in the appendix). Even on average male applicants assess themselves higher (83%) than their female counterparts do (78%). Nevertheless, there is no statistically significant difference between female and male applicants.

The observed trends become even clearer when differentiating approved and not approved applicants additionally by gender (see Figure 48). First, it can be seen that the median level of male applicants in the successful and in the unsuccessful group is in both cases higher than the median level of female applicants. Whereas the difference is bigger in the approved group. Second, the group of unsuccessful applicants shows a wider spread, especially the maximum is higher than the maximum in the successful group. To conclude, male applicants seem to have higher levels of self-efficacy than female applicants and approved applicants seem to be somewhat more self-critical than not approved applicants.

Figure 48: Self-assessment on a scale from 1 to 100 of approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103), “How convinced are you that you are an excellent researcher?”

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Next, we are moving from the feeling of self-efficacy to the more specific feeling of belonging within the applicants’ research groups or department/institute.²¹ Figure 49 shows how applicants rate the experiences differentiated by the funding decision (approved, not approved). Overall, the experiences within applicants’ research teams or departments are very positive. The majority at least rather agrees with all the statements, which ask for the recognition on a social level on the one hand and for the recognition on an academic level on the other hand. However, the agreement is stronger for the statements that ask for the recognition on an academic level. Most applicants (86%) at least rather agreed that their research team/department values their contribution, 78% agreed that it provides them an opportunity to grow and 75% agreed that it supports them. Less applicants (69%) at least rather agreed that they are satisfied with the academic

²¹ In the online-survey, applicants received the same type of question either referring to their research group if they previously indicated to work in a group (and not alone) or referring to their department/institute if they indicated to work primarily alone. For the purpose of the analysis, both are shown in the same figures. Applicants without a contract at the time of the application did not receive the question.

opportunities in their research team or department. A very big amount of applicants claimed that they found it easy to establish relationships in their research team/department (81% at least rather agree), that they associate themselves with their team or department (82% at least rather agree) and that their cultural customs are accepted in their team or department (84% at least rather agree). Fewer applicants agreed with following statement according the recognition on a social level. 75% at least rather agreed to attend social events from their research team or department, just 66% rather or strongly agreed that they feel “at home” there and 65% feel similar to other people there. Furthermore, approved applicants more often agree with these statements that is to say that successful applicants tend to be more satisfied with their research group/department and feel more recognised.

Figure 97 in the appendix presents these experiences within the research teams differentiated by gender. Overall, female and male applicants reacted to the statements relatively similar. However, with most of the statements male applicants agreed more strongly than female applicants did. One exception is the statement that asks for the easiness to establish relationships within the team, here female applicants (85%) clearly agreed more often than male applicants (77%) did. With all other statements female and male applicants agreed to a similar degree or male applicants agreed stronger, which means that male applicants tend to be more satisfied with their research team and tend to feel more recognised. These assumptions will be analysed more specifically in the following part.

Figure 49: Experiences within the research team/department among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Further, a belonging score has been calculated: This score is based on the average agreement to each of the items shown in Figure 49 (alternatively referring to the department or institute). For this purpose,

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alternative answers (“can’t say” and “not applicable”) were excluded, taking the average responses on the scale from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 4 (“strongly agree”). Hence, the belonging-score is a real number between one and four, whereas a higher score indicates a higher sense of belonging.

Whether the answers are based on the experiences in the research team or refer to the entire department or institute depends on applicants’ group membership, as indicated in the online-survey. Looking first at how scores differ with respect to this group membership, data shows that researchers working in ad hoc research teams have a lower median belonging score (2) than those who indicate being part of a research group (3) or being the leader of a research group (4). Researchers, who generally work alone and referred their answers to the department or institute, show a relatively low sense of belonging (2). All scores depicted are median levels. Further calculations have shown that according to the Kruskal-Wallis test there is a significant difference on the 5%-level in the belonging score between researchers who work in a research team and the others.

Now looking at the funding decision with respect to the belonging-score indicates a higher sense of belonging among approved applicants (3.4) compared to not approved applicants (3.0) (see Figure 98 in the appendix). Note again that a higher score indicates a higher sense of belonging, with a maximum at four as it is the maximum in the Likert-scale. Hence, data shows that a higher sense of belonging is associated with higher chances of success. Furthermore, gender differences with respect to the belonging-score are presented in Figure 99 in the appendix, it shows what has already been assumed above – the median level of the belonging-score is higher for male applicants than it is for female applicants.

Until now, it seems like male applicants are more socially integrated in their research team or department and receive more acknowledgement from their colleagues. However, Figure 50 shows how the scores change when differentiating female and male applicants additionally by the grant success. Remarkably, there are no gender differences in the approved group, while they become obvious in the not approved group. To conclude, the more applicants are convinced that they belong to their research group/department, the higher their success chances are. Although this effect is observable for both genders, it is stronger for female applicants. However, there are no significant differences on the 5%-level in the belonging score between approved and not approved and male and female applicants according to the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Looking at the impact of applicants’ support shows that support by their PhD supervisor has an impact on the sense of belonging. There is a significant correlation on the 5%-significance level. Not like the support of a mentor, where no significant correlation with the belonging score on the 5%-significance level could have been found. Somewhat surprisingly, there is no correlation between the applicants’ belonging-score and their level of self-efficacy. Hence, there appears to be no clear connection between the perceived belonging within the applicants’ research group and their self-confidence levels. There is also no clear connection with applicants’ scientific area.

Figure 50: Belonging-score of approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

3.7 Past performance

The GRANteD applicant survey further asked about applicants' past performance in order to evaluate the weight and importance of certain indicators on grant success. Some of the main questions relating to past performance can be summarized as follows:

- Do applicants show different past performance levels concerning previous grants or awards?
- How many of them have already applied for or received grants over 50,000 EUR?
- How many of them have already applied for an FWF grant?
- What sort of scientific awards have applicants received prior to the application for the „ESPRIT Program“?

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Questions concerning past performance were **limited to the last five years** prior to the FWF application in 2022. Of course, all these questions are viewed with respect to grant success and gender of applicants. However, also other previously discussed indicators, such as the academic position or care responsibilities, may be of importance in this context and will be considered more closely.

Altogether, 52% of applicants have applied for at least one grant over 50,000 EUR, 22% have applied for smaller grants and 23% have never applied for any external funding in the last five years prior to their 2022 FWF application. This distribution does not change when splitting the group in approved and not approved applicants (see Figure 51). Looking at differences between female and male applicants (see Figure 100 in the appendix) reveals interestingly that a slightly higher share of female applicants – compared to male applicants – have already applied for grants over 50,000 EUR (56% of female and 49% of male applicants) and also for smaller grants (25% of female and 20% of male applicants). Figure 52 shows approved and not approved applicants additionally separated by gender. It is noticeable that the distribution among not approved applicants is the same as for the whole sample but it differs among approved applicants. Approved female applicants have more experience with applications for bigger grants but also smaller grants than approved male applicants. Quite a high share of approved male applicants (40%) has not applied for a grant in the last 5 years. Therefore, it can be assumed more experience with grant applications has a positive influence for female researcher, while it does not seem to have the same influence for male applicants.

Figure 51: Applications for grants over 50,000 EUR in the last 5 years prior to the FWF application among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 52: Applications for grants over 50,000 EUR in the last 5 years prior to the FWF application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

The applicant survey further asked all those, who have applied for at least one grant over 50,000 EUR (n=54), about the total number of received, rejected and currently pending grants in such size. It further distinguished between national and international grants. The applicants over all have had little experience with applications for such high grants, as was to be expected due to the composition of the sample. However, on the median level applicants have already applied for two national and one international grants over 50,000 EUR, on average the numbers are even a little bit higher (two national and two international).

Surprisingly, not approved applicants have applied for slightly more grants than approved applicants. Although the median for national and international grant applications over 50,000 EUR is three for both groups, the difference becomes clear when looking at the average level. Approved applicants have then applied for 3.6 grants and not approved applicants have applied for 3.9 grants on average. When comparing female and male applicants a difference becomes again only obvious on average and not on the median

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level. Male applicants have applied for 4.2 grants over 50,000 EUR, while female applicants have already just applied for 3.4 grants on average.

The total grant applications over 50,000 EUR differentiated by gender and grant decision is presented in Figure 53. Here the minor differences, which have been explained above, are more apparent. Looking at female applicants first, interestingly not approved female applicants have on the median level applied for more large grants in the last 5 years prior to the FWF application than approved female applicants have. When looking at male applicants the opposite trend becomes clear. Approved male applicants have a slightly higher median level and a higher minimum than not approved male applicants do, although the maximum of both groups is the same. Therefore, approved male applicants have a little bit more experience with applications for larger grants in the last 5 years prior to the FWF applications than not approved male applicants have. But overall, the differences between approved and not approved applicants are quite small.

Looking now only at previously successful grant applications (see Figure 54) shows a weak relationship between past success and the likelihood to receive a grant in the recent FWF application. As approved applicants have slightly been more often successful in the past. However, the difference to the not approved group is relatively small. Figure 101 and Figure 102 in the appendix additionally show the number of approved applications by grant decision and gender, respectively.

Figure 53: Total number of applications for grants over 50,000 EUR in the last 5 years prior to the FWF application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=54)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 54: Total number of successful applications for grants over 50,000 EUR in the last 5 years prior to the FWF application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=54)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Although the young age of the applicants in the ESPRIT Program, the total grant amount received in the last five years differs tremendously between applicants. Altogether, 86 applicants answered this question in the online-survey, whereas 54 indicated a concrete amount of received grant money in the last five years. The data does not only show a large variance, but also some significant (positive) outliers: The median lies at 85,000 EUR, the average at 115,421 EUR with a minimum of 2,500 and a maximum of 700,000 EUR. For the purpose of this analysis, outliers (over 200,000 EUR in this case) have been excluded, leaving 47 valid answers to this question.²²

²² The online-survey asked applicants to indicate only their share of collaborative grants. In case of very high total grant amounts it cannot be said for certain, whether applicants indicated the entire grant or only their share, leading to potential inconsistencies in the data. Outliers were defined as all values larger than the third quartile (Q3) plus 1.5 times the interquartile range.

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Figure 55 shows the total grant amount among approved and not approved female and male applicants (without outliers). It shows no significant difference neither between approved and not approved applicants nor between male and female applicants. The median level of not approved female applicants is higher than for their male counterparts and their approved counterparts. Not approved male applicants got the highest grant amount here. Considering this, the conclusion is that the received grant amount does not influence the grant success.

Figure 55: Total grant amount within 5 years prior to the 2020 FWF application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=47), without outliers

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Another indicator of past performance consists of previously received scientific awards and prizes. In the GRANteD applicant survey, respondents were asked about whether they had already received any of the following awards (multiple selection was possible):

- Conference best paper award
- Conference best poster award

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- Prize for PhD thesis
- Other scientific awards

Altogether, exactly 50% of applicants indicated that they have already received a scientific award (see Figure 56). Among them, nine applicants who have already received a conference best paper award, 21 a conference best poster award, 18 have received a price for their PhD thesis and 30 another scientific award.

As presented in Figure 56, the difference between approved and not approved applicants in this respect is vanishingly small. The same applies for the difference between male and female applicants, presented in Figure 104 in the appendix. However, it is noticeable that having earned a scientific award increases the grant success for female applicants (60% of approved female applicants have an award but only 39% of not approved female applicants) but not necessarily for male applicants (40% of approved male applicants have an award but 58% of not approved male applicants) (see Figure 57). However, there is no significant group difference regarding scientific awards between approved and not approved female and male applicants according to the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test.

Figure 56: Scientific awards prior to the FWF application among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 57: Scientific awards prior to the FWF application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Among all applicants that filled out the online-survey, 30% have already applied for a grant from the FWF in the last five years before the „ESPRIT Programme “. As shown in Figure 58, just a very small share of 3% already applied for a grant in the same funding line, 27% in another funding line and 1% in this and another funding line. Overall, all applicants are relatively unexperienced with applying for grants from the FWF. Nevertheless, the more FWF experience applicants have, the more successful they are. As shown in Figure 59, this influence seem stronger for male applicants than for female applicants, because the share of male applicants with experience is higher in the approved group than in the not approved group and the share of female applicants with experience is similar in both groups. At this point, it is also worth mentionable that over all applicants, male and female have experiences with FWF to the same degree but not the same type (see Figure 103 in the appendix). Female applicants rather than male applicants have experiences in the current funding line (as the predecessor of the ESPRIT programme was a women only programme). Male applicants just have experiences in other funding lines.

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Figure 58: Prior application to the FWF in the last 5 years among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 59: Prior application to the FWF in the last 5 years among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

3.8 Application process

This chapter focuses on the FWF application process for the „ESPRIT Programme“. The main questions in this chapter are:

- How much time did applicants spent on writing the proposal to the FWF?
- How did COVID-19 affect the time available for the application?
- How do applicants assess the evaluation and assessment procedure?
- How do applicants assess their own proposal with respect to the same criteria?

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Overall, the number of hours spent on the proposal range from 20 to 1500 hours. Applicants spent 188 hours on the proposal at the median level. Due to some outliers, the average is higher, at 261 hours. Figure 105 in the appendix shows the total number of hours spent on the FWF proposal by approved and not approved applicants. It shows that not approved applicants spent more hours on the proposal than approved applicants did. Although the median is slightly higher among approved applicants, most of them spend less than 250 hours. While not approved applicants tend to have spent more time as very high outliers are in this group and a greater percentage spent more than 250 hours.

Considering the difference between female and male applicants (see Figure 106 in the appendix) indicates that female applicants spent more time on the proposal at the median (200 hours) as well as the average (316 hours) level than men (median of 155 hours, mean of 208 hours). The gender difference persists also when comparing approved and not approved applicants by gender (see Figure 60). Approved female and male applicants differ tremendously, while not approved female and male applicants have a similar distribution.

The time spent on the FWF proposal also differs with respect to applicants' scientific areas: Applicants researching the Natural Sciences or Health Sciences spent more hours at the median level than those researching in the fields of Economics & Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities or Applied Sciences.

Figure 60: Hours spent on the FWF application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Another factor, which may have influenced the hours spent on the proposal, are time constraints due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The online-survey therefore asked applicants about their assessment of the impact of COVID-19 on the available time for proposal writing.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the implemented preventive measures, applicants reported different experiences of time availability with their FWF application. As shown in Figure 61, the majority (58%) have been able to work on their application as long as initially planned, 8% had significantly less time as planned, 16% had a bit less time and 14% indicated that they had even more time than initially planned. Among not approved applicants, delays have been more frequent. Figure 107 in the appendix shows that female applicants experienced not only time-constraints but also higher time availability more often than male applicants (while 67% of male applicants were able to comply with the time period set, this applies just for 48% of female applicants).

The negative influence of time constraints due to the COVID-19 pandemic on the grant success again becomes visible in Figure 62, where approved and not approved female and male applicants are plotted

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separately. Most obviously, 93% of approved male applicants did not report any time-constraints, the remaining 7% had just a bit less time than planned. This effect is not as obvious for female applicants, which overall experienced more constraints, as already mentioned. That indicates that being able to work on the proposal as planned has a positive effect on the grant success.

To get a sense of the impact of children, the answers of female applicants who indicated to have care responsibilities for children under 16 years have been compared with those who indicated to not have care responsibilities. From female applicants with children 58% indicated to had roughly equal time for the application as planned and 42% had a bit or significantly less time as planned. Whereas 76% of female applicants without children had equal or more time for their application and just 24% had less time as planned. Care responsibilities therefore are an important source of the time constraints faced by women applicants due to COVID-19.

Figure 61: Impact of COVID-19 on time spent on the FWF application among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 62: Impact of COVID-19 on time spent on the FWF application among approved and not approved female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Applicants were further asked to provide an assessment on a series of factors relevant for a successful FWF application (see Figure 63 and Figure 64). The relevance for the assessment should be rated along a four-level scale from “highly relevant” to “not relevant. Alternatively, applicants could select “can’t say / N.A.” in any case.

Overall, applicants rated the novelty of the research approach (77% highly relevant, 16% somewhat relevant) and the feasibility of the research design (72% highly relevant, 21% somewhat relevant) as the most relevant factors for a successful FWF application. Other factors that applicants consider as important are international visibility, the independence of the applicant, the reputation of the host institution, the fit to the strategic orientation of the RFO, interdisciplinarity and established network ties of the applicant in the academic community. Latter is perceived as relevant especially by unsuccessful applicants. Other factors like reputation of the PhD supervisor, reputation of the home institution, personal acquaintances between applicants and panel members, the presence of the candidates in non-scientific media, scientific

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awards or prices or the success in raising third-party funding are not perceived as relevant for funding success in the FWF ESPRIT programme. Interestingly, approved applicants rated the performance on bibliometric indicators as less relevant than not approved applicants did. Female and male applicants rate all factors similarly except one (see Figure 110 and Figure 111): the sex of the applicant is more relevant in the perception of female applicants (33% of female applicants think it is not relevant) but not so for male applicants (57% of male applicants think it is not relevant).

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Figure 63: Assessment of relevant factors for a successful FWF application among approved and not approved applicants (n=103), part

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 64: Assessment of relevant factors for a successful FWF application among approved and not approved applicants (n=103), part II

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

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Figure 65 shows, how applicants rate the assessment of the newly introduced CV format among successful and unsuccessful applicants. At this point, it must first be mentioned that the most frequent answers here is “can’t say” which might be explained by the fact, that the CV is a newly introduced tool and was not widely communicated by the FWF. However, most of the applicants, who gave an answer, agreed that the new CV format/ CV assessment recognizes their achievements better (50% of all agreed and 10% of all disagreed) and that the new CV format recognizes their contributions to the research community and society better (45% agreed and 14% disagreed). It is unsurprising that the answers of approved applicants are rather approving and the answers of not approved applicants rather critical. More specifically, not approved applicants rather agreed that they would need to rethink their modes of knowledge production and diffusion in the light of the new CV format in order to be more competitive in the future (33% of not approved and 16% of approved applicants agreed). Not approved applicants also agreed more often with the statement that the new CV format would have changed the assessment practice of reviewers (31% of not approved and 14% of approved applicants agreed).

The answers separated for female and male applicants are presented in Figure 112 in the appendix. As the figure shows there are no significant differences in the answer behaviour of female and male applicants, except female applicants seem to agree more with the statement that the new way of describing and recognizing different types of research outputs would have increased their chances to receive funding.

Figure 65: Assessment of the new CV format among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Figure 66 shows, how applicants rate the assessment procedure of the FWF's „ESPRIT Programme“. It is not surprising that overall approved applicants rate the assessment procedure better and fairer. For example, 57% of approved applicants at least rather agreed that all panellists were impartial, while just 37% of not approved applicants did. Not approved applicants on the other hand rather agree with statements, which indicate that the assessment procedure has been unfair. Just 27% of approved applicants indicated to think

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that the selection was a matter of luck, while 68% of not approved applicants agreed with this statement. As well as the statement, that the panellists would have not understood the application correctly (while just 9% of approved applicants rather agreed, 49% of not approved applicants at least rather agreed). Furthermore, approved applicants rather think, the funding decision was comprehensible (77% of approved applicants agreed and 43% of not approved applicants) and the panellists' comments were helpful (75% of approved applicants agreed and 48% of not approved applicants)

However, approved and not approved applicants have answered some statements similarly. The statement with which most of all applicants agreed is that the assessment criteria were clear and comprehensible (94% of approved applicants and 76% of not approved applicants agreed). The majority of the applicants also agreed that the procedure was transparent (83% of approved applicants and 61% of not approved applicants agreed), that the professional competence of the panellists was high (71% of approved applicants and 55% of not approved applicants agreed) and the professional quality of the assessment was high (86% of approved applicants and 62% of not approved applicants agreed). The statement to which most of the applicants disagreed or refused the answer has been that the selection was subject to political considerations (52% of approved applicants disagreed and 46% answered "can't say", 30% of not approved applicants disagreed and 53% answered "can't say").

To sum up, not only approved applicants but also not approved applicants perceived the assessment procedure as fair. Still, it has become clear that not approved applicants see the selection process more critical, which is a result of their unsuccessful application.

Interestingly, no significant differences are visible when comparing the answers to these questions of female and male applicants (see Figure 113 in the appendix).

Figure 66: Evaluation of the FWF assessment procedure among approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

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Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

3.9 Future plans and comments

Finally, the applicants were asked about their future career plans and whether they have anything to add concerning their perception of potential gender bias in the selection process. The main questions in this last chapter are:

- Do applicants differ in their career plans?
- Did applicants notice anything in the application process that points towards a gender bias?

Concerning the applicants' career plans the data shows that a vast majority of the applicants would be happy to remain in academia until they are eligible to retire (91% at least rather agree) and intend to apply for a permanent position in academia/ research soon (79% at least rather agree). Most of the applicants are not interested in a job outside of academia or research (16% of applicants are actively looking and 32% intend to look for such a job). However, not approved applicants are rather interested in a non-academic job (22% are actively looking and 40% intend to look for a job outside of academia) than approved applicants (2% are actively looking and 15% intend to look for a job outside of academia). While the majority of not approved applicants (76%) agreed that they intend to submit a revised or a new proposal at the next opportunity, just 20% of approved applicants agreed. Most applicants strongly disagreed that they would like to switch to a managerial function within academia. Female and male applicants answered this questions similarly (see Figure 114 in the appendix).

Figure 67: Future plans of approved and not approved applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANted Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

Overall, roughly 24% of the applicants answered the final open question on whether they have witnessed anything throughout their FWF application that strikes them as specific concerning gender inequalities. These answers are very different. The invented gender policies have been not only assessed as positive, but also as negative or insufficient. Some applicants pointed out the advantages of the gender policies in the context of the “ESPRIT Programme”, including the fact that parental leave has been subtracted when

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calculating the applicants' academic age. However, one applicant explained, that care commitments are still an obstacle for the grant success. On the one hand, few applicants reported to have experienced discrimination based on other aspects but gender, like ethnicity or race. On the other hand, some applicants reported unfairness because of the FWFs gender policies. Mostly male applicants criticised the gender policies with the argument that it leads to preferential treatment of female applicants. Additionally the reviewers' feedback has been criticised a lot for being unfair. For example, reviewers would not have known enough about the applicants' background to consider it appropriately in their feedback or the proposal would have not been understood correctly. Few comments were also about reviewers being unfair to female applicants or simply about unsatisfactory feedback.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Summarizing the above results, the survey sample consists mostly of applicants of the FWF “ESPRIT programme” from Natural Sciences and with smaller shares from Health Sciences, Applied Sciences, Economic and Social Sciences as well as Arts and Humanities. Applications in the Natural Sciences and the Arts and Humanities have a comparatively higher success rates and while the success rates of applicants in other broad disciplinary fields are comparatively lower. Women are particularly successful in Arts and Humanities and in the Natural Sciences whereas men applicants are more successful in Natural Sciences and in the Applied Sciences. Overall, the sample is quite homogenous in terms of positions of applicants and their academic age, which is a result of the specific eligibility criteria of the “ESPRIT programme”. Although the majority of applicants have an affiliation with an higher education institution or a public research organisation, there are some successful women in the survey sample that did not have an academic/research affiliation at the time of submitting their proposals. Women applicants and especially successful women applicants also reported more often that they have worked outside academia/research since they have completed their PhD thesis. This can be interpreted as evidence that the FWF ESPRIT programme allows early stage researchers with non-linear research careers to (re-)enter the academic field.

In the following paragraphs we will discuss whether the empirical evidence supports the hypotheses we have formulated in the introduction. Our **first hypothesis** was that a strong support from a mentor or supervisor will increase the success chances of applicants. As men are theoretically expected to receive more formal and informal support by mentors and/or supervisors they will also have higher success chances compared to their female colleagues. Summarizing the results related to this hypothesis, we observe that approved applicants more often consider their supervisors as very or rather helpful. Not approved applicants often did not seek the support of their supervisors for their career development, for whatever reasons. Additionally, more male applicants considered their supervisor as helpful compared to female applicants. Moreover, approved male applicants find their supervisors more helpful than approved female applicants. **Hence, data shows that success chances are enhanced by a helpful supervisor and male applicants tend to receive more career support by their supervisors than female applicants.** On the other hand, the majority of applicants say they did also have a mentor other than their supervisor during their PhD or Postdoc years. **However, the presence of a mentor did not affect the chances of receiving a grant from the FWF,** leading to no advantage of male applicants who do report having a mentor slightly more often than women applicants do.

Considering the data on the specific support for the FWF ESPRIT application shows **that applicants who report that they have received higher levels of support also tend to be more successful.** No gender differences concerning the proposal writing support were observable. But, there were differences in the types of support between approved and not approved applicants. Approved applicants relied more often on support from their colleagues, from an international network, from their PhD supervisor, their research team and from the grants office of their host or the home institution. This could indicate that these types of support increase the chances of success for applicants. Specific proposal writing trainings seem to have a positive effect for female applicants but not for male applicants.

The first hypothesis can be partly substantiated by the survey data as men report more career support by their supervisors which also increases their success chances. But for mentors this is not the case as there are no substantial gender differences visible in the data and these do not increase the success chances of applicants. The data shows that more proposal writing support translates into higher success chances in the case of the FWF ESPRIT programme although the correlation is not statistically significant and there are some indications that women who received proposal writing trainings have higher success chances compared to male applicants.

The **second hypothesis** assumed that male applicants have a higher sense of belonging and also higher success chances compared to female applicants. As the average outcome on the self-efficacy scale is rather high, the majority of applicants tend to be very convinced that they are excellent researchers. Additionally, the average rating among successful applicants is in general slightly lower and shows a higher variance than among unsuccessful applicants. Although men exhibit higher levels of self-efficacy than women applicants, gender differences in this context are not significant. Furthermore, the ratings of applicants' experiences in their research groups (belonging) are overall very positive too. For example, most of the applicants associate themselves with their research team, feel "at home" in their research team, feel that their research team values their contributions, and their team supports them. Male applicants more often strongly agree to various answer possibilities of belonging in their research team. In contrast to the self-confidence, the scale of belonging to the research team or department seems to have a positive influence on grant success. Applicants with a higher belonging-score are also more likely to be successful. Additionally, gender differences are evident in this regard. Male applicants tend to have a higher belonging-score than female applicants, though this trend is not as clearly visible among approved applicants as it is among not approved applicants. But, there is no statistically significant correlation between belongingness and funding success of men and women applicants observable. Applicants who rated the support of their PhD supervisor as (very) helpful also reported higher levels of belongingness whereas the support by mentors does not have an influence on the feelings of belonging of applicants.

Looking at the evidence above the **second hypothesis** can be confirmed – at least partly – as women do exhibit slightly lower levels of belongingness compared to male applicants. Although not statistically significant, there is some evidence pointing into the direction that higher levels of belongingness correspond with higher success chances – especially for women.

As a **third hypothesis** we formulated that female applicants are more engaged in childcare responsibilities and therefore have less time for research and grant applications which lowers their success chances compared to their male colleagues. In terms of care responsibilities there are significant differences between female and male applicants: Most applicants report that they share care responsibilities with someone else. There is a smaller group of applicants – consisting only of women reporting that they are the main caretaker. Nevertheless, this does not influence success chances of these women negatively as the share of female main caretakers is higher among approved applicants than not approved applicants.

Although, male and female applicants report to be involved in care responsibilities equally often with different degrees of involvement, the presence of children in the household or their age does not influence the success chances of applicants. Compared to men, women report more often that care responsibilities

affect their research work to a large or some extent. But, this does not necessarily lower their chances of success as the share of female (and male) applicants reporting that they are more affected in their research work by care responsibilities is comparatively high among successful female and male applicants – compared to unsuccessful women and men. Also parental leave periods do not negatively influence success chances of women or men applicants. Although women have much longer leave periods compared to male applicants this does not affect their chances of success as the average parental leave duration is similar between successful and unsuccessful women. This could be interpreted as a result of the FWF gender equality policies aiming at taking care responsibilities in the selection of proposals into account.

The care responsibilities hypothesis could not be confirmed as neither care responsibilities nor parental leave periods have a negative effect on success chances. Although women are more invested in childcare and also report that this affects their research work more than reported by male applicants, this does not lower their chances of success. One could even conclude that their success chances are even higher than for applicants with less demanding care responsibilities.

Another hypothesis formulated in the introduction is that female applicants use less working time for research and publication activities compared to their male colleagues which affects their research performance negatively and consequently reduces their success chances. Applicants spend the largest part of their weekly working time on research activities (60% of their working time). All other activities do not take up a bigger share of applicants weekly working time. For instance, teaching and supervision together only make up around 14% of the weekly working time. Although approved applicants report a bit more time for research activities, there are hardly any differences between approved and not approved. This is also true for male and female applicants: Female researchers report a little bit less time for research than their male colleagues but the differences in time use are insignificant. The data indicates no clear connection between time use patterns and grant success and no significant gender differences in this respect.

There are some gender differences in respect to research objectives: whereas all applicants report that they aim to move the knowledge frontier and to educate the next generation of scientists, female applicants report more often to aim their research at solving societal problems and supporting specific social groups or stakeholders. However, these differences in research objectives do not influence the success chances of applicants. Concluding, there is no evidence in the data that supports the assumption that women applicants are more invested in so called academic housework compared to the male applicants. Whether this means that, only such women researchers have submitted an application who are less engaged into academic housework or whether these results are generalizable for early stage researchers in the Austrian academia needs to be explored in other contexts.

We have also formulated a **hypothesis on the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic** on the lower success chances of female applicants due to their lower or slower academic productivity in the wake of COVID-19. There is clear evidence that non-successful applicants reported more often that their research work was significantly delayed due to COVID-19 compared to successful applicants. Grant success seems to be affected by COVID-19. Unsuccessful women applicants report even more often that their research work was affected than unsuccessful male applicants. Additionally, the survey also asked if applicants had more or less time for preparing the FWF ESPRIT application due to COVID-19. There are similar patterns:

unsuccessful applicants reported more often that they could not invest as much time as planned compared to successful applicants. Interestingly, this effect seems to be stronger for unsuccessful men applicants as they reported more often that they had less time than planned for their proposal compared to successful male applicants. For women applicants this is not the case as the differences are not as strong between successful and unsuccessful women applicants. Therefore, although women report higher impacts of COVID-19 on their research work and also that they have had less time than planned for writing their proposals, it seems that latter has affected male applicants more severely as those who reported less time were also more often not successful. Based on our data we can confirm the hypothesis that COVID-19 has affected research work and grant success negatively: for women and men whose research productivity was suffering and for men who had less time than planned for preparing a proposal.

Finally, we assumed that male applicants exhibit higher research performance scores (measured in successful grant applications) and therefore have higher success chances. Overall applicants do not have much experience with bigger grant applications (over 50.000 EUR) and have also earned only comparatively lower total grant amounts. This is of course a result of their comparatively young academic age. Consequently, the survey data shows that successful applicants do not have more experiences with grant applications as not approved applicants. Looking at gender differences we noted that approved female applicants have slightly less experiences with proposal writing compared to their successful male colleagues. For the group of not approved candidates only minor gender differences are visible. There is only a weak relationship between previous grant success and success chances in the FWF case. And the differences between women and men applicants are also not pronounced.

In terms of the total grant money earned by applicants in the last 5 years prior to their FWF application there are no significant differences between successful women and men applicants or between successful and unsuccessful applicants. Therefore, the previously earned total grant amount is not a good predictor of funding success in the case of the FWF ESPRIT programme. This result can be explained by the rather young academic age of the applicants and that they have not earned a lot of grant money yet which might differentiate them from other applicants.

There is some but rather weak evidence that past performance measured by engagement in grant applications and success of these applications does have an influence on the success chances in the FWF ESPRIT programme. But, contradictory to our assumption female applicants do not exhibit a significantly lower research performance compared to men in terms of previous proposal writing experiences and grant success.

Furthermore, we have tried to measure research performance also through previously received awards or prizes. Again, the overall picture showed that there are no differences between approved and not approved applicants in respect to previously received scientific awards and prizes. However, taking gender into account made evident that earning a scientific award increases the grant success for female applicants whereas this is not the case for male applicants: the share of male applicants with a previously received award or price is higher in the group of not approved applicants. Therefore, the last hypothesis was not confirmed by the survey data of FWF ESPRIT applicants. The differences in the data between women and men applicants are considerable small and therefore statistical not significant.

The results for the FWF applicants survey could confirm the hypotheses formulated in the introduction in respect to gender disparities only partially. The clearest gender disparities among FWF ESPRIT applicants were observable in relation to engagement in care responsibilities but this differential engagement had no effect on success chances of applicants. This could be interpreted that FWF policies aiming at mitigating the effect of engagement in care work (see Husu et al. 2022) are working as intended. Another important issue which should be highlighted here is that successful and unsuccessful applicants as well as women and men do not differ significantly in terms of past performance measured by prior submitted successful research proposal. This indicates that for this group of early stage researchers previous successful grants are not a good predictor for success chances, as applicants do not differ significantly in their proposal writing experiences and success.

5 APPENDIX

5.1 Data preparation

All data collected through the online-survey is limited only to those cases that reached the end of the survey (i.e. finished the survey) and with more than 50% of questions answered. In the case of the FWF survey, data can be considered as rather complete among all applicants that filled out an online-survey. Consistency checks were conducted to further clean the data.

Information that was added from data provided by the FWF includes the funding decision (approved/not approved), gender, scientific area and academic age (PhD year). Gender and scientific area were only added to check representativity of the sample. Data was provided by the FWF on the individual level for 156 applicants who signed the Informed Consent Sheet. Data on all 188 applicants was provided anonymously in the form of summary statistics and used only to check representativity. Representativity checks were conducted in different ways: (1) Relative frequencies were compared used contingency tables; and (2) a χ^2 as well as Fisher's exact test were calculated to check, whether the distributions are significantly different (see below for more information and results).

The results of part (1) of the representativity checks were presented in chapter 2 (Sample and Methodology). The results of both χ^2 and Fisher's exact test in part (2) confirmed that there is no significant difference between the sample and population distribution with respect to funding decision, gender. Small deviations between the sample and population distributions by gender are acceptable and considered when interpreting the results.

χ^2 Test

The one sample χ^2 test was used as a "Godness-of-fit" test. The test works non-parametric and is based on comparing whether the sample variance is equal to a given value (population variance). The Chi-square test statistic is given by

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(n - 1) s^2}{\delta^2}$$

where s^2 is the sample variance and δ^2 is the population variance. The null hypothesis states that the sample distribution fits the population distribution.

Test result

	stat.	p-value
χ^2	1.62	0.666*

* p-value equals 0.666 using explicitly simulated (based on 2000 replicates), and 0.654 using Chi-squared approximation

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5.2 Calculation of scores

In this report, scores were calculated based on the responses to selected questions.

First, a belonging-score was calculated. To do so, the average was taken over all ten items of a likert-scale asking about the experiences in applicants' research teams or departments/institutes. The likert-scale went from 1 (= "strongly disagree") to 4 (= "strongly agree"). A higher score therefore means higher average agreement, which is in line with a higher sense of belonging. Cronbach's alpha was used to test the correlation between items and to assess, whether the items included in the score measure the same construct. Cronbach's alpha takes on values between zero and one, whereas values closer to one indicate higher levels of consistency between items.²³ For constructing the belonging-score, the average answers over ten items were calculated. Cronbach's alpha was calculated to be 0.94, which can be seen as highly consistent and therefore forming an index is appropriate.

5.3 Additional figures

This chapter presents additional, relevant figures discussed throughout the text.

5.3.1 Figures

Figure 68 : Scientific areas of female and male applicants (n=103)

Source: GRANteD Applicant Survey (JR, 2022), Original Funding Data (FWF, 2022), own calculations.

²³ See <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4205511/> (last visited on April 15, 2021).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

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PART C: ANALYSIS OF FWF FUNDING DATA

THREE EUROPEAN FUNDING AGENCIES' USE OF REMOTE REVIEW AND SITTING PANELS

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1 INTRODUCTION

Research funding plays a pivotal role in advancing scientific knowledge and driving scientific newness and innovation. However, gender bias in research funding allocation has long been a prevalent issue that adversely impacts women scientists' careers and scientific progress. Gender bias in research funding has far-reaching consequences. It hinders career progression, reduces opportunities for women researchers to conduct impactful studies, and perpetuates a lack of diversity in scientific leadership. This paper explores the extent of gender bias in the panel review part of the process.

The underrepresentation of women in science and technology fields has been a persistent challenge, and research funding disparities contribute significantly to this issue. Gender bias in research funding allocation could occur at various stages of the funding process, including grant application review, evaluation, and decision-making.

The analyses in this report are dependent on and based on former work and results presented in several WPs from the GRANteD project: 1) Deliverable 2.1 outlined a strategy for researching the question of bias in the selection of project grants; 2) Reports D5.1 and D6.1 detailed the different forms of organization of the panel work in five cases from five countries.

The present analysis builds on a collection of data from 571 applicants and from 268 peer panelists (aka referees or sometime reviewers) in three of the completed case studies, Austria (FWF), Ireland (SFI) and Sweden (SRC).

1.1 The literature on biased funding

An analysis of the discussion concerning bias is laid out in the D1.1 report from the Granted project. We refer to that report for the recent theoretical, philosophical and empirical discussions with a focus on gendered funding and nearby policy issues.

The examination of gender disparities within the field of science yields multifaceted outcomes. Conducting an analysis of 17,000 papers spanning from 2013 Kahn et al. (2021), find that the majority of research outcomes exhibit inconsistencies. Most of gender disparities encompass key aspects such as productivity, impact, collaboration, careers, and grant success. The notable variance in results can be attributed to differences in data, methodologies, and approaches utilized in these studies. Consequently, these discrepancies have contributed to controversies and challenges in establishing a coherent understanding of the issue at hand. For recent insights and discussions on this matter, reference can be made to the works of Abramo et al. (2013), Ceci & Williams (2011), Kwiek & Roszka (2021), Lutter & Schröder (2018), Lutter et al. (2022), Nygaard et al. (2022), Witteman et al. (2019), as well as Van den Besselaar & Sandström (2017). Wennerås & Wold (1997) delved into the question of whether women's academic achievements are undervalued, signifying assessment based on criteria other than "pre-established impersonal criteria" as outlined by Merton (1942). Their investigation centered on 114 applications for post-doctoral fellowships submitted to the Swedish Medical Research Council (MFR) in 1994, revealed a significant gender disparity.

Their findings demonstrated that women were required to amass 2.5 times more journal impact points to attain a competence score equivalent to that awarded to men by the council's evaluation panels. This discrepancy was compounded by an additional factor – reviewer affiliation, commonly referred to as nepotism – which contributed to the observed outcome. It is noteworthy, however, that potential interaction effects were not explored in their analysis.

In a subsequent investigation conducted by Sandström & Hällsten (2008), utilizing data from the MFR competition for project grants in 2004 (distinct from post-doctoral fellowships), the trend of negative scoring for women, as observed in the Wennerås & Wold study, ceased to persist. Over a decade after the Wennerås & Wold study, the evaluation of applications no longer exhibited bias against women. Concurrently, the examination highlighted the discernible impact of both nepotism and an extensive list of publications on the evaluation process. During the 2004 assessment cycle, it was noted that women received approximately 5 % higher scores than their male counterparts, even when their performance was comparable (see correction by Sandström & Hällsten in 2020). However, whether this advantageous scoring for women translated into a corresponding increase in successful grant awards was not specifically addressed in the report.

Similarly, Wennerås & Wold's investigation shares a parallel circumstance; their study did not extend its analysis to encompass the outcomes of the grant application procedures. The scope of their examination was confined to the assessment of competence scores linked to cumulative journal impact, which revealed a bias against women. Yet, they did not explore the possibility of compensatory mechanisms within other facets of the council's protocols. The outcomes of the council's procedures might be influenced by variables that are not immediately apparent. In addition to the previously mentioned reviewer affiliation or nepotism, these variables could encompass elements such as cognitive proximity (bias as suggested by Sandström [2009]) and policies related to equity and other related factors. However, conducting a more comprehensive investigation into these aspects poses significant challenges. The examination of nepotism on a large scale is unattainable, and an in-depth exploration of cognitive bias would demand substantial resources as well as additional efforts of gathering ad access to data.

The incorporation of performance indicators assumes a pivotal role in comprehending potential gender disparities. Publications hold a central position within the social dynamics of the scientific realm. Regrettably, many studies concerning gender disparities fall short in this crucial regard. A prime illustration is the meta-analysis by Bornmann et al. (2007), which encompassed 66 assessment procedures across 21 instances (spanning six countries). Their findings demonstrated that men held a 7 % higher likelihood of securing grants based on readily accessible data concerning success rates.

Additional research endeavors have involved a comparative analysis of grant applications submitted by men and women, revealing divergent outcomes. For instance, a study conducted by Waisbren et al. (2008) indicate a higher prevalence of success for men in terms of both the number of awarded grants and the corresponding funding amounts. Nonetheless, upon introducing controls for academic rank, Waisbren et al. established a noteworthy shift, demonstrating that men and women exhibit equal proficiency in securing

grants. This equilibrium in grant attainment was attributed to heightened political pressures advocating for gender parity and a corresponding increased awareness within research councils.

Analogously, investigations utilizing data from the Australian Research Council (ARC) yielded comparable conclusions. Marsh et al. (2008) revealed a lack of gender-based disparities and a notable absence of bias within the peer review process. The intriguing disparity in outcomes across these various studies prompted Bornmann and Marsh to collaborate in conducting an innovative multi-level meta-analysis, which gave some new insights (Marsh et al. 2009).

The Bornmann-Marsh collaborative research effort significantly enhanced the methodological rigor of the investigation by introducing a crucial distinction between *fellowship applications* (career grants) and *project grant applications* (normal grants). Building on the results provided by Cole (1979) and Fox (1991), it is apparent that the degree of specific information accessible to reviewers about applicants plays a pivotal role in mitigating the influence of gender bias within the assessment process. Established researchers seeking grants often possess comprehensive research track records, which they emphasize as indicators of the potential success of their proposed endeavors. In contrast, fellowship applications frequently originate from early-career scholars who have recently completed their doctoral studies. Evaluating the track record of this latter group in an unbiased manner presents greater challenges, thereby affording more significant leeway for factors such as nepotism and specific variables like gender, academic supervisor, and institutional affiliation to exert influence.

The research undertaken by the Marsh/Bornmann collaboration underscored a fundamental divergence between applications for post-doctoral fellowships and project grants (Marsh et al. 2008), but the research initiative refrained from incorporating performance indicators into their study. Notably, among the limited recent papers that have integrated such controls, the work of Ginther et al. (2016) stands out. Their investigation spanning 2006 to 2010 revealed that prior to implementing controls, both men and women exhibited similar success rates; however, upon introducing controls for research output, women demonstrated a heightened likelihood of securing grants. This finding harmonizes with the conclusions drawn by Sandström & Hällsten (2008). Intriguingly, the disparities in outcomes when compared to the Wennerås & Wold study could potentially be attributed to the distinct subjects of examination – the latter focusing on early fellowships and the former on project grants. This observation will have consequences also for the investigation reported here.

Numerous studies spotlight gender imbalances in the outcomes of council procedures, favoring male applicants. For instance, the Analysis Division of the Swedish Research Council (SRC) has released multiple reports elucidating gender-based discrepancies in success rates within the medical sub-council of the SRC (2006, 2010). Concurrently, their analyses suggest that the outcomes of the natural sciences and engineering council procedures demonstrate a relatively unbiased distribution. It is notable that these studies have primarily concentrated on success rates and have not integrated performance analyses, omitting bibliometric data and thus impeding a comprehensive evaluation of the councils' procedures. Jansson and Jonsson (2009) emerge as exceptions to this trend within the SRC, as their study validated the

findings of Sandström & Hällsten (2008). Their extensive dataset, encompassing approximately 1,200 applicants to the Medical sub-council (of which 40% were women) between 2006 and 2007, incorporated bibliometric analysis without fractional counting. Their results exhibited gender parity when correlating the competence score with the bibliometric profile (Sum of Journal Citation Score).

Their conclusions pointed toward a productivity gap as an explanatory factor for the observed variance in success rates between men and women, a disparity that, over certain years, could reach up to a ten percent differential between the two genders.

1.2 The Equality Shift

However, the gender mainstreaming discourse has exerted a substantial transformative influence on the operational procedures of the SRC in Sweden. A pivotal shift occurred in 2011 when the council introduced a strategy of affirmative action, also termed positive discrimination, within its funding policy. This strategic move aimed to establish equitable success rates and funding levels for both male and female researchers, while taking into account the unique characteristics of the research projects and the manner of support being provided (Ulfendahl 2021: 54; Peer Review Handbook 2020, p. 22).

The adoption of this policy was guided by the Law of Discrimination (SFS nr 2008:567), which stipulated its implementation when a particular field exhibited gender underrepresentation. Specifically, the criterion for gender balance was established at a proportion of 40/60, signifying that the gender composition should ideally fall within this range. When applications from equally qualified male and female candidates vied for grants, this rule was invoked to address the gender gap and rectify the imbalance prevailing in specific scientific and medical domains. Consequently, if women were underrepresented, their applications would be given priority provided their qualifications were commensurate.

The evaluation system employed in Sweden operates on a seven-grade scale to meticulously assess applications, culminating in an overarching grade. When applications secure identical grades, their scientific quality is presumed to be akin, assuming precise evaluations. This approach confers review panels with the authority to prioritize female applicants when parity in grade (score) exists between genders. A parallel approach has been observed in the cases we explore within this study – Austria and Ireland. These countries have adopted comparable policies aimed at ensuring an equitable outcome during the review process. Procedures should, if applied, control against gender bias or, if necessary, override it within an acceptable range.

In the context of this report, our focus shifts to delve deeper into the review process, specifically examining whether the organizational structure of the process exerts any influence on the ultimate outcome and its potential gendered implications.

In order to study the phenomena of *Gender Bias* in the process of panel peer review we are in need of a precise definition of bias based on gender. As is noted in D2.1 report from the Granted project there is a need to clarify the concept of gender bias in contrast to plain gender differences or gaps created by other mechanisms not related to gender (e.g., class, race-ethnicity, geography and alike). The task of the current

report is to empirically investigate whether gender bias is to be detected based on a clear definition and operationalization of the concept and a fairly large set of data points.

1.3 Defining Gender Bias in Peer Review

Peer review is a cornerstone of the scientific community, ensuring the rigor and quality of published research. Panels is one typical way to draw together field experts to debate and discuss a pool of applications in a certain discipline.²⁴ However, while some studies have indicated the presence of gender bias in the peer review process, where authors' gender influences the evaluation and acceptance of their work (see Lee et al. [2013] Bias in Peer Review JASIST) other studies, see above, explain that bias is due to evaluative problems when applicants are young and without a specific and own research line.

The peer review process is designed to uphold scientific integrity by subjecting research to rigorous evaluation. Nevertheless, gender bias can infiltrate this process, hindering the advancement of knowledge and exacerbating gender inequalities in academia. Understanding the underlying factors and implications is crucial for creating a more equitable scientific environment.

There are several possible manifestations of gender bias in peer review:

a. Implicit Bias: Implicit biases, formed through societal norms and stereotypes, can affect reviewers' judgments and evaluations. Gender-based assumptions about research quality or competencies may inadvertently influence reviewers' assessments. [Moss-Racusin et al. 2012], [Wennerås & Wold 1997], [Knobloch-Westerwick et al. 2013];

b. Disparate Evaluation: On the one hand studies have found evidence of different evaluation criteria for male and female researchers, with male-authored papers often receiving higher ratings for perceived competence and significance. [Wennerås & Wold 1997], [c.f. Sandström & Hällsten 2008]. [Bol et al. 2022] find that women are more poorly evaluated by panels but that the outcome is “corrected” by council boards. On the other hand, Squazzoni et al. 2020 detect no evidence for bias when it comes to acceptance of submitted articles. Ceci & Williams (2011) finds that the overall evidence for gender bias is quite weak, the same is concluded in a recent study by Ceci et al. 2023²⁵ studying six STEM domains. In their view the null hypothesis seems more relevant than taking gender bias for granted.

c. Double Standards: Female authors may face higher scrutiny, encounter gender-specific criticisms, or receive biased feedback that focuses on their personal attributes rather than the research content itself. Here the empirical data are of various quality as they are based on self-reporting. This is the case with career breaks reported in applications to funding agencies. Data that seldom are further controlled. Using the data might correct at least a portion of the productivity gap (Zuckerman & Cole 1987 in Scientific American). In

²⁴ As Lamont, 2009, have shown this has frequently also been the case with interdisciplinary areas who used the same type of peer panels but covering several macro areas, e.g., humanities, natural science and medicine.

²⁵ Ceci, Kahn & Williams: Exploring Gender Bias in Six Key Domains of Academic Science: An Adversarial Collaboration. Psychological Science in the Public Interest. doi.org/10.1177/152910062311163

this paper we will use the self-reported data on career breaks due to parenthood to adjust the production figures.

Gender bias could hamper the inclusion and retention of women in academia, thereby perpetuating gender disparities in research careers. Already a rumor of practice of bias in peer review can diminish the confidence and motivation of female researchers, hindering their professional growth and scientific contributions. Also, gender bias can lead to the overlooking of important research questions or the neglect of certain areas of study, impeding the progress and diversity of scientific knowledge.

A number of mitigating strategies have been suggested including actions like the following: Implementation of blind review processes, where authors' identities are concealed from reviewers, can help reduce the influence of gender bias on evaluations. Another is implicit bias training of grant reviewers providing training to raise awareness of biases can help mitigate their impact on review decisions. Panel observers has become a frequent model for checking the assessments in council procedures. Panel composition has been a cornerstone in many countries. Ensuring diverse representation among peer reviewers, including gender and other demographic factors, could promote fair and inclusive evaluations. Already during the 1990s Wennerås & Wold proposed that clearly defined evaluation criteria for reviewers would enhance the objectivity and consistency of assessments, minimizing the potential for gender bias.

1.4 A broad definition of panel work

We propose a broad definition of panel work which includes remote reviewers into the panel process. A more limited and traditional view on this would say that sitting panels do exercise a specific relational dynamic and that this is not the case when remote reviewers are utilized during the process. However, based on the experiences from looking at the two-staged cases we do believe that such a view should be revised. Remote review is a way of stretching the panel process, which can include virtual conferences and other schemes. Standing panels, at least in Sweden, divides the work between members of the panel and these do their work during summer and send their evaluations (white sheets) to the council. That is more or less the same as the remote system, although dressed in the form of panel work. The main difference between systems is that remote reviewers normally do not have the chance of negotiation with the administrative center during the process, which is an option for the standing panel members.

The main idea that follows from these observations is that panel work is not only restricted to deliberation in panel meetings or virtual meetings over the net. Panel work includes also work at remote sites and includes the possibility of informal contacts between members concerning issues like how to handle different situations that might come up during the panel meetings, how to prioritize, and how to round any obstacles. Therefore, we consider stages in the panel process which then involves all types of related work before, during and after the panel meeting.

In the GRANteD report D6.1 on page 31, Schiffbänker et al. (2023) outline the process for the respective Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) under investigation (see Fig 1). The primary distinction between FWF and SFI, on one hand, and SRC, on the other, is the absence of an intermediate stage in the SRC process.

Unlike FWF and SFI, the SRC process lacks project officers overseeing it, and applicants do not have the opportunity to provide or request feedback. Notably, a key aspect affecting our investigation is that the initial reviews, similar to remote reviews, are unavailable. The white sheets detailing each panel member’s evaluation of applications are kept confidential and considered as working material, not adhering to the principle of openness in public affairs—a fundamental principle in Swedish society and governance. Unfortunately, this lack of accessibility hinders a direct comparison with the other cases, creating a limitation in the current study.

Figure 1: Funding processes of the respective RFO in focus

1.5 Data description

The number of applications and reviewers that have assessed these applications are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of number of applications and number of reviewers in in all stages

RFO	Applications	of which Women	Remote Rev	of which Women	Panel sitting	of which Women	No. Panels	Areas of Research
FWF	161	70	306	78	53	20	3	Nat, Med, Eng, Hum&Soc
SFI	243	99	149	30	27	9	3	Nat, Med, Eng, Hum&Soc
SRC	169	81	n.a	n.a.	41	21	2	Nat, Med, Eng
	570	250	456	108	121	50		
		44%		24%		41%		

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The analysis is based on data provided by the respective Research Funding Organizations (RFOs). Specifically, we were granted access to lists of applicants, including information such as age, affiliation, PhD completion date, ORCID identifiers, and rosters of both remote reviewers and sitting panel members. These rosters of individuals have been utilized to compile datasets for publication information, subsequently facilitating the generation of bibliometric scores.

The study is conducted with informed consent from applicants and reviewers in both Ireland and Austria. Swedish data is publicly accessible under the Public Administration Act (SFS 2017:900). Overall, we achieved a 95% participation rate from applicants, ensuring a relatively stable dataset. However, it's important to note that the participation rate for Austria is 86.1%, warranting caution in drawing conclusions for this specific case.

Throughout this endeavor, close to 1,150 bibliometric assessments have been conducted. For applicants, the CVs linked to their proposals have proven instrumental in the identification process within the scientific index of Web of Science. Our investigation has encompassed the employment of three principal indexing databases: SCI-E, SSCI, and A&HCI. We focused on document categories including Articles, Letters, Proceeding Papers, and Reviews.

Presently, Web of Science offers a feature for identifying researchers. By utilizing variables such as affiliation and name variations, we were able to narrow down publications to those authored by specific individuals. Although we lacked access to CVs for reviewers, their current affiliations significantly contributed to the identification process. Supplementary sources like ResearchGate and presentations on university websites also proved valuable. In a few instances involving Chinese names (3), delimiting publications to a single researcher proved challenging. Readers should be aware that various databases employ distinct criteria for defining scientific journals. Web of Science has a distinct and rather narrow definition compared to e.g., Scopus.

For researchers in Ireland the English language is natural and therefore publications in international scientific journals are easier than what it is for Swedish and Austrian researchers. Especially in the latter country there is such a large language community that several publication channels are in German language. Therefore, in addition to Web of Science we have applied *Harzing's Index* based on *Google Scholar* in order to capture the publications. The Age-weighted Cited Records per Author (AWCRpA)-indicator works well in our data set and have been used as Bibliometric Score (z-score normalized) for Swedish and Austrian applicants but is not available for the SFI data (for further information see Sandström 2014, p. 54-55).

Harzing's Index is a bibliometric measure used to quantify the impact and productivity of an academic researcher's publications. It is named after Anne-Wil Harzing, a Dutch professor of international management known for her work in the fields of international business and research evaluation. It calculates a researcher's impact by considering the number of publications and the number of citations those publications have received. It is often used as a complementary measure alongside other traditional metrics like the h-index and the g-index.

Harzing's Index offers a straightforward method to gauge a researcher's overall impact within a particular field or discipline. However, like other bibliometric measures, it does have its limitations. Notably, it does not consider the quality of publications, the relevance of citations, or the varying impact factors of different journals. Additionally, it can be influenced by factors such as self-citations, collaborations, and the unique characteristics of a researcher's field. It's important to acknowledge that the index relies on Google Scholar, which often includes items beyond traditional publications, like curricula. For further examples of “dirty data” in the Google Scholar database and the connected problems, see e.g., Dogan et al. (2016); Delgado Lopez-Cozar et al. (2019).

Despite this, the indicator consistently proves to be highly responsive to publications that reach a broader audience. Therefore, it could work as well as the WoS indicators although it is built in a different manner. Note that the Harzing's Index is implemented solely on the Austrian and Swedish data, but not on the Irish.

2 PANEL PEER REVIEW IN DIFFERENT FORMATS

Several factors contribute to the perpetuation of bias in research funding. These include implicit bias during the grant review process, lack of diversity in review panels, gendered evaluation criteria, and career interruptions due to family responsibilities. This paper will touch upon these factors and their impact on research funding outcomes, but we will also introduce other factors of importance.

To address gender bias in research funding, various organizations and funding agencies have implemented initiatives and policies to promote equity and inclusion. This paper will examine three examples of funding instruments implemented by research councils in Europe complementing the peer review process. Building on the lessons learned from different initiatives, the paper will investigate on these strategies for promoting diversity and inclusivity, and whether they contribute to a fair allocation of research resources. This section delves into the concept of panel peer review, its advantages, challenges, and its role in promoting fairness and objectivity in the assessment of scientific literature.

To maintain the integrity of scientific findings, it is crucial to subject research papers and grant proposals to rigorous scrutiny. Panel peer review, also known as group peer review or collective peer review, has for a long time been seen as an effective approach to achieve these goals. Unlike single-expert review models, panel peer review is said to incorporate the perspectives of multiple experts, thereby providing a more comprehensive evaluation compared to alternative solutions.

The typical process of panel peer review, starting from the submission of a proposal to the final decision, include reviewer selection, review assignment, evaluation criteria, organization and guidance of review meetings, and the final assessment process. A crucial point is the interaction and discussion among panel members, aiming at fostering a collaborative and critical environment. Differences in this process across five core-RFOs are highlighted in Granted Report D6.1., (see Schiffbänker et al. 2023).

The first step in the panel peer review process is the selection of appropriate reviewers. Reviewers are usually chosen based on their expertise and knowledge in the specific field related to the submission. Funding agencies take the responsibility of selecting reviewers, considering factors such as expertise (reviewers should possess relevant expertise in the subject matter to provide insightful and constructive feedback); impartiality (ensuring that reviewers do not have any conflicts of interest with the authors or the content of the submission is vital to maintain objectivity); diversity (a diverse panel with representatives from different institutions, regions, and backgrounds can help reduce bias and bring in varied perspectives). However, how this is done might differ between countries and systems of grant peer evaluation.

Once the panel of reviewers is finalized, the submissions are distributed among them for evaluation. Review assignment can be done by program chair or administrators of funding agencies. Assigning each submission to multiple reviewers allows for a comprehensive assessment, and the workload is distributed among panel members.

The panel of reviewers normally follows predefined evaluation criteria, which may differ based on the type of submission (e.g., career grant proposal, normal grant proposal or program-based proposals). These criteria are established by the funding agency and serve as a guideline for reviewers to evaluate different aspects of the submission. Common evaluation criteria may include: Originality: Assessing the novelty and uniqueness of the research or proposal. Methodology: Evaluating the rigor and appropriateness of the research design or the feasibility of proposed methodologies. Significance: Gauging the potential impact and contribution of the work to the field, and also societal relevance. Clarity and Structure: Assessing the organization, coherence, and overall clarity of the writing. Ethical Considerations: Ensuring the adherence to ethical standards, such as plagiarism and conflict of interest. As will be shown later on, also other criteria might be applied in nationally decided funding programs.

In some cases, panel peer review involves review meetings where the reviewers come together to discuss the submissions they have evaluated. These meetings can be conducted in person or, nowadays more commonly, through virtual platforms. The purpose of these meetings is to share individual evaluations and comments with each other, leading to a broader understanding of the submission's strengths and weaknesses. Discussions are meant to lead to a building of consensus on the final decision for borderline submissions. In other RFOs the panel have a function of controlling the quality of remote reviews.

In case of conflicting opinions among reviewers, the review meeting (sitting) provides a platform to resolve disagreements and reach a collective decision, not always in consensus. After the review process is complete, reviewers submit their evaluations and recommendations to the funding agency deciding board or the general director. Based on eventual feedback received, the decision-making authority makes the final judgment on whether the submission should be accepted, revised, or rejected.

Panel peer review occasionally preserves the confidentiality of both assessors and authors, yet this is not universally practiced. In the Swedish Research Council, for example, panel members and the proposals they assess are not kept anonymous. This lack of anonymity introduces the possibility of biases stemming from the authors' reputation or institutional associations influencing the reviewers' judgments. As a result, it

becomes essential to establish a protocol addressing potential conflicts of interest (social proximity) within systems similar to the Swedish model, as observed in the Austrian assessment procedures. It's worth noting that, as far as our knowledge extends, the issue of conflict of interest does not appear to be a concern in the context of Ireland.

2.1 Different versions of panel peer review

Two fundamental versions govern the process of grant peer review and assessment organization. The first version primarily relies on remote (mail) reviews and subsequent sitting panel discussions for evaluation. This approach draws inspiration from institutions like the NSF in the U.S., where external reviews are key, although the NSF involves a program officer overseeing significant aspects of the procedure. The second model establishes a standing panel comprising 7 to 9 members for each disciplinary domain or multidisciplinary subject. The N.I.H. in the U.S., with its study sections (review groups) operating over an extended duration, serves as a prime example of this model. While these models offer comprehensive and intuitive frameworks, practical implementation reveals numerous variations and challenges. For instance, questions arise regarding the selection of peers (who assumes responsibility for peer identification?) and the treatment of responses from mail reviews (should they be scrutinized or accepted at face value?). Our analysis of three primary case studies showcases distinct approaches to tackling such questions.

Within the scope of the GRANteD project's analysis, it is evident that two of the examined three funding programs adhere to traditional multi-stage decision-making procedures, the NSF model. The SRC employs a NIH-model, with several stages, for evaluation and ranking; however, ultimate funding determinations rest not within the panels, but with the General Director, who acts upon a recommendation from the sub-council's Board.

The initial phase of the process is characterized by a peer review undertaken by remote reviewers for both the Austrian FWF and the Irish SFI. The quantity of remote reviewers enlisted to assess a given application varies based on the specific RFO. Notably, the SFI involves three remote peers in the review of each application, whereas the FWF typically engages two remote reviewers per application (for further information on this see GRANteD Reports D5.1 and D6.1). Also, the SRC have several stages but the first stage – the individual assessment performed by each panel member of the qualified applicants – are hidden due to a secrecy policy. Grades are then negotiated at the panel meeting.

The effective implementation of the review process depends greatly on the critical task of identifying suitable peers. The NIH-model, characterized by panels structured around academic disciplines, provides the advantage of fostering a shared understanding of quality criteria and the necessary proficiencies required for successful execution of scientific projects. However, it's important to recognize that not all research domains can be comprehensively addressed within such a framework. For example, some applied fields of study would include several disciplines and that could possibly result in a hampered review process. Conversely, in the model inspired by the NSF, which involves remote reviewers, there is the potential challenge of sourcing peers who encompass the ideal range of expertise. This situation may introduce

inherent positive biases, resulting in excessively optimistic reviews, or conversely, overly negative assessments stemming from competition-related aversions, such as the perception that similar research has already been undertaken.

The concept of optimal cognitive distance, as initially introduced by Wang and Sandström (2015), finds its roots in the work of Nooteboom et al. (2007). This theory encompasses two fundamental dimensions within the realm of review work. The first-dimension centers on the process of learning, which is intricately linked to the reviewer's capacity for absorption. The second dimension is concerned with cognitive distance, which is contingent upon the degree of novelty and innovation embedded within the proposal. As the reviewer's capacity for absorption reaches its peak, the level of novelty tends to decrease, and conversely, when absorption capacity is lower, novelty tends to increase. The optimal cognitive distance is hypothesized to reside at an intermediary point, somewhat resembling an arm's length, situated between these two extremes.

While the quantification of this phenomenon presents challenges, it is important to acknowledge that bibliographical coupling, while not exhaustive in its coverage, has the potential to shed some light on these intricate dynamics.

In instances where the second model, with a stage of remote review, is employed, there is need for a function that takes care of the pivotal role as the guarantor of an equitable process. This can be done by requesting a third review to mitigate the potential biases (Austria) or to ask for a reply from the applicants (Ireland). Comparing the proximity values between the two models proves to be an intriguing avenue of investigation. It is hypothesized that Model 1 would exhibit a higher capacity to identify representatives who are well-versed in the subject matter and share common reference points, possibly indicated by bibliographical coupling. Simultaneously, employing peers from the same research line may introduce complications, as the "similar-to-me" effect can instigate undue enthusiasm among peers, a phenomenon the Austrian Office (the Büro) might be less inclined to endorse.

2.2 Proximity problems in peer review

The utilization of panel peer review presents numerous advantages. These encompass leveraging diverse expertise, mitigating reviewer bias, fostering consensus-building, and elevating the quality of feedback to applicants. However, like any evaluation system, panel peer review encounters specific challenges. In this paper, we will delve into potential concerns, including conflict of interest, often referred to as 'nepotism' or friendship between the applicant and the reviewer [Wennerås & Wold 1997]. In this context, we will term this the *social proximity* challenge.

Another is the *cognitive proximity* challenge – sometime called the *similar-to-me-effect* [Banal-Estanol et al. 2023] – which involves a reviewer bias for those applicants who explore the similar lines of research. Another challenge arises from potential bias due to *geographical proximity*, where reviewers may exhibit bias towards individuals from the same university [Pfeffer et al., 1976; see also Sandström, 2012]. However, in the present version of the report, we will not consider this factor. Instead, we have implemented a

reputation factor to examine the influence of affiliation. Does being affiliated with a high-ranked university result in higher ratings even if the individual's performance is lower?

There are several possible small-group problems among panel members, conflicts that might hamper the work, the possibility of dominant opinions, and the risk of reviewer fatigue. Obviously, panel peer review offers an opportunity for the promotion of fairness and diversity in academic evaluations. By involving experts from diverse backgrounds and regions, the potential for unconscious biases can be minimized.

The lack of conflict-of-interest reports from Ireland could depend on the specific version of the peer review process that have been developed by the SFI in Ireland; there is seldom bias based on affiliation.

2.3 Research Design: three versions of review work in three countries

The panel process data collected in the Granted project cover the three versions of review work at European research councils.

The strategy applied starts with descriptive statistics for each version and country concerning merit scores and grant success. From that we focus on controlling for performance and use regression analysis with several different indicators. Which one of these can best mimic the peer review process? Are the peers sensitive to the performance of applicants and do they rank them according to performance indicators?

In our analysis, we lack an indicator that accurately reflect the scientific quality of the proposal, such as exploration versus exploitation, novelty, and disruption. This inherent difficulty means we will have to accept a level of uncertainty, considering this as a significant factor accounting for much of the unexplained variance in our models.

Our focus is to conduct a more in-depth exploration of bias types that can be categorized as fraudulent behavior. We aim to assess the impact of various factors such as conflict of interest (social proximity), cognitive proximity, and affiliation prestige. Our analysis will scrutinize the potential roles these factors may have at each stage of the review process.

2.4 Descriptive statistics

The following three Tables display descriptive statistics categorized by gender and country. Subsequently, additional statistics concerning grant success (outcome) are presented for each respective country. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are prominently highlighted in bold and as percentages.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics per gender (Sweden)

Variable	Female	N	Min	Max	Median	Mean	Sd	P-value
Grant Success	Male	88	0	1.000	0.000	0.273	0.448	34.35%
	Female	81	0	1.000	0.000	0.210	0.410	
Grade (Merit)	Male	88	3	7.000	5.000	4.864	0.996	40.02%
	Female	81	3	7.000	5.000	4.753	0.916	
Grade (Quality)	Male	88	2	6.000	5.000	4.739	1.150	3.91%
	Female	81	0	7.000	4.000	4.407	1.170	
Grade (Overall)	Male	88	2	6.000	5.000	4.739	1.067	21.11%
	Female	81	0	7.000	5.000	4.531	1.163	
Academic Age	Male	88	0	3.000	1.000	0.693	0.764	77.73%
	Female	81	0	2.000	1.000	0.627	0.653	
High Rank Univ	Male	88	0	1.000	1.000	0.739	0.442	43.41%
	Female	81	0	1.000	1.000	0.790	0.410	
Social Proximity	Male	88	0	1.000	0.000	0.170	0.378	5.89%
	Female	81	0	1.000	0.000	0.074	0.264	
Cognitive Proximity	Male	88	0	0.050	0.001	0.006	0.011	13.40%
	Female	81	0	0.041	0.000	0.003	0.006	
ΣNJCS	Male	88	0	72.212	3.513	6.685	10.433	1.90%
	Female	81	0	20.075	1.664	3.598	4.914	
AWCRpA	Male	88	0	140.850	9.245	16.019	23.079	1.15%
	Female	81	0	254.780	5.130	12.611	30.090	

Note: P-Value of Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney-Test

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics per gender (Austria)

Variable	Female	n	min	max	median	mean	sd	P
Grant Success	Male	91	0.0	1.000	0.000	0.264	0.443	27.91%
	Female	70	0.0	1.000	0.000	0.343	0.478	
Grade (Merit)	Male	91	1.0	4.000	3.500	3.308	0.722	55.51%
	Female	70	1.5	4.000	3.500	3.386	0.655	
Grade (Quality)	Male	91	0.5	4.000	3.000	3.066	0.889	22.26%
	Female	70	0.5	4.000	3.000	2.900	0.915	
Grade (Overall)	Male	91	0.0	4.000	3.500	3.005	0.932	37.28%
	Female	70	0.5	4.000	3.000	2.936	0.838	
Academic Age	Male	91	0.0	9.000	3.000	2.762	1.754	23.28%
	Female	70	0.0	7.000	2.333	2.436	1.745	
High Rank Univ	Male	91	0.0	1.000	0.000	0.451	0.500	2.55%
	Female	70	0.0	1.000	1.000	0.629	0.487	
Cognitive Proximity	Male	91	0.0	0.112	0.002	0.010	0.019	7.52%
	Female	70	0.0	0.227	0.000	0.009	0.031	
ΣNJCS	Male	91	0.0	61.104	7.228	9.323	10.423	1.44%
	Female	70	0.0	32.241	3.327	5.577	6.366	
AWCRpA	Male	91	0.0	78.820	10.540	13.799	13.606	3.42%
	Female	70	0.0	84.430	6.620	10.600	13.588	

Note: P-Value of Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney-Test

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics per gender (Ireland)

Variable	Female	n	min	max	median	mean	sd	P
Grant Success	Male	144	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.222	0.417	58.6%
	Female	99	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.253	0.437	
Grade (Merit)	Male	144	2.000	5.000	4.167	4.060	0.611	30.1%
	Female	99	2.000	5.000	4.167	4.025	0.533	
Grade (Quality)	Male	144	1.000	5.000	4.000	3.890	0.710	31.7%
	Female	99	1.500	5.000	4.000	3.847	0.663	
Grade (Overall)	Male	144	1.333	4.917	4.083	3.931	0.642	61.2%
	Female	99	2.056	4.833	4.056	3.937	0.562	
Academic Age	Male	144	3.000	38.000	12.000	13.188	7.279	14.2%
	Female	99	3.000	39.000	14.000	14.313	7.286	
High Rank Univ	Male	144	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.486	0.502	1.8%
	Female	99	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.333	0.474	
Cognitive Proximity	Male	144	0.000	0.161	0.002	0.009	0.018	45.6%
	Female	99	0.000	0.178	0.003	0.009	0.020	
ΣNJCS	Male	144	0.000	399.487	27.450	45.334	56.808	26.6%
	Female	99	0.379	123.852	24.001	33.230	27.559	

Note: P-Value of Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney-Test

Table 5. Descriptive statistics per grant success (Sweden)

Variable	Granted	n	min	max	median	mean	sd	P
Grade (Merit)	No	128	3	6.000	4.000	4.500	0.823	40.02%
	Yes	41	4	7.000	6.000	5.780	0.652	
Grade (Quality)	No	128	0	6.000	4.000	4.148	0.997	3.91%
	Yes	41	5	7.000	6.000	5.927	0.346	
Grade (Overall)	No	128	0	6.000	4.000	4.219	0.939	21.11%
	Yes	41	5	7.000	6.000	5.951	0.312	
Academic Age	No	128	0	3.000	1.000	0.664	0.735	77.73%
	Yes	41	0	2.000	1.000	0.652	0.641	
High Rank Univ	No	128	0	1.000	1.000	0.766	0.425	43.41%
	Yes	41	0	1.000	1.000	0.756	0.435	
Social Proximity	No	128	0	1.000	0.000	0.141	0.349	5.89%
	Yes	41	0	1.000	0.000	0.073	0.264	
Cognitive Proximity	No	128	0	0.050	0.000	0.004	0.009	13.40%
	Yes	41	0	0.041	0.001	0.005	0.010	
ΣNJCS	No	128	0	72.212	1.856	4.412	8.236	1.90%
	Yes	41	0	35.734	6.605	7.683	8.450	
AWCRpA	No	128	0	254.780	6.725	13.285	26.253	1.15%
	Yes	41	0	140.850	8.430	17.821	27.881	

Note: P-Value of Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney-Test

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Table 6. Descriptive statistics per grant success (Austria)

Variable	Granted	n	min	max	median	mean	sd	P
Grade (Merit)	No	113	1.00	4.000	3.500	3.159	0.720	55.51%
	Yes	48	3.00	4.000	4.000	3.771	0.357	
Grade (Quality)	No	113	0.50	4.000	3.000	2.664	0.870	22.26%
	Yes	48	3.00	4.000	4.000	3.771	0.291	
Grade (Overall)	No	113	0.00	4.000	3.000	2.637	0.841	37.28%
	Yes	48	3.00	4.000	4.000	3.771	0.309	
Academic Age	No	113	0.00	9.000	3.000	2.569	1.782	23.28%
	Yes	48	0.00	7.000	2.833	2.741	1.694	
High Rank Univ	No	113	0.00	1.000	1.000	0.513	0.502	2.55%
	Yes	48	0.00	1.000	1.000	0.562	0.501	
Cognitive Proximity	No	113	0.00	0.227	0.002	0.011	0.029	7.52%
	Yes	48	0.00	0.023	0.002	0.005	0.008	
ΣNJCS	No	113	0.00	61.104	5.640	7.974	9.144	1.44%
	Yes	48	0.00	44.195	3.900	7.036	8.915	
AWCRpA	No	113	0.00	84.430	7.790	12.009	13.489	3.42%
	Yes	48	0.33	78.820	10.615	13.347	14.117	

Note: P-Value of Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney-Test

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Table 7. Descriptive statistics per grant success (Ireland)

Variable	Granted	n	min	max	median	mean	sd	P
Grade (Merit)	No	186	2.000	5.000	4.000	3.923	0.584	30.1%
	Yes	57	3.333	5.000	4.500	4.447	0.331	
Grade (Quality)	No	186	1.000	5.000	3.833	3.684	0.663	31.7%
	Yes	57	3.250	5.000	4.500	4.488	0.316	
Grade (Overall)	No	186	1.333	4.833	3.917	3.775	0.592	61.2%
	Yes	57	3.333	4.917	4.500	4.453	0.297	
Academic Age	No	186	3.000	38.000	12.125	13.154	6.733	14.2%
	Yes	57	3.000	39.000	14.000	15.253	8.736	
High Rank Univ	No	186	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.403	0.492	1.8%
	Yes	57	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.491	0.504	
Cognitive Proximity	No	186	0.000	0.178	0.002	0.009	0.021	45.6%
	Yes	57	0.000	0.057	0.004	0.009	0.013	
ΣNJCS	No	186	0.000	399.487	23.850	37.404	47.964	26.6%
	Yes	57	1.476	229.413	40.987	50.188	44.678	

Note: P-Value of Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney-Test

3 METHODS

3.1 Regression analysis

The study uses linear regression to explain the merit and quality grades assigned to the applications by the reviewers. Additionally, it uses binary logistic regression to explain grant success.

In Table 10, we present the definitions for all variables employed in the regression analysis. Prior to their utilization in the regressions, we z-score normalized all variables, excluding the dummy variables, to *the specific panel handling* the application.²⁶:

$$\frac{x - \mu_p}{\sigma_p}$$

here x represents the variable value, μ_p denotes the average of the variable value for the applicable panel, and σ_p represents the standard deviation of the variable value for the applicable panel. This normalization approach addresses the heterogeneity present in the investigation due to panel differences.

²⁶ In the case of Ireland, we have defined two artificial panels based on the priority area: medical (Priority Area E - Medical Devices; Priority Area F – Diagnostics; Priority Area G - Therapeutics) and other.

Table 8. Regression variables and definitions

Variable	Definition
Grant Success	Final decision – granted (1) vs. rejected (0).
Grade (Merit)	The grade assigned by the panel/reviewer to the application in relation to the scientific merits of the PI. For Austria and Ireland, the average of the grades assigned by the remote reviewers have been used. For Austria (where 1 is the top grade), the grade is defined as 5 minus the assigned grade.
Grade (Quality)	The grade assigned by the panel/reviewer to the application in relation to the quality of the application. For Austria and Ireland, the average of the grades assigned by the remote reviewers have been used. For Austria (where 1 is the top grade), the grade is defined as 5 minus the assigned grade.
Grade (Overall)	For Sweden, the overall grade assigned by the panel/reviewer to the application. For Austria, 5 minus the average of the final assessment (abschließende beurteilung) assigned by the remote reviewers. For Ireland, the average of all the grades assigned by the remote reviewers.
ΣNJCS	The sum of the PI's normalized journal citation score, for publications published 2011-2020; see further details below.
ΣNJCS (ln)	Natural logarithm of Σ NJCS + 1.
AWCRpA	AWCRpA stands for Age-Weighted Citation Records per Author. Available from the app "Publish or Perish" based on Google Scholar database; see further details below. This indicator is not available in the Ireland dataset.
AWCRpA (ln)	Natural logarithm of AWCRpA + 1.
Cognitive Proximity (c-prox)	The average cosine normalized bibliographic coupling (0 – 1) between the PI and the reviewers handling the assessment (Sweden: the reviewers in the applicable panel; Ireland/Austria: the applicable remote reviewers).
Academic Age	Full years from the PhD dissertation of the PI to the end of the calendar year when the application was registered (2020/2021), minus the number of months that the PI has been absent for care responsibilities (as specified in the application), but at least zero.
High Rank Univ	A dummy variable that indicates if the PI is at a top 200 ranked university according to THE ranking of World Universities (1) or not (0); see further details below.
Social Proximity (s-prox)	A dummy variable that indicates if any review member has registered a conflict of interest (social proximity) in relation to the applicant(s). This indicator is not available in the Ireland dataset.
Same Gender	A dummy variable that indicates if the PI and the applicable reviewer are either both men or both women.

For each of the regressions, we have used a stepwise procedure (adding and removing variables) to find the model with the best (lowest) Akaike information criterion (AIC). The AIC score enables us to assess the

model's fit to the dataset while guarding against overfitting. It favors models that strike a balance between achieving a high goodness-of-fit score and avoiding excessive complexity by imposing penalties accordingly. In the regression tables, we present a “model 1” that includes only the primary independent variable, a “model 2” that contains all variables, and a “model 3” that is the final model best on the stepwise procedure.

3.2 Normalized Journal Citation Score (NJCS)

Each PI in our study has been thoroughly identified, and information has been collected about the papers (articles, letters, proceeding papers, and reviews) published by the PI between 2011 and 2020 (inclusive) and indexed in the Web of Science (WoS Core Collection; SCI-E, SSCI, and AHCI).

The NJCS of a paper is defined as the average of the field normalized citation scores of all papers published in the same journal, during the same publication year, and with the same document type (article, letter, proceeding papers, or review):

$$\frac{1}{P} \sum_{i=1}^P \frac{c_i}{[\mu_f]_i}$$

where c_i is the number of citations received by paper i , and μ_f is the average number of citations received by all papers indexed in Web of Science (WoS Core Collection; SCI-E, SSCI, and AHCI) with the same publication year, WoS journal subject category, and document type (article, letter, proceeding papers, or review).

To calculate the Σ NJCS for the PI, we aggregate the NJCS for all papers published by the PI during the applicable years. Consequently, the indicator is size-dependent. (See Sandström [2014] for further discussion on the use of bibliometric indicators).

Testing other performance indicators gave the result that Σ NJCS gave the best matching to the peer assessments (see Sandström [2014] for the definition of alternative indicators like the NCSf, FAP, PP10%, and the P-Model based on citation percentiles). These indicators have been used also for as performance indicators for reviewers.

Given the highly skewed distribution of Σ NJCS across PIs, we opted to utilize the natural logarithm of Σ NJCS (with an addition of one to accommodate zeros) in our regression analyses.

3.3. AWCRpA

The AWCR measures the number of citations to an entire body of work, adjusted for the age of each individual paper. It is an age-weighted citation rate, where the number of citations to a given paper is divided by the age of that paper. AWCRpA is the same but fractionalized to one author's contributions. This indicator allows younger and as yet less cited papers to contribute to the performance.

Due to the distribution of AWCRpA over PIs being very skewed, we have used the natural logarithm of AWCRpA (plus one to handle zeros) in the regressions.

3.4 Cognitive Proximity

To measure the cognitive proximity between a PI and a review panel member, we use cosine normalized bibliographic coupling:

$$\frac{C_{ij}}{\sqrt{C_i C_j}}$$

where C_{ij} is the number of unique references used by both the PI and the panel member, and C_i and C_j are the total number of unique references used by the PI and the panel member, respectively. On both sides, we use references from papers (articles, letters, proceeding papers, and reviews) published between 2011 and 2020 (inclusive) and indexed in the Web of Science (WoS Core Collection; SCI-E, SSCI, and AHCI).

To measure the cognitive proximity between a PI and a review panel, we use the *maximum* cognitive proximity between the PI and the respective remote reviewer or review panel members.

3.5 Affiliation prestige

Universities are categorized using a binary dummy variable, divided into two groups: high-ranked and low-ranked. In this case, we utilized the THE ranking of World Universities and defined the threshold for high-ranked universities at the 200th level; below this rank is considered high-ranked (1), while ranks above 200 are considered low-ranked (0). The ranking data for the year 2021 was employed to construct this variable

4 RESULTS

4.1. Regression results of merit scores

Here, we provide a brief overview of the regression results concerning merit scores. As anticipated, there is a significant correlation between bibliometric performance and merit grade, as depicted in Table 9. However, there is no clear indication that gender plays a role in influencing merit grading.

Why is it expected that the bibliometric indicator sum of NJCS could be highly correlated to the merit score? Developing an expert role in a field of research is the same as developing knowledge concerning the differences between publication venues. During the assessment process, which is often time consuming, and a type of extra-effort for the scientific community, the main problem is to assess the proposal where there is always need for deep reading. But, for the merit assessment there are short-cuts which makes the evaluation concise but also quicker, and that is the use of an estimate of journals or conference proceedings in order to find the few that have better publications than the others. This can be done just by looking through a list of publications and an expert do not have to use databases to judge the merit of an applicant. This observed pattern holds true in country-specific analyses (refer to Table 10-12), where bibliometric performance is significantly correlated with merit scoring. Variables such as social proximity and cognitive

proximity do not exhibit a significant impact. However, in Austria, a noteworthy effect emerges when the PI is affiliated with a high-ranked university (refer to Table 11).

Table 9. Regression analysis – what determines the merit grade (Sweden, Austria and Ireland)

Dependent Variable: Grade (Merit)			
Independent Variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
(Intercept)	0.021 (0.055)	-0.135 (0.079)	-0.097 (0.068)
Female	-0.049 (0.084)	0.117 (0.122)	0.017 (0.08)
High Rank Univ		0.234* (0.107)	0.162* (0.08)
ΣNJCS (ln)		0.293*** (0.054)	0.295*** (0.041)
Academic Age		-0.078 (0.053)	-0.08 (0.053)
Female:Academic Age		0.13 (0.082)	0.136 (0.081)
Cognitive Proximity		-0.015 (0.054)	
Female:High Rank Univ		-0.175 (0.162)	
Female: ΣNJCS (ln)		0.014 (0.087)	
Female:Cognitive Proximity		0.038 (0.085)	
Sample-Size	573	573	573
Log-Likelihood	-808.853	-777.565	-778.29
Adj. R-squared	-0.001	0.09	0.094
AIC	1623.707	1577.129	1570.581

*** significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, * significant at $p < 0.05$

Note: Standard Errors in Parentheses

Note: All variables (except dummy) are standardized (z-score) in relation to the applicable panel (see method above)

Table 10. Regression analysis – what determines the merit grade (Sweden)

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable: Grade (Merit)		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
(Intercept)	0.024 (0.106)	-0.165 (0.231)	0 (0.069)
Female	-0.049 (0.153)	0.134 (0.327)	
Σ NJCS (ln)		0.392** (0.131)	0.307*** (0.087)
AWCRpA (ln)		0.188 (0.135)	0.183* (0.087)
Academic Age		-0.136 (0.096)	-0.106 (0.07)
High Rank Univ		0.172 (0.249)	
Social Proximity		0.097 (0.292)	
Cognitive Proximity		-0.041 (0.103)	
Female:High Rank Univ		-0.13 (0.359)	
Female:Social Proximity		0.033 (0.491)	
Female: Σ NJCS (ln)		-0.197 (0.188)	
Female:AWCRpA (ln)		-0.003 (0.184)	
Female:Academic Age		0.086 (0.146)	
Female:Cognitive Proximity		0.062 (0.154)	
Sample-Size	169	169	169
Log-Likelihood	-238.235	-217.855	-219.305
Adj. R-squared	-0.005	0.149	0.187
AIC	482.47	465.709	448.611

*** significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, * significant at $p < 0.05$

Note: Standard Errors in Parentheses

Note: All variables are standardized (z-score) in relation to the applicable panel (see method above)

Table 11. Regression analysis – what determines the merit grade (Austria)

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable: Grade (Merit)		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
(Intercept)	0.019 (0.104)	-0.207 (0.138)	-0.143 (0.123)
Female	-0.044 (0.158)	0.155 (0.235)	-0.038 (0.156)
High Rank Univ		0.466* (0.204)	0.32* (0.154)
ΣNJCS (ln)		-0.123 (0.107)	-0.11 (0.1)
AWCRpA		0.301** (0.11)	0.29** (0.107)
Female: ΣNJCS (ln)		0.453* (0.189)	0.441* (0.184)
Female:AWCRpA (ln)		-0.279 (0.183)	-0.274 (0.176)
Academic Age		-0.092 (0.107)	
Cognitive Proximity		0.095 (0.114)	
Female:High Rank Univ		-0.349 (0.315)	
Female:Academic Age		0.06 (0.163)	
Female:Cognitive Proximity		-0.052 (0.162)	
Sample-Size	161	161	161
Log-Likelihood	-226.896	-216.452	-218.023
Adj. R-squared	-0.006	0.057	0.07
AIC	459.791	458.904	452.047

*** significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, * significant at $p < 0.05$

Note: Standard Errors in Parentheses

Note: All variables (except dummy) are standardized (z-score) in relation to the applicable panel (see method above)

Table 12. Regression analysis – what determines the merit grade (Ireland)

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable: Grade (Merit)		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
(Intercept)	0.021 (0.083)	-0.095 (0.11)	-0.017 (0.078)
Female	-0.052 (0.131)	0.053 (0.165)	0.03 (0.124)
Σ NJCS (ln)		0.372*** (0.08)	0.343*** (0.062)
Academic Age		-0.027 (0.08)	-0.029 (0.079)
Female:Academic Age		0.205 (0.127)	0.19 (0.123)
High Rank Univ		0.158 (0.16)	
Cognitive Proximity		-0.077 (0.075)	
Female:High Rank Univ		-0.03 (0.266)	
Female: Σ NJCS (ln)		-0.098 (0.14)	
Female:Cognitive Proximity		0.071 (0.135)	
Sample-Size	243	243	243
Log-Likelihood	-343.718	-324.348	-325.928
Adj. R-squared	-0.003	0.115	0.122
AIC	693.436	670.696	663.855

*** significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, * significant at $p < 0.05$

Note: Standard Errors in Parentheses

Note: All variables (except dummy) are standardized (z-score) in relation to the applicable panel (see method above)

In the context of Ireland, we have access to well-organized data regarding the gender of both the remote reviewer and the PI, with a substantial number of assessments (totaling 551). To explore whether the gender of the reviewer or the performance of the reviewer evaluated by reviewer quality or experience — based here on Σ NJCS, representing the influence of high-ranked journals on the assessment procedure — has an impact, we included these variables in a regression analysis (refer to Table 13).

Bibliometric performance of the PI demonstrates a strong correlation with the merit scores. Also, the analysis reveals that the variable "same gender" between the reviewer and the PI holds no significant importance, applicable to both female and male PIs. However, having a female reviewer positively influences the merit grading. Conversely, if the PI is evaluated by a high-performing reviewer, this seems to have a negative effect on the merit score for both genders of PIs. Interestingly, an interaction effect emerges in connection with longer academic experience, as measured by academic age. This factor contributes positively to higher scores for female PIs.

Moreover, in this analysis, no correlation is found between the merit score and cognitive proximity, as measured through bibliographic coupling.

It should be noted that gender has no significant effect also in the analysis at the reviewer level, as displayed in Table 13.

Table 13. Regression analysis – what determines the merit grade (Ireland; reviewer level)

	Dependent Variable: Grade (Merit)		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
(Intercept)	4.067*** (0.045)	3.475*** (0.183)	3.481*** (0.162)
Same Gender	-0.026 (0.058)	-0.068 (0.068)	
Female (PI)		0.199 (0.288)	0.01 (0.221)
High Rank Univ (PI)		0.125 (0.072)	0.117* (0.058)
Female (Reviewer)		0.248*** (0.068)	0.257*** (0.067)
Academic Age (PI)		-0.004 (0.005)	-0.004 (0.005)
ΣNJCS (In) (PI)		0.214*** (0.04)	0.219*** (0.039)
ΣNJCS (In) (Reviewer)		-0.031 (0.031)	-0.051* (0.025)
Female (PI):Academic Age (PI)		0.019* (0.008)	0.019* (0.008)
Female (PI): ΣNJCS (In) (PI)		-0.084 (0.069)	-0.094 (0.065)
Cognitive Proximity		-0.709 (2.769)	
Female (PI):High Rank Univ (PI)		-0.027 (0.12)	
Female (PI):Female (Reviewer)			
Female (PI):Same Gender			
Female (PI):Cognitive Proximity		2.332 (4.18)	
Female (PI): ΣNJCS (In) (Reviewer)		-0.064 (0.054)	
Sample-Size	551	551	551
Log-Likelihood	-565.414	-527.288	-528.481
Adj. R-squared	-0.001	0.108	0.113
AIC	1136.828	1084.577	1076.962

*** significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, * significant at $p < 0.05$

Note: Standard Errors in Parentheses

Note: All variables (except dummy) are standardized (z-score) in relation to the applicable panel (see method above)

It's important to note that the adjusted r^2 values of the regressions in Table 9 – 13 are notably low, implying that the inclusion of additional variables would be necessary for a more comprehensive explanation of the grading.

4.2 Investigating panel peer review by following the stages of the process

In Tables 14 to 16, we present the scoring process at various stages of the panel peer review. Beginning with Table 14, we focus on the Swedish case, which encompasses fewer stages in the panel process due to the exclusion of first assessment scores (deemed as working material and therefore not accessible). In the initial row, we provide the count of applications per gender, with 81 female PIs and 88 male PIs. The subsequent row displays the panel's grading utilizing three levels based on the 7-grade overall scale employed by the SRC: lower than 5, level 5, and higher than 5 for both male and female applicants. Following this, we present the grant success determined by the board or the general director for each gender/grade group, and the last row shows the total success rate per gender. The findings reveal that more women receive a lower score (< 5), although the disparities at higher levels are relatively minor and statistically insignificant. Specifically, 92% of highly scored men achieved grant success compared to 94% of highly scored women. As showed in Table 2 there are no considerable significant differences between men and women. The grant success rates mirror the overall scores and there is, thus, no indicating a biased review process.

Table 14. Routes to Grant Success (Sweden)

	Female PI			Male PI		
Applications	81			88		
Grade (Overall)	< 5	5	> 5	< 5	5	> 5
		39 (48.1 %)	25 (30.9 %)	17 (21.0 %)	32 (36.4 %)	32 (36.4 %)
Grant Success	0 (0 %)	1 (4 %)	16 (94 %)	0 (0 %)	2 (6.3 %)	22 (91.7 %)
	17 (21 % of 81)			24 (27.3 % of 88)		

Note: Unless otherwise specified, percentages are in relation to the preceding count

In the Austrian case, as shown in Table 15, an additional stage in the panel peer review process is revealed through access to remote reviews. In this stage, we utilize a simplified two-level scoring system: scores lower than 3.5 and scores of 3.5 or higher. When comparing these groups in percentages, we assess the recommendation level for funding by the Büro and Referent*innen. Notably, a higher proportion of females with high scores are recommended to the Board for a positive decision. Moreover, in the final round, the Board's decision, a similar disproportion is revealed. The significance of these disproportions is tested below, using binary regression analysis (see Table 17).

Table 15. Routes to Grant Success (Austria)

	Female PI		Male PI	
Applications	70		91	
Grade (Overall)	< 3.5	>= 3.5	< 3.5	>= 3.5
	40 (57.1 %)	30 (42.9 %)	45 (49.5 %)	46 (50.5 %)
Recommended for funding by Büro/Ref	2 (5.0 %)	25 (83.3 %)	2 (4.4 %)	28 (60.9 %)
Recommended for funding by panel	27 (38.6 % of 70)		30 (33.0 % of 91)	
Grant Success	24 (34.3 % of 70)		24 (26.6 % of 91)	

Note: Unless otherwise specified, percentages are in relation to the preceding count

Note: Applications granted a B2 or higher by the panel are considered "recommended"

Finally, we present the results for the Irish case in Table 16. Similarly, we incorporate the remote review results, providing us with insights into all stages of the panel peer review process. Proposals exceeding a defined threshold proceed to the oversight panels, as indicated in row two, where approximately 45% of all proposals are sifted away. In row four, we present data on the number of proposals with overall grades below 4 and 4 or higher, categorized by gender. Comparing the proportions in row four and five provides insight into the sitting panels' influence over the process. While the recommendation and grant success rate are very similar for female and male PIs, a higher proportion of women with low scores (≤ 4) received a recommendation for funding from the sitting panel members—over 50% for women compared to 20% for men. However, binary regression analysis reveals no significant effect of gender on grant success when controlling for the overall grade (see Table 17).

Table 16. Routes to Grant Success (Ireland)

	Female PI		Male PI	
Applications	99		144	
Qualified (not sifted)	56 (56.6 %)		79 (54.9 %)	
Grade (Overall)	<= 4	> 4	<= 4	> 4
	17 (30.4 %)	39 (69.6 %)	20 (25.3 %)	59 (74.7 %)
Recommended for funding by panel	9 (52.9 %)	31 (79.5 %)	4 (20.0 %)	52 (88.1 %)
Recommended for funding by panel	40 (71.4 % of 56)		56 (70.9 % of 79)	
Grant Success	25 (44.6 % of 56)		32 (40.5 % of 79)	

Note: Unless otherwise specified, percentages are in relation to the preceding count

To further analyze the consistency between overall grades and grant success, we present a binary regression analysis in Table 17 with grant success (final round) as the dependent variable, controlling for overall grades. Naturally, the pseudo-R-squares obtained have the potential to be high, given the inclusion of the overall grade in the regression; anything less would be surprising. In the Swedish case, such overall grades results from negotiations within the panel, while in the Austrian case, each remote reviewer assigns an overall grade. In the Irish case, there is no overall grade, instead we have used an average of the three scores (merit, program, and impact). Notably, the R-square is lower for the Irish case which might indicate that such an unweighted average does not properly reflect the individual impact of each grade.

In the Austrian case, there is a notable effect of the female gender, as affirmed by the average marginal effect analysis illustrated in Figure 2.

Table 17. Regression analysis – consistency between overall grade and grant success

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

Dependent Variable: Grant Success				
	All	Sweden	Austria	Ireland
(Intercept)	-3.382*** (0.336)	-5.406*** (1.089)	-3.68*** (0.707)	-2.702*** (0.399)
Female	0.569 (0.291)	-0.525 (0.929)	1.215* (0.558)	0.516 (0.394)
Grade (Overall)	4.201*** (0.393)	7.024*** (1.188)	4.808*** (0.87)	3.014*** (0.457)
Sample-Size	573	169	161	243
Log-Likelihood	-161.252	-18.82	-46.22	-85.379
Pseudo R-squared	0.504	0.799	0.529	0.355
AIC	328.504	43.641	98.44	176.758

*** significant at $p < 0.001$, ** significant at $p < 0.01$, * significant at $p < 0.05$

Note: Standard Errors in Parentheses

Note: All variables (except dummy) are standardized (z-score) in relation to the applicable panel (see methods section)

Figure 2. Average marginal effect of Female PI on grant success considering grades, all three (top left); Sweden (top right); Austria (below left); Ireland (below right)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

4.3. Panel members and remote reviewers' quality (performance)

Membership within the standing panels in Sweden bestows significant prestige and offers substantial rewards, enabling participants to acquire profound insights into the process and potentially enhancing their performance in competitions, surpassing those without such exposure. Although the authors are not privy to the exact prestige associated with panels in Austria and Ireland, a glimpse into their publication achievements indicates a noteworthy trend. Comparing their publication performance to the Swedish panels for the period spanning 2011 to 2020, as delineated in Table 18, it becomes evident that both Austria and Ireland exhibit a superior overall performance.

Table 18. Panel quality based on performance indicators.

Country	Remote reviewers				Sitting panels			
	NJCS	Frac P	FAP	TOP10%	NJCS	Frac P	FAP	TOP10%
AT	29,93	5,91	9,75	56%	39,48	7,71	12,11	56%
IE	71,97	9,15	12,94	92%	68,41	8,40	12,91	73%
SE		n.a	na.	n.a	29,34	4,39	7,40	40%

Note: NJCS=median values; Frac P=paper fractions; FAP=field adjusted production; TOP10%=share of reviewers that fulfill the requirement to be among the 10 percent most productive researchers in Sweden. The last three indicators are explained in Sandström (2014). The first three are based on median values due to skewed data. All values are based on production 2011-2020. FAP normalizes the production to Nordic researchers and is therefore an interesting alternative as there are several areas included.

4.4 Some further notes on the panel process

The Austrian case uses two international mail reviewers (from about 50 countries all over the world²⁷) for each application. In a few cases, when the review is considered as problematic, a third assessor is engaged. In about ten out of 161 proposals only one mail review is received, and the Office (the Büro) finds that it is sufficient; another illustration of the vulnerability of mail review. At the intermediate stage of the process scientific officers (the Büro) and reporters (Referentin and commentator) check for bias and formalities.

The Büro (office) wields significant influence; they take the lead in crafting a summary of remote reviews and possess the authority to modify assessments according to their perspectives. Typically, the Austrian reporters align with the Büro's evaluation, making only minor adjustments to the grading. Consequently, it becomes likely that the reliance on the Büro is tied to its influence in the peer selection process.

The Büro does not seem to hesitate to modify the grade that was proposed by the remote reviewers. Upon a more detailed examination of the specific figures, it becomes apparent that the agency process underwent modifications in its assessment of Grade A determinations within 17 instances out of the total 39 cases. In these cases, the input provided by remote reviewers diverged from either 1-2 or 2-1 (with 1 signifying the highest possible grade). Furthermore, in a substantial 25 out of 39 cases, the recommended

²⁷ Data builds on institutional addresses on reviewer's publications.

grades were not aligned with a 1-1 assessment, which is indicative of a robust Grade A evaluation. Strikingly, the agency even assigned Grade C decisions to ten cases wherein the combined evaluations of the remote reviewers indicated the highest estimation (1-1). This underscores the considerable influence wielded by the agency in shaping these outcomes.

Also, similar to the above, when remote reviewers assign grades 1 and 2 to a proposal, they exhibit high positivity, though one of the two reviewers might offer minor critiques, such as an overly ambitious project timeline. In numerous instances, this concern holds little significance, resulting in the successful grant allocation to both men and women – 24 of each – with such grades (1-1 or 1-2). However, in 30 cases, these points prompt a rejection or a request for revision. Notably, this affects a larger number of male applicants (21) compared to female applicants (9). The latter number is proportional to the number of applicants, but the former is not.

The Büro derives its influence from its mandate to assess reviews, combined with its comprehensive understanding of all applications and the competitive landscape of the applicant pool. This comprehensive perspective is unavailable to remote reviewers, who lack insights into the overall level of competition.

The Austrian council comprises three panels, which engage in discussions regarding the process and ultimately make decisions on whether to propose acceptance or rejection. These panels encompass the broad domains of Biology-Medical, Natural and Technical Sciences and Humanities-Social Sciences. The extensive coverage of these domains contributes significantly to the Agency's prominence within the process. This is due to the potential existence of limited scientific consensus and shared understanding among panel members. In situations where some members emphasize explanatory proficiency while others prioritize functional capability, a genuine consensus becomes elusive, leading to more of a normative consensus.

In contrast to the Austrian model, which relies heavily on the involvement of the Agency administration within its sitting panels, the Irish approach places greater trust in remote reviewers called the “virtual panel”. In the Irish model, each reviewer is responsible for evaluating up to six applications, marking a significant departure from the Austrian procedure. The quantity of reviews allocated per reviewer imparts stability to the review process, aided by the substantial expertise of the reviewers (refer to Table 19).

The remote reviewers assign scores across three dimensions – applicant, program, and potential impact – but not an overarching summary score. Rebuttal can be made by the applicant and is taken back to the three remote reviewers, who then takes this into account in their final assessment. Eventually reviewers can change their review in any direction. As the SFI uses international remote reviewers (from less than 30 countries²⁸) the possible conflict of interest is minimized (but probably not non-existing due to frequency of collaboration in the current science system).

The role of the sitting panelists in the Irish system is to comment on the fairness of the evaluation rather than to express their own perspectives on the proposal or the applicant. Additionally, it is worth highlighting

²⁸ Based on institutional addresses.

that the sitting panels in Ireland consist of multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary members. Consequently, they are broad and lack a shared understanding of objectives and methodologies across diverse scientific pursuits (see further on this Report D6.1 from GRANteD).

In the Swedish model, there is no right to appeal. The SRC, firmly based in their NIH-inspired panel process with a strong confidence in the elected members of the boards, is dependent on a process that excludes any possible conflict of interest. However, as have been shown in several studies, it is relatively common with institutional conflict of interest due to university affiliation or department affiliation.

The Austrian FWF in their ESPRIT program uses national reviewers for the sitting panel (the Board) and these are checked for possible integrity problems. The Austrian system exercise a function for conflict of interest by noting it in the assessment sheets (Befangenheit).

The panel systems in the three countries are summarized in Table 19 below.

Table 19. Characteristics of funding programs and panel system in three countries

Country	Austria	Ireland	Sweden
Funding programme	ESPRIT	Future FP	Int post-doc
Program type	Career grants	High-risk	Career grants
Applicant type (age)	Young	Mid-age	Young
Deciding unit	Board	Board	Board/GD
Panel type	Remote/Sitting	Remote/Sitting	Sitting

Both the Austrian and the Swedish funding is aimed for post-doctoral researchers with no more than five years since their PhD exam. The Irish FFP is more of an all-age program but with a focus on priority areas of research to be supported – therefore a mix of basic and genuinely applied research.

The center of gravity for the case studies are young researchers. This create a strong limitation to the performance analysis which is needed for our analysis of gender bias. Why is this the case? In their meta-analysis of studies of funding grants Marsh et al. (2009) suggest that gender differences might arise because fellowship applicants tend *not to have established a solid track record* in their research. Instead, they are in the beginning of their career and consequently have only a few publications and maybe they have not developed a research track of their own. They could be dependent on their supervisor(s), whether that is the case is hard for the reviewers to disclose. Lacking sound evidence on which to base their judgements, peer reviewers might therefore have been influenced by irrelevant characteristics, e.g., gender or other factors.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The primary aim of the GRANteD project is to comprehensively observe the grant review process and analyze various factors intrinsic to it in several European countries. Drawing insights from research conducted across three distinct countries (Austria, Ireland and Sweden) employing differing forms of panel

peer review, we conclude that no substantiated evidence points toward a gender bias during the assessment of applications for research council grants.

Suggested here is a broad view of the panel peer review process integrating what is done before the panel meeting until the final decision of the Board, or alike. Remote reviews are part of the process and similar to that is the individual assessments that are executed by each panel member and sent to the council before the meeting (even if these documents are considered secret to the public eye). With such a definition it becomes possible to follow the process over stages and to detect if there are major or minor changes of perspective at any specific stage.

While it might appear that the grant competition's outcome would be influenced by the perspectives of peers (both panel and remote reviewers), the actual outcome diverges slightly due to the ultimate decision-making authorities (Boards or General Directors). These decision-making bodies adhere to established and intended policies concerning quotas and related considerations.

The examination of factors associated with panel peer review reveal the following findings:

- Merit grading, which assesses the applicant, correlates with performance in Sweden and Ireland, while in Austria, peer processes seem to be affected both by performance and the affiliation. Notably, the indicator for performance used is size-dependent and relies on journal quality, reflecting the expected recognition for an average article in the chosen publication venues. Journal quality is presumed to be a knowledge possessed by each expert and is not necessarily derived from specific journal rankings or database access.
- As indicated above, we find no gender bias in the review process, at the different stages before the decision of the Board or General Director. But there are redistributions of men and women at the final grant decision stage, probably due to implementation of policy.
- For Austria, the results indicate that female Principal Investigators achieved a grant success level surpassing what could be predicted based on overall grades.
- It should be highlighted that academic age, when accounting for career breaks, do not exert an impact on the review process, but, then again, more than half of the investigated applicants are early career researchers. Social proximities, involving potential conflicts of interest, and cognitive proximity seem not to hold sway over the peer review process.

Nevertheless, our study is subject to certain limitations arising from specific attributes of the datasets obtained from each country (=low number of applicants). In the case of both the Swedish and Austrian data, an improved representation could have been achieved with a span of approximately three years encompassing the execution of the process. Furthermore, a restriction pertaining to the data from these two countries is their focus on the evaluation of applications submitted by early career researchers. This

aligns with observations made a decade ago by Marsh and Bornmann, highlighting a multitude of challenges inherent to peer review within this context of assessing young researchers.

Additional research is warranted, leveraging the existing dataset at hand. In this instance, we have drawn upon the dimensions of "merit of Principal Investigator" and the overall score. In the Irish case we have taken the average of scores which is not a sufficient method, although pragmatic due to time restrictions. However, there remains a reservoir of untapped data for analysis.

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